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IMPLEMENTASI PROGRAM SENI TILAWAH DALAM MEMBAGUSKAN BACAAN AL-QUR'AN DI RUMAH TAHFIDZ AL-GHIFARI DESA SIALANG DUSUN IV

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Abstract

The implementation of the art of reciting the Koran is the application or implementation of reading the Koran using rhythm or song. The purpose of this research is: to find out the model of the method used in carrying out the recitation art program at the Tahfidz Al-Ghifari House. The data used is qualitative data. Qualitative data obtained from interviews and direct observation. The research results obtained, the model and learning method used is by using the tallaqi method (directly).

Keywords: *Implementation, Recitations, and Al-Qur'an*

Abstrak

Implementasi seni tilawah al-qur'an merupakan penerapan atau pelaksanaan membaca al-qur'an dengan menggunakan irama atau lagu. Tujuan dari penelitian ini ialah : untuk mengetahui model metode yang digunakan dalam melaksanakan program seni tilawah di Rumah Tahfidz Al-Ghifari. Data yang digunakan yakni data kualitatif. Data kualitatif diperoleh dari wawancara dan observasi langsung. Hasil penelitian diperoleh, model dan metode belajar yang digunakan yaitu dengan menggunakan metode *tallaqi* (secara langsung).

Kata Kunci: *Implementasi, Tilawah, dan Al-Qur'an*

PENDAHULUAN

Pendidikan ialah suatu hal yang sangat penting dalam kehidupan manusia, karena dengan adanya pendidikan, manusia dapat terarahkan agar menjadi manusia yang berguna bagi bangsa, negara dan agama. Pendidikan bagi kehidupan umat manusia merupakan suatu kebutuhan yang mutlak yang harus dipenuhi sepanjang hayat, dan pendidikan juga merupakan wadah yang sangat penting yang dapat dijadikan sarana perubahan yang paling utama untuk seluruh umat manusia.

Menurut Ki Hadjar Dewantara, pendidikan adalah upaya untuk memajukan bertumbuhnya budi pekerti, kekuatan batin, karakter, pikiran intelek dan tubuh anak dalam rangka kesempurnaan hidup dan keselarasan dengan dunia-Nya. Pendidikan ini dapat diperoleh dari sejak dini sampai akhir hayat kelak. Tanpa pendidikan sangat mustahil suatu

kelompok manusia dapat hidup berkembang sejalan dengan cita-cita untuk maju, sejahtera dan bahagia menurut konsep pandangan hidup mereka. Pendidikan juga diperlukan untuk melihat perkembangan potensi yang dimiliki seseorang dalam meningkatkan keimanan yang dimilikinya.¹ (Robie Fanreza, 2023) Adapun salah satu cara yang dapat dilakukan untuk meningkatkan pendidikan Islam yaitu dengan mengenalkan kepada siapapun mengenai Al-Qur'an.

Al-Qur'an merupakan mukjizat yang telah Allah turunkan kepada Nabi Muhammad SAW sebagai pedoman kehidupan. Sudah seharusnya kita sebagai manusia yang beriman agar mengkaji dan mengamalkan yang terkandung di dalamnya. Al-Qur'an dapat menyembuhkan segala penyakit tersebut. Al-Qur'an juga menjadi rahmat, karena dapat menghasilkan atau mendatangkan keimanan, hikmah (kebijaksanaan), dorongan pada kebaikan, dan kegemaran untuk berbuat baik. Semua hal tersebut hanya dapat diraih oleh orang-orang yang beriman pada Al-Qur'an, membenarkannya, serta mengikuti petunjuk yang ada di dalamnya. Demikianlah Al-Qur'an menjadi *syifa'* dan rahmat yang sebenarnya.

Dipertengahan surat, Allah SWT menyuruh rasul-Nya agar bersabar menghadapi berbagai ucapan orang yang mendustakannya. Biarkanlah mereka mendapatkan azab yang dijanjikan Allah. Sesungguhnya Allah mengancam orang-orang kafir itu dengan azab yang pernah diturunkan kepada Fir'aun dan pengikutnya akibat menentang dan melanggar ajakan rasul mereka. Selain itu, Allah juga memaparkan tentang kedahsyatan hari kiamat agar mereka menjadi takut. Wahai orang yang melipat diri dengan selimut, bangunlah pada malam hari untuk melakukan shalat. Kurangilah waktu tidurmu. Isilah dengan shalat seperdua malam atau kurang sedikit hingga mencapai sepertiganya. Atau tambahkanlah waktunya hingga mencapai duapertiga dari waktu malam itu. Bacalah Al-Qur'an secara perlahan-lahan sehingga jelas huruf dan saat berhentinya. Bacalah dengan bacaan yang baik dan benar

Selain tafsir di atas terdapat pula tafsir lain yang menuturkan bahwa Tartil dalam ayat ini sebagian ulama menafsirkan yaitu membaca dengan perlahan-lahan, menunaikan hak setiap huruf, sesuai kaidah dan dengan suara yang indah. Hal ini adalah pendapat Imam Syafi'i dan mayoritas ulama lainnya yang mengatakan bahwa tartil juga berarti membaguskan suara dengan melagukan.

Tilawah ini mahsyur digunakan oleh para (Qari dan Qari'ah) dalam membaca Al-Qur'an. Akan tetapi seni tilawah dalam membaca Al-Qur'an tidak terlepas dari ilmu tajwid. Mengimplementasikan tilawah dalam membaca Al-Qur'an juga berpengaruh positif terhadap konsentrasi, kualitas belajar, kesehatan dan kesejukan hati bagi para pembaca dan pendengarnya.

Membicarakan soal seni, membaguskan bacaan Al-Qur'an dengan seni Tilawah merupakan salah satu cara yang cukup efektif, sebagaimana yang diterapkan di Rumah Tahfidz Al-Ghifari desa Sialang dusun IV. Dimana karena adanya pembelajaran atau pelatihan Tilawah Al-Qur'an ini, banyak peserta didik yang cenderung termotivasi untuk mempelajarinya. Supaya dalam membaca atau melantunkan *kalamullah* ini peserta didik memiliki kualitas yang bagus dan baik.

Dari permasalahan-permasalahan tersebut tentunya dapat diatasi dengan menggunakan program tilawah, sebelumnya peneliti juga sudah mengetahui bagaimana kinerja program tilawah ini, karena peneliti juga merupakan salah satu peserta didik di Rumah Tahfidz Al-Ghifari. Maka dari itu peneliti tertarik untuk mengangkat penelitian yang berjudul **“Implementasi Program Seni Tilawah Dalam Membaguskan Bacaan Al-Qur'an Di Rumah Tahfidz Al-Ghifari Desa Sialang Dusun IV.”**

METODE PENELITIAN

Dalam melakukan penelitian ini, peneliti menggunakan jenis penelitian kualitatif. Menurut Creswell, J.W. (1994) dalam bukunya yang berjudul: “Research Design: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches, mengemukakan bahwa Penelitian kualitatif merupakan suatu proses penelitian untuk memahami masalah-masalah manusia atau sosial dengan menciptakan gambaran menyeluruh dan kompleks yang disajikan dengan kata-kata, melaporkan pandangan terinci yang diperoleh dari para sumber informasi, serta dilakukan dalam latar (setting) yang alamiah.

Menurut Denzin & Lincoln (1998) dalam bukunya yang berjudul Handbook of Qualitative Research, mengemukakan bahwa, penelitian kualitatif esensinya bersifat ganda: suatu komitmen terhadap pandangan naturalistik-pendekatan interpretatif terhadap pokok persoalan studi dan suatu kritik yang berkelanjutan terhadap politik dan metode positivisme.

Peneliti kualitatif menekankan realitas yang dibentuk secara sosial, hubungan yang erat antara peneliti dan yang diteliti dan mempunyai ciri penelitian yang sarat nilai.

Dari pengertian diatas dapat disimpulkan bahwa penelitian kualitatif adalah penelitian yang bertujuan untuk mendapatkan pemahaman yang mendalam tentang masalah-masalah manusia dan sosial, bukan mendeskripsikan bagian permukaan dari suatu realitas sebagaimana dilakukan penelitian kuantitatif dengan positivismenya. Peneliti menginterpretasikan bagaimana subjek memperoleh makna dari lingkungan sekeliling, dan bagaimana makna tersebut mempengaruhi perilaku mereka, Penelitian dilakukan dalam latar (*setting*) yang alamiah (*naturalistic*) bukan hasil perlakuan (*treatment*) atau manipulasi variable yang dilibatkan. (Prof. Dr. Warul Walidin AK., 2015)

HASIL DAN PEMBAHASAN

Perencanaan di dalam bahasa inggris biasa disebut dengan istilah *planning*, artinya serangkaian kegiatan yang dilakukan di masa yang akan datang. *Lesson Plan* berarti perencanaan pembelajaran. Selain *plan* juga dikenal dengan istilah *design* (baca : desain) yang dapat juga diartikan perencanaan. Ada juga yang mengartikan *design* sebagai “persiapan”.

Didalam buku yang berjudul *Administrative Action Techniques of Organization and Management*, Wiliam H. Newman, sebagai mana dikutip oleh Majid, mengemukakan bahwa “perencanaan adalah menentukan apa yang akan dilakukan. Perencanaan mengandung rangkaian-rangkaian putusan yang luas dan penjelasan-penjelasan dari tujuan, penentuan kebijakan, penentuan program, penentuan metode-metode dan prosedur tertentu dan penentuan kegiatan berdasarkan jadwal sehari-hari”.³⁹ (Nazir, 2013)

Definisi lain menyatakan bahwa perencanaan adalah hubungan antara yang ada sekarang (*what is*) dengan bagaimana seharusnya (*what should be*) yang berkaitan dengan kebutuhan, penentuan tujuan, prioritas, program dan alokasi sumber. Perencanaan disini menekankan pada usaha mengisi kesenjangan antara keadaan sekarang dengan keadaan pada masa yang akan datang yang sesuai dengan apa yang dicita-citakan.⁴⁰ (Dr. Muhammad Sunan, 2017)

Berdasarkan hasil observasi dan wawancara yang dilakukan di *Rumah Tahfidz Al-Ghifari Desa Sialang Dusun IV* menunjukkan bahwa perencanaan implementasi program seni tilawah dalam membaguskan bacaan Al-Qur’an diawali dengan peserta didik yang dengan seni

bertilawah untuk mempermudah membaguskan bacaan Al-Qur'an. Sebab peserta didik yang sudah lancar membaca Al-Qur'an belum tentu seluruh bacaannya bagus. Sehingga untuk bisa menjadikan bacaan Al-Qur'an tersebut bagus dan baik sesuai dengan hukum-hukum bacaan yang sudah ada, peserta didik harus benar-benar serius dalam mengikuti program seni tilawah tersebut.

Berdasarkan hasil observasi dan wawancara yang peneliti lakukan di *Rumah Tahfidz Al-Ghifari Desa Sialang Dusun IV* dengan didampingi ustadz M. Arfan selaku guru tilawah, peneliti menemukan data tentang pelaksanaan program seni tilawatil Qur'an, berikut beberapa langkah-langkahnya :

1. Menentukan jadwal yang sudah ditentukan
2. Penentuan lokasi
3. Memilih metode, media, dan materi ajar

Langkah pertama yang dilakukan dalam pelaksanaan program seni tilawah di Rumah Tahfidz Al-Ghifari Desa Sialang yaitu menentukan jadwal yang sudah ditentukan, dilaksanakan pada hari jum'at pukul 14:00 WIB – 17:00 WIB biasanya diikuti oleh semua peserta didik yang mengikuti program seni tilawah, namun hanya 3 orang saja yang ditentukan oleh Ustadz untuk dibimbing dalam tilawah, mengingat waktunya yang singkat. Selain hari jum'at, jadwal selanjutnya dilaksanakan pada hari minggu yang dimulai dari pagi pada pukul 09:00 WIB hingga sore hari pada pukul 17:00 WIB. Pada hari minggu ini durasi waktu untuk belajar cukup panjang, maka dari itu seluruh peserta didik yang mengikuti program seni tilawah dapat semua di bombing satu-persatu oleh Ustadz untuk membacakan Al-Qur'an.

Langkah kedua yaitu lokasi, pelaksanaan program seni tilawah dilakukan didalam ruangan yang memang sudah ditetapkan khusus untuk belajar tilawah. Pakaian yang dikenakan peserta didik juga bebas yang terpenting menutupi bagian-bagian yang termasuk aurat serta pakaian yang digunakan sopan dan bersih.

Langkah yang ketiga yaitu memilih metode, media, dan bahan ajar, Ustadz disini berperan sangat penting dalam menentukan metode pembelajaran, metode yang biasa digunakan adalah metode *tallaqi* yaitu metode pembelajaran secara langsung berhadapan dengan guru atau disebut dengan *mentoring (face to face)*. Maka dalam pelaksanaannya, peserta didik secara langsung bisa mendengar dan melihat ketiga ustadz mencontohkan tilawahnya di hadapan peserta didik. Cara ini adalah cara paling bagus dan efektif karena peserta didik bisa melihat langsung bagaimana cara menarik nafas, melafalkan makhorijul huruf dan pengeluaran nafas dan ustadz dapat mengatur tempo bacaannya agar peserta didik dapat dengan jelas mengikuti

irama tilawah yang dicontohkan oleh ustadz. Media yang digunakan saat pembelajaran berlangsung ialah Al-Qur'an serta mik, serta *sound system*. Untuk materi ajar, ustadz sudah menentukan 4 lagu yang harus dipelajari ketika pelaksanaan tilawah yaitu biasanya lagu *bayyati, hijaz, nahawand, dan rost*.

Terdapat beberapa hal yang harus diperhatikan dengan baik terkait pelaksanaan program seni tilawah Al-Qur'an agar program ini berhasil hal-hal tersebut adalah :

1. Tajwid. Dalam membaca Al-Qur'an terdapat beberapa aturan yang harus diperhatikan dan dilaksanakan bagi pembacanya. Seperti makhorijul huruf yaitu tempat keluarnya huruf.
2. Naghmah. Memiliki arti lagu atau irama khusus dalam membacakan Al-Qur'an atau seni baca Al-Qur'an
3. Suara. Bagian yang tidak kalah pentingnya dalam seni tilawah Al-Qur'an adalah masalah suara peserta didik, sebagaimana diketahui bahwa suara manusia itu banyak perubahan, sejalan dengan bertambahnya usia atau karena masa yang dialaminya, yaitu dari masa kanak-kanak, remaja, dewasa, tua sampai renta.
4. Nafas. Nafas juga merupakan bagian yang sangat penting dalam seni tilawah Al-Qur'an.

Secara etimologi "evaluasi" berasal dari bahasa Inggris yaitu *evaluation* dari kata *value* yang berarti nilai atau harga. Secara terminologi, beberapa ahli memberikan pendapat tentang pengertian evaluasi salah satunya adalah menurut M, Chabib Toha, mendefinisikan evaluasi merupakan kegiatan yang terencana untuk mengetahui keadaan objek dengan menggunakan instrument dan hasilnya dibandingkan dengan tolak ukur untuk memperoleh kesimpulan. Pengertian evaluasi secara umum dapat diartikan sebagai proses sistematis untuk mengetahui nilai sesuatu (ketentuan, kegiatan, unjuk-kerja, proses, orang, objek dan lain sebagainya) berdasarkan kriteria tertentu melalui penilaian.⁴¹ (B, 2017)

Dari pendapat ahli di atas dapat diperoleh gambaran bahwa evaluasi adalah suatu proses yang sistematis dan berkelanjutan untuk menentukan kualitas (nilai dan arti). Berdasarkan pengertian ini, ada beberapa hal yang perlu kita pahami lebih lanjut, yaitu :

1. Evaluasi merupakan suatu proses dan bukan suatu hasil. Hasil yang diperoleh dari kegiatan evaluasi adalah kualitas daripada sesuatu, baik yang menyangkut tentang nilai maupun arti. Sedangkan kegiatan untuk sampai kepada pemberian nilai dan arti itu adalah evaluasi.
2. Evaluasi juga memiliki tujuan yaitu untuk menentukan kualitas daripada sesuatu, terutama yang berkenaan dengan nilai dan arti. Pemberian nilai dilakukan apabila seorang evaluator memberikan pertimbangannya mengenai evaluasi tanpa menghubungkannya dengan sesuatu yang bersifat dari luar.

3. Dalam proses evaluasi harus ada pemberian pertimbangan (*judgement*).
4. Pemberian pertimbangan tentang nilai dan arti haruslah berdasarkan criteria tertentu.

Berdasarkan hasil Observasi dan wawancara yang telah dilakukan di *Rumah Tahfidz Al-Ghifari Desa Sialang Dusun IV* menunjukkan bahwa kegiatan evaluasi yang dilakukan yaitu dengan cara tes lisan, yang mana tes lisan berupa pembacaan Al-Qur'an dengan melihat Al-Qur'an sesuai dengan materi yang diajarkan ustadz. Ustadz melakukan evaluasi lagu dan pembagusan bacaan Al-Qur'an dalam 1 lagu bisa 3-4 kali pertemuan dan evaluasinya, jika belajar makro maka bisa selesai 4 bulan dengan evaluasi masing-masing peserta didik, lagu yang sering digunakan yaitu lagi *bayyati, hijaz, nahawand, dan rast*.

SIMPULAN DAN SARAN

Berdasarkan uraian di atas yang merupakan perpaduan dari kajian teoritis dengan hasil penelitian data yang diperoleh dari lokasi penelitian serta berpijak pada focus penelitian skripsi ini, maka peneliti memperoleh kesimpulan sebagai berikut :

Perencanaan Implemetasi Program Seni Tilawah Dalam Membaguskan Bacaan Al-Qur'an Di *Rumah Tahfidz Al-Ghifari Desa Sialang Dusun IV* sudah sesuai dengan apa yang telah direncanakan oleh tenaga pendidik di Rumah Tahfidz Al-Ghifari sebelumnya.

Pelaksanaan Implementasi Program Seni Tilawah Dalam Membaguskan Bacaan Al-Qur'an Di *Rumah Tahfidz Al-Ghifari Desa Sialang Dusun IV* pada pelaksanaannya terdiri dari 3 langkah, yaitu menentukan jadwal, menentukan lokasi, dan memilih metode, media dan alat ajar. Jadwal yang ditentukan adalah 2 kali pertemuan dalam satu minggu yaitu pada hari Jum'at pada pukul 14:00 – 17:00 WIB dan pada hari Minggu pada pukul 09:00 – 17:00 WIB. Penentuan lokasi yaitu di salah satu ruangan yang sudah disediakan untuk program ini, serta pemilihan metode *tallaqi*, media berupa Al-Qur'an, mik, dan *sound system*.

Evaluasi Implementasi Program Seni Tilawah Dalam Membaguskan Bacaan Al-Qur'an Di *Rumah Tahfidz Al-Ghifari Desa Sialang Dusun IV* pada evaluasi ini ustadz menggunakan tes lisan dengan melihat Al-Qur'an, yang mana tes lisan dilakukan pembacaan Al-Qur'an sesuai dengan materi yang diajarkan oleh ustadz.

Setelah melakukan beberapa tahapan penelitian, maka dapat dirumuskan saran-saran kepada beberapa pihak antara lain sebagai berikut : Program seni tilawah yang ada pada Rumah Tahfidz Al-Ghifari Desa sialang sudah cukup dikatakan bagus, karena di sana pemilik Rumah Tahfidz sekaligus guru tilawahnya memberikan fasilitas yang memadai sehingga peserta didik yang mengikuti program seni tilawah untuk membaguskan bacaan Al-Qur'an berjalan dengan

baik dan lancar. Selain itu untuk guru tilawah yang diharapkan lebih lagi dalam memotivasi peserta didik agar tetap semangat dalam mengikuti program seni tilawah supaya kedepannya dapat membanggakan keluarga terutama Rumah Tahfidz yang sudah mengasah kemampuannya. Motivasi dari seorang guru itu sangat penting bagi peserta didik, jika tidak ada motivasi dan tidak ada guru dalam melaksanakan kegiatan ini maka tidak akan berjalan dengan lancar program tilawah tersebut, sebaliknya juga jika tidak ada peserta didik yang mengikuti program ini maka tidak akan berjalan lancar juga program tersebut. Saran peneliti untuk pemilik Rumah Tahfidz ialah Ustadz harus benar-benar memperhatikan selalu fasilitas yang digunakan peserta didik, serta memungkinkan menambah lagi fasilitas yang jauh lebih lengkap dan baik. Serta guru dan peserta didik harus mempunyai kegigihan yang lebih untuk mengikuti dan mempelajari program seni tilawah dalam mebaguskan bacaan Al-Qur'an ini

Untuk keberhasilan peserta didik, diharapkan untuk lebih istiqomah dan aktif dalam mengikuti program seni tilawah guna untuk mebaguskan bacaan Al-Qur'an lebih baik lagu, mengembangkan bakat dan potensinya. Karena dari program ini dapat dilihat sejauh mana potensi seseorang untuk terus mengembangkan bakatnya terutama dibidang Al-Qur'an yaitu Tilawah.

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PENGARUH PROGRAM INDONESIA PINTAR (PIP) TERHADAP MOTIVASI BELAJAR SISWA DI SMP NEGERI 1 DOLOK MERAWAN KECAMATAN DOLOK MERAWAN KABUPATEN SERDANG BEDAGAI TAHUN AJARAN 2021/2022

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the Learning Motivation of Students who received the Smart Indonesia Program (PIP) at SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan and the Effect of the Smart Indonesia Program (PIP) on Student Motivation at SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan. This research uses quantitative methods. The results of this study, the learning motivation of students at SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan is quite high, the relationship obtained through the Product Moment correlation test between the influence of the Smart Indonesia Program (PIP) and the learning motivation of students at SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan has a positive correlation or a positive correlation. walk in the same direction. Through the Product Moment table r value can be interpreted at a significant level of 0.297. By comparing the magnitude of r_{count} with r_{table} , it can be seen that the value of $r_{count} > r_{table}$ is $0.4577 > 0.297$. Thus the hypothesis taken is H_a , which means that there is a significant influence between the learning motivation of students who receive assistance from the Smart Indonesia Program (PIP) at SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan Academic Year 2021/2022. Based on the calculation of the Determinant Coefficient, it can be seen that the influence value of the Smart Indonesia Program (PIP) on student learning motivation at Dolok Merawan 1 Public Middle School is 21%, this means that the variation in student learning motivation at Dolok Merawan 1 Public Middle School is due to the Smart Indonesia Program (PIP), while the remaining 79% is caused by other variables not included in this study.

Keywords: *Influence, Motivation, Learning*

PENDAHULUAN

Pemerintah berupaya meningkatkan akses dan mutu pendidikan kepada masyarakat sebagai upaya meningkatkan kualitas sumber daya manusia yang dapat membangun dan memajukan Bangsa dan Negara agar tercapai masyarakat berilmu, cerdas, berakhlak mulia, berkarakter, sehat, cakap, kreatif, mandiri, bertaqwa, dan berbudi pekerti luhur. Upaya peningkatan akses dan mutu pendidikan maka Pemerintah mengeluarkan Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan Dan Kebudayaan Republik Indonesia Nomor 10 Tahun 2020 tentang Program Indonesia Pintar, Peraturan Sekretaris Jenderal Kementerian Pendidikan dan kebudayaan Nomor 3 Tahun 2021 tentang Pelaksanaan Program Indonesia Pintar Pendidikan Dasar dan Pendidikan Menengah dan Perubahan atas Peraturan Sekretaris Jenderal Kementerian pendidikan Dan Kebudayaan Nomor 7 Tahun 2021 yang memberikan layanan kepada siswa siswi yang sebagian besar dari masyarakat kurang mampu, kurang beruntung serta berada di daerah terpencil dan perbatasan.

Hak dasar warga Negara adalah mendapatkan layanan pendidikan yang terjangkau dan bermutu. Diharapkan dengan bekal akses pendidikan yang bermutu, peserta didik dapat tumbuh dan berkembang menjadi generasi yang unggul, hebat, dan bermartabat. Bagi siswa yang berasal dari latar belakang ekonomi yang kurang beruntung, akses pendidikan yang baik juga diharapkan dapat menjadi instrument pemutus mata rantai kemiskinan. Dalam konteks ini, Pemerintah menetapkan kebijakan afirmatif akses pendidikan khususnya bagi siswa yang berasal dari keluarga kurang mampu secara ekonomi. Hal ini sebagaimana Pemerintah mengeluarkan Instruksi Presiden Nomor 7 Tahun 2014 yang menginstruksikan kepada menteri, Kepala Lembaga Negara, dan kepala Pemerintah Daerah untuk melaksanakan Program Keluarga Produktif melalui Program Simpanan Keluarga Sejahtera (PKS), Program Indonesia Sehat (PIS) dan Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP).

Pemerintah dalam bidang pendidikan mengeluarkan Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) yang merupakan bantuan berupa uang dari pemerintah yang diberikan kepada peserta didik yang orang tuanya tidak dan/atau kurang mampu membiayai pendidikannya, sebagai kelanjutan dan perluasan sasaran dari program Bantuan Siswa Miskin (BSM). Siswa yang mendapatkan Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) dengan beberapa syarat yang salah satunya mempunyai Kartu Indonesia Pintar (KIP) bertujuan agar siswa mendapatkan fasilitas pendidikan yang layak, semangat dalam belajar dan terus melanjutkan sekolah. Dengan bantuan Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) diharapkan siswa di Indonesia dapat memutuskan mata rantai kemiskinan dan meningkatkan derajat keluarga hingga derajat Indonesia dimata Negara lain.

Pemerintah juga ingin menurunkan angka buta aksara di Indonesia dengan bantuan dalam bidang pendidikan. Dalam Islam juga mewajibkan setiap muslim dan muslimah untuk menuntut ilmu dan terus belajar dan membaca, sesuai dengan firman Allah Surah Al- Alaq ayat 1 – 5 yang berbunyi:

اقْرَأْ بِاسْمِ رَبِّكَ الَّذِي خَلَقَ ﴿١﴾ خَلَقَ الْإِنْسَانَ مِنْ عَلَقٍ ﴿٢﴾ اقْرَأْ وَرَبُّكَ الْأَكْرَمُ ﴿٣﴾ الَّذِي عَلَّمَ بِالْقَلَمِ ﴿٤﴾ عَلَّمَ الْإِنْسَانَ مَا لَمْ يَعْلَمْ ﴿٥﴾

Bacalah dengan (menyebut) nama Tuhanmu yang Menciptakan (1). Dia telah menciptakan manusia dari segumpal darah (2). Bacalah, dan Tuhanmulah yang Maha pemurah (3). Yang mengajar (manusia) dengan perantaran kalam (Maksudnya: Allah mengajar manusia dengan perantaraan tulis baca)(4). Dia mengajar kepada manusia apa yang tidak diketahuinya (5). (Q.S. Al-Alaq [96]: 1-5)

Surat Al-Alaq ayat 1-5, menerangkan bahwa Allah SWT menciptakan manusia dari benda yang hina dan memuliakannya dengan mengajar membaca, menulis dan memberinya pengetahuan. Dengan kata lain, bahwa manusia mulia di hadapan Allah SWT apabila memiliki pengetahuan, dan pengetahuan bisa dimiliki dengan jalan belajar. Allah SWT menyuruh manusia untuk belajar dan berfikir. *Iqra* yang berarti bacalah adalah sebagai simbol pentingnya pendidikan bagi umat Islam karena pendidikan merupakan masalah hidup yang mewarnai kehidupan manusia dan mengharuskan untuk mencarinya yang tidak terbatas pada usia, tempat, jarak, waktu dan keadaan.

Lembaga Pendidikan didalamnya terdapat proses belajar dan mengajar, dalam hal belajar ada faktor yang mempengaruhi tinggi rendahnya motivasi, salah satunya adalah kemiskinan yang menyebabkan ketidaklengkapan fasilitas dalam menunjang kegiatan belajar. Fakta tersebut memperlihatkan bahwa berjalannya program Pemerintah yaitu Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) dalam menunjang kegiatan belajar siswa kurang mampu.

Data lapangan yang didapat penulis dalam observasi dan wawancara dengan Wakil Kepala Sekolah SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan dan siswa yang mendapatkan dana bantuan Program Indonesia Pintar bahwa siswa yang mendapat dana Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) di Kecamatan Dolok Merawan, ada siswa yang mendapatkan bantuan Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) tidak menggunakan dana tersebut sesuai dengan tujuan pendidikan seperti menghabiskannya untuk kepentingan pribadi, membeli kuota internet untuk bermain game online maupun media sosial, belanja beras, belanja sandal, pergi ketempat wisata, dan tidak menggunakan dana PIP untuk meningkatkan pengetahuan dalam konteks pendidikan. Terdapat juga siswa yang tidak menunjukkan semangat dan motivasi dalam belajar walaupun mereka mendapatkan dana Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) tersebut.

Peneliti tertarik untuk mengungkapkan fenomena dana Program Indonesia Pintar terhadap Motivasi belajar Siswa terkhususnya di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan kedalam sebuah bentuk penelitian. Peneliti tertarik meneliti fenomena ini pada siswa SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan karena adanya bantuan dana Program Indonesia Pintar yang sasarannya pada siswa SMP negeri 1 Dolok Merawan. Sehingga perlu dilakukan suatu penelitian ilmiah bagaimana pengaruh Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) yang mereka terima, apakah dapat meningkatkan motivasi belajar mereka. Maka penulis merasa terdorong untuk mengkaji dan meneliti dengan judul: Pengaruh Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) Terhadap Motivasi Belajar Siswa di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan.

METODE PENELITIAN

Peneliti menggunakan jenis penelitian Kuantitatif dengan metode survey. Penelitian ini menggunakan statistika dan data - data variabel yang penjumlahannya dapat diukur hasilnya. Seperti yang dikatakan "Sugiyono bahwa data kuantitatif adalah data yang berbentuk angka. Dengan demikian, penelitian ini memungkinkan digunakan teknik analisa statistic untuk mengolah data. Penelitian ini juga termasuk jenis penelitian *ex post facto*. Menurut Sukardi penelitian *ex post facto* merupakan penelitian dimana variabel-variabel bebas telah terjadi ketika peneliti mulai dengan pengamatan variabel terikat dalam suatu penelitian.

Penelitian dilakukan dengan penelusuran kembali kebelakang untuk mengetahui faktor-faktor yang menimbulkan kejadian itu tanpa memberikan perlakuan atau memanipulasi variabel yang diteliti. Penelitian ini dilakukan untuk mengetahui informasi mengenai pengaruh Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) dengan motivasi belajar siswa di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan. Jika dilihat dari tujuannya, penelitian ini bermaksud menemukan adanya pengaruh Program Indonesia Pintar terhadap Semangat dan Motivasi siswa dalam belajar di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan. Dengan demikian penelitian ini merupakan penelitian korelasi.

Teknik Pengumpulan Data berupa Angket, Metode Dokumentasi dan Analisis Data Penelitian menggunakan Analisa Korelasi yaitu Menganalisis kedua variabel menggunakan Teknik Analisa Korelasi Bivariat dengan rumus *Product Moment* dari Karl Pearson. Analisis Korelasi yang merupakan istilah biasa digunakan untuk menggambarkan ada atau tidaknya

hubungan suatu hal dengan hal lain. Analisis korelasi adalah suatu cara atau metode untuk mengetahui ada atau tidaknya hubungan linear antar variabel. Jika terdapat hubungan maka perubahan – perubahan yang terjadi pada salah satu (X) akan mengakibatkan terjadinya perubahan pada variabel lainnya (Y). Adapun korelasi variabelnya:

Pengaruh Program Bantuan Siswa Miskin (BSM) (X) dalam motivasi belajar siswa (Y).

$$r_{xy} = \frac{N \sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{\{N \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2\} \{N \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2\}}}$$

Keterangan:

r_{xy} = koefisien korelasi antara X dan Y

N = jumlah responden

$\sum YX$ = Jumlah hasil perkalian antara skor X dan Y

$\sum X$ = Jumlah seluruh skor X

$\sum Y$ = jumlah seluruh skor Y

$\sum X^2$ = jumlah dari kuadrat nilai

$\sum Y^2$ = jumlah dari kuadrat nilai

Analisis *Product Moment* dimaksudkan untuk mencari titik nilai korelasi antara variabel X dan Y serta untuk mengetahui kadar eratnya hubungan antara variabel X dan Y di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan.

a. Uji Hipotesis

Uji ini digunakan mengetahui apakah variabel independen (X) berpengaruh secara signifikan terhadap variabel dependen (Y). signifikan berarti pengaruh yang terjadi dapat berlaku untuk populasi (dapat digeneralisasikan). Dapat ketentuan dalam uji hipotesis didalam penelitian ini yaitu:

a. Jika nilai sig < 0,05, atau $r_{hitung} > r_{tabel}$ maka terdapat pengaruh variabel X terhadap variabel Y.

b. Jika nilai sig > 0,05, atau $r_{hitung} < r_{tabel}$ maka tidak terdapat pengaruh variabel X terhadap variabel Y.

Hasil uji hipotesis ditentukan dengan nilai akhir pada rumus *Product Moment* dengan membandingkan besaran signifikan 5 % maupun taraf signifikan 1 % pada nilai hasil akhir *Product Moment* maka peneliti mengacu pada table *Product Moment* (r_{tabel}).

b. Koefisien Determinasi

Koefisien Determinasi (KD) digunakan untuk menyatakan besar kecilnya sumbangan atau kontribusi variabel X (Pengaruh Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP)) terhadap variabel Y (Motivasi Belajar Siswa). Perhitungan Koefisien Determinasi ini dimaksudkan untuk mengetahui besarnya pengaruh Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) dengan motivasi belajar siswa. Koefisien Determinasi dapat dinyatakan dengan rumus:

$$KD = (r_{xy})^2 \times 100\%$$

Keterangan:

KD = Kontribusi variabel X terhadap Y

r_{xy} = Koefisien korelasi antara variabel X dan Y

Uji Instrumen Penelitian

1. Uji Validitas

Sebuah alat ukur dikatakan valid apabila mampu mengukur apa yang diinginkan dan mengungkapkan data dari variabel yang akan diteliti secara tepat. Pengujian validitas dalam penelitian ini menggunakan alat bantu komputer *SPSS Statistic versi 22 for windows*. Variabel dinyatakan valid dapat diketahui dari signifikan dari hasil perhitungan korelasi lebih kecil dari 0,05. Variabel juga dapat dinyatakan valid jika r_{hitung} positif, serta $r_{hitung} > r_{tabel}$.

Tabel 1. Uji Validitas

Item Pernyataan	r_{hitung}	r_{tabel}	Keterangan
Pernyataan 1	0,425	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 2	0,534	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 3	0,347	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 4	0,361	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 5	0,477	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 6	0,480	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 7	0,564	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 8	0,299	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 9	0,677	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 10	0,626	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 11	0,366	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 12	0,626	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 13	0,775	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 14	0,398	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 15	0,615	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 16	0,341	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 17	0,722	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 18	0,673	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 19	0,775	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 20	0,388	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 21	0,485	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 22	0,506	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 23	0,380	0,297	Valid
Pernyataan 24	0,775	0,297	Valid

Hasil uji coba validitas instrument dapat diketahui bahwa instrument dari variabel Penggunaan Program Indonesia Pintar (Variabel X) dan variabel Motivasi Belajar Siswa (Variabel Y) dapat dikatakan valid, karena hasil nilai $r_{hitung} > r_{tabel}$.

2. Uji Reliabilitas

Alat ukur yang baik tidak akan bersifat tendensius atau mengarahkan responden untuk memilih jawaban-jawaban tertentu. Alat ukur yang reliabel (dapat dipercaya) akan menghasilkan data yang juga dapat dipercaya. Pengujian reliabilitas yang digunakan dalam penelitian ini adalah koefisien alfa atau *cronbach's alpha*. "Item pengukuran dikatakan reliabel jika memiliki koefisien alfa lebih besar dari 0,600." Dalam pengujian reliabilitas instrument didalam penelitian ini peneliti menggunakan alat bantu komputer *SPSS Statistic versi 22 for windows*. Adapun hasil uji coba reliabilitas instrument dalam penelitian ini dapat dilihat pada tabel berikut,

Tabel 2. Uji Reliabilitas

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.828	24

Keterangan tabel diatas dapat diketahui bahwa variabel X (Penggunaan Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP)) dan variabel Y (Motivasi Belajar Siswa) memiliki *cronbach's alpha* $0.828 > 0.600$, dengan demikian alat instrument reliabel atau layak digunakan.

HASIL DAN PEMBAHASAN

Responden yang menjadi sampel didalam penelitian ini sebanyak 44 orang. Pada penelitian ini peneliti menyebarkan angket sebanyak 24 pernyataan. Adapun yang menjadi sampel pada penelitian ini yaitu siswa yang mendapatkan dana bantuan Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan. Jumlah siswa yang mengisi angket ini sesuai sampel yaitu 44 responden. Angket tersebut sudah dilakukan uji validitas dan reliabilitas.

1. Pengujian Hipotesis

A. Hasil Uji Analisis Korelasi

Analisis korelasi ini digunakan untuk mencari hubungan dan membuktikan hipotesis hubungan dua variabel bila data kedua variabel berbentuk interval atau ratio, dan sumber data dari dua variabel atau lebih tersebut adalah sama. Dengan ketentuan sebagai berikut:

- Jika nilai koefisien korelasi positif, maka hubungan antara variabel X dengan variabel Y adalah hubungan searah, dengan kata lain meningkat variabel X, maka meningkat pula variabel Y.
- Jika nilai koefisien korelasi negatif, maka hubungan antara variabel X dan variabel Y adalah hubungan berlawanan, dengan kata lain meningkatnya variabel X maka diikuti menurunnya variabel Y.

Menganalisis hubungan kedua variabel digunakan Teknik Analisis Korelasi Bivariat dengan rumus *Produt Moment* dari Karl Pearson yaitu:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{N \sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{\{N \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2\} \{N \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2\}}}$$

Selanjutnya dilakukan penghitungan korelasi *Product Moment* antara variabel X dengan variabel Y. untuk perhitungan korelasi *Product Moment* beberapa langkah yang dilakukan, yaitu:

- Membuat Tabel Kerja Silang Variabel X dan Variabel Y

Tabel 4. Kerja Silang Variabel X dan Variabel Y

No. Responden	X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
1	40	30	1600	900	1200
2	36	27	1296	729	972
3	33	32	1089	1024	1056
4	40	39	1600	1521	1560
5	29	34	841	1156	986
6	41	20	1681	400	820
7	36	38	1296	1444	1368
8	37	29	1369	841	1073
9	30	35	900	1225	1050
10	26	25	676	625	650
11	30	33	900	1089	990
12	37	21	1369	441	777
13	34	37	1156	1369	1258
14	32	33	1024	1089	1056
15	28	34	784	1156	952
16	44	36	1936	1296	1584
17	44	27	1936	729	1188
18	38	45	1444	2025	1710
19	42	18	1764	324	756
20	42	29	1764	841	1218
21	27	33	729	1089	891
22	22	43	484	1849	946
23	33	20	1089	400	660
24	19	26	361	676	494
25	28	33	784	1089	924
26	29	40	841	1600	1160
27	31	35	961	1225	1085
28	30	28	900	784	840

29	23	34	529	1156	782
30	31	28	961	784	868
31	25	32	625	1024	800
32	28	37	784	1369	1036
33	36	33	1296	1089	1188
34	26	28	676	784	728
35	24	22	576	484	528
36	30	31	900	961	930
37	22	28	484	784	616
38	36	34	1296	1156	1224
39	33	25	1089	625	825
40	26	23	676	529	598
41	26	36	676	1296	936
42	30	26	900	676	780
43	23	29	529	841	667
44	23	33	529	1089	759
Total	1380	1359	45100	43583	42489

b) Menghitung Korelasi Dengan Rumus

$$r_{xy} = \frac{N \sum XY - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{\{N \sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2\} \{N \sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2\}}}$$

Diketahui:

$$\sum XY = 42.489$$

$$\sum X = 1.380$$

$$\sum Y = 1.359$$

$$\sum X^2 = 45.100$$

$$\sum Y^2 = 43.583$$

$$\text{Maka, } r_{xy} = \frac{44.45374 - (1380)(1415)}{\sqrt{\{(44.45100 - (1380)^2\} \{(44.48101 - (1415)^2\}}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{1996456 - 1952700}{\sqrt{(1984400 - 1904400)(2116444 - 2002225)}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{43756}{\sqrt{(80000)(114219)}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{43756}{\sqrt{9137520000}}$$

$$r_{xy} = \frac{43756}{95590,38}$$

$$r_{xy} = 0,4577$$

Berdasarkan hasil perhitungan korelasi *Product Moment* dapat diketahui bahwa hubungan antara variabel Penggunaa Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) (X) dengan Motivasi Belajar Siswa (Y) sebesar 0,4577 dalam arah positif. Maka selanjutnya menafsirkan nilai r_{hitung} sesuai tabel penafsiran sebagai berikut:

Tabel 5. Nilai r *Product Moment*

Besarnya r <i>Product Moment</i> (r_{xy})	Interpretasi
0,0-0,20	Antara variabel X dan variabel Y memang terdapat korelasi, akan tetapi korelasi tersebut sangat lemah atau sangat rendah sehingga korelasi itu diabaikan (dianggap tidak ada korelasi antara variabel X dan variabel Y).
0,20-0,40	Antara variabel X dan variabel Y terdapat korelasi yang lemah atau rendah.
0,40-0,60	Antara variabel X dan variabel Y terdapat korelasi yang sedang atau cukup.
0,60-0,80	Antara variabel X dan variabel Y terdapat korelasi yang kuat atau tinggi.
0,80-1,00	Antara variabel X dan variabel Y terdapat korelasi yang sangat kuat atau sangat tinggi.

Berdasarkan tabel diatas dapat disimpulkan bahwa, koefisien korelasi antara Dana Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) terhadap Motivasi Belajar Siswa di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan Kecamatan Dolok Merawan Kabupaten serdang Bedagai terdapat korelasi yang sedang atau cukup yaitu terletak pada interval 0,40-0,60. Sehingga dapat disimpulkan terdapat hubungan yang sedang atau cukup antara Dana Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) terhadap Motivasi Belajar Siswa di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan Tahun ajaran 2021/2022.

B. Hasil Uji Hipotesis

Pengujian hipotesis penelitian ini digunakan untuk mengetahui apakah variabel independen (X) berpengaruh secara signifikan terhadap variabel dependen (Y), dengan ketentuan dalam uji hipotesis didalam penelitian ini yaitu:

- Jika nilai $\text{sig} < 0,05$, atau $r_{hitung} > r_{tabel}$, maka terdapat pengaruh variabel X terhadap variabel Y.
- Jika nilai $\text{sig} > 0,05$ atau $r_{hitung} < r_{tabel}$, maka tidak terdapat pengaruh variabel X terhadap variabel Y.

Taraf kepercayaan 0,05 (5%), maka dapat diperoleh harga r_{tabel} sebesar 0,297. Dengan membandingkan r_{hitung} dengan r_{tabel} maka dapat diketahui bahwa nilai $r_{hitung} > r_{tabel}$, yaitu 0,4577

> 0,297. Dengan demikian hipotesis yang diajukan dalam penelitian yaitu adanya pengaruh yang signifikan antara Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) terhadap motivasi belajar siswa di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Meraawan Tahun Pelajaran 2021/2022.

C. Koefisien Determinan (R^2)

Uji ketepatan perkiraan (R^2) menyatakan persentase total variasi dari variabel X yang dapat dijelaskan oleh variabel Y dalam model. Perhitungan koefisien determinasi ini dimaksudkan untuk mengetahui besarnya pengaruh Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) terhadap motivasi belajar siswa di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan . berdasarkan hasil perhitungan korelasi *Product Moment* diketahui nilai r_{xy} sebesar 0,1085. Dengan demikian koefisien determinan dalam penelitian ini yaitu sebagai berikut:

$$KD = (r_{xy})^2 \times 100\%$$

Keterangan;

KD = Kontribusi variabel X terhadap Y

r_{xy} = koefisien korelasi antara variabel X dan Y

$$KD = (0,4577)^2 \times 100\%$$

$$KD = 0,2095 \times 100\%$$

$$KD = 20,95\%$$

$$KD = 21\%$$

Berdasarkan perhitungan koefisien determinan diatas maka dapat diketahui bahwa nilai pengaruh Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) terhadap motivasi belajar siswa di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan sebesar 21%, hal ini berarti variasi motivasi belajar siswa di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan disebabkan faktor Program Indonesia Pintar, sedangkan sisanya 79% disebabkan oleh variabel – variabel lain yang tidak disertakan dalam penelitian ini.

2. Pembahasan

Hubungan yang diperoleh melalui uji korelasi *Product Moment* antara pengaruh Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) dengan motivasi belajar siswa sebesar 0,4577 dalam arah positif. Maka dapat diinterpretasikan secara sederhana bahwa hasil perhitungan korelasi antara pengaruh Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) dengan motivasi belajar siswa tidak bertanda negatif, dengan kata lain variabel terdapat hubungan korelasi positif atau korelasi yang berjalan searah.

Hasil perhitungan *Product Moment* r_{xy} atau r_{hitung} adalah 0,4577 yang merupakan nilai r pada *Product Moment* dalam rentang nilai 0,40 – 0,60 menunjukkan bahwa antara variabel Penggunaan Dana Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) dengan variabel Motivasi Belajar Siswa di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan Tahun Ajaran 2021/2022 terdapat korelasi yang sedang atau cukup. Melalui nilai r tabel *Product Moment* dapat diinterpretasikan pada taraf signifikan sebesar 0,297. Dengan membandingkan besarnya r_{hitung} dengan r_{tabel} , maka dapat diketahui bahwa nilai $r_{hitung} > r_{tabel}$, yaitu $0,4577 > 0,297$. Dengan demikian hipotesis yang diambil adalah H_a yang berarti adanya pengaruh yang signifikan antara motivasi belajar siswa yang mendapatkan dana bantuan Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan Tahun Ajaran 2021/2022.

Berdasarkan perhitungan Koefisien Determinan maka dapat diketahui bahwa nilai pengaruh Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) terhadap motivasi belajar siswa di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan sebesar 21%, hal ini berarti variasi motivasi belajar siswa di SMP Negeri 1

Dolok Merawan disebabkan faktor Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP), sedangkan sisanya 79% disebabkan oleh variabel – variabel yang lain yang tidak disertakan dalam penelitian ini.

SIMPULAN DAN SARAN

Berdasarkan hasil analisis data dan pembahasan yang telah diuraikan, maka dapat diambil kesimpulan sebagai berikut:

Motivasi belajar siswa penerima dana Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) dengan menjumlahkan skor pada angket Motivasi Belajar Siswa yang disebar ke responden sebesar 1380, pada kriteria motivasi belajar siswa yaitu cukup tinggi berada pada rentang skor 1.202 – 1562. Maka motivasi belajar siswa penerima Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) yaitu cukup tinggi. Hubungan yang diperoleh melalui uji korelasi *Product Moment* antara pengaruh Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) dengan motivasi belajar siswa sebesar 0,4577 dalam arah positif. Maka dapat diinterpretasikan secara sederhana bahwa hasil perhitungan korelasi antara pengaruh Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) dengan motivasi belajar siswa tidak bertanda negatif, dengan kata lain variabel terdapat hubungan korelasi positif atau korelasi yang berjalan searah.

Melalui nilai r tabel *Product Moment* dapat diinterpretasikan pada taraf signifikan sebesar 0,297. Dengan membandingkan besarnya r_{hitung} dengan r_{tabel} , maka dapat diketahui bahwa nilai $r_{hitung} > r_{tabel}$, yaitu $0,4577 > 0,297$. Dengan demikian hipotesis yang diambil adalah H_a yang berarti adanya pengaruh yang signifikan antara motivasi belajar siswa yang mendapatkan dana bantuan Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan Tahun Ajaran 2021/2022.

Berdasarkan perhitungan Koefisien Determinan maka dapat diketahui bahwa nilai pengaruh Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP) terhadap motivasi belajar siswa di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan sebesar 21%, hal ini berarti variasi motivasi belajar siswa di SMP Negeri 1 Dolok Merawan disebabkan faktor Program Indonesia Pintar (PIP), sedangkan sisanya 79% disebabkan oleh variabel – variabel yang lain yang tidak disertakan dalam penelitian ini.

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PENGUNAAN MEDIA FLASH CARD HIJAIYAH TERHADAP KEMAMPUAN MEMBACA AL-QUR'AN DI SMP PAB 5 PATUMBAK

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the effect of using hijaiyah flash card media on the ability to read the Al-Qur'an. The research method used is quantitative, quasi-experimental research. The subjects of this research were students in class VIII-3 as the experimental class and VIII-5 as the control class. The data collection techniques used were Al-Qur'an reading tests, observation, interviews and documentation. The data analysis used was the independent sample t-test. Based on the results of data analysis using the independent sample t test, it was obtained that the sig(2-tailed) value was smaller than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$) as H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted. The result of the average number of the experimental class was 85,66 while the result of the average number of the control class was 67,16. This shows that there are difference in students ability to read the Al-Qur'an using hijaiyah flash card media and iqro media so it can be concluded that the use of hijaiyah flash card media has an effect on the ability to read the Al-Qur'an at SMP PAB 5 Patumbak

Keywords: *Flash card media, The ability to read the Al-Qur'an*

Abstrak

Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengetahui pengaruh penggunaan media *flash card* hijaiyah terhadap kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an. Metode penelitian yang digunakan yaitu kuantitatif jenis penelitian quasi eksperimen. Subjek penelitian ini adalah siswa kelas VIII- 3 sebagai Kelas eksperimen dan VIII-5 sebagai kelas kontrol. Teknik pengumpulan data yang digunakan adalah tes membaca Al-Qur'an, observasi, wawancara dan dokumentasi. Analisis data yang digunakan adalah uji idependen simple t-tes. Berdasarkan hasil analisis data dengan menggunakan uji idependen simple t test diperoleh nilai sig(2-tailed) lebih kecil daripada 0,05 ($0,000 < 0,05$) sebagaimana H_0 ditolak dan H_a diterima. Hasil jumlah rata-rata kelas eksperimen sebesar 85,66 sedangkan hasil jumlah rata-rata kelas kontrol sebesar 67,16. Hal ini menunjukkan ada perbedaan kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an pada siswa antara menggunakan media *flash card* hijaiyah dengan media iqro sehingga dapat disimpulkan bahwa penggunaan media *flash card* hijaiyah berpengaruh terhadap kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an di SMP PAB 5 Patumbak.

Kata Kunci: *Media Flash Card, Kemampuan Membaca Al-Qur'an*

PENDAHULUAN

Pendidikan bagi anak dalam pandangan Islam menjadi salah satu acuan yang sangat penting, sejak usia dini anak perlu diberikan pembelajaran tentang Pendidikan Agama Islam yaitu mempelajari dan mengenalkan Al-Qur'an yang merupakan sumber hukum dan pedoman hidup manusia terutama bagi umat islam. Untuk dapat memahami ajarannya yaitu dengan cara dibaca, ditulis, dihafal, dipahami maknanya, dan dilaksanakan. Mempelajari Al- Qur'an bagi umat islam merupakan suatu kewajiban. Langkah pertama untuk

mempelajari Al-Qur'an adalah belajar membaca, karna seseorang yang dapat membaca tulisan maka langkah selanjutnya seseorang dapat menulis, dan dengan membaca orang hafal dengan abjad huruf-huruf dasar. Al- Qur'an pada dasarnya itu mudah dipelajari, tidak susah dan tidak berat, dengan syarat ada kemauan, keseriusan, dan kesungguhan dalam mempelajarinya. (Niswatz Zahro' et al., 2022)

Sebagaimana Allah SWT berfirman. *"Bacalah dengan (menyebut) nama Tuhanmu yang menciptakan. Dia telah menciptakan manusia dari segumpal darah. Bacalah, dan Tuhanmulah yang Maha mulia. yang mengajar (manusia) dengan pena. Dia mengajarkan manusia apa yang tidak diketahuinya".* (Q.S Al-alaq 1-5).

Dari ayat diatas maka dapat disimpulkan bahwa Allah memerintahkan manusia untuk mencari ilmu dari ilmu yang bersifat umum sampai ilmu yang menyangkut tentang agama. Selain itu ,pada ayat tersebut juga memerintahkan untuk membaca guna memperluas pengetahuan dan wawasan. Allah menerangkan bahwa manusia itu diciptakan dari segumpal darah yang kemudian diberikan Allah kemuliaan dengan cara mengajar membaca, menulis dan memberi ilmu pengetahuan.

Media adalah perantara, penghubung, alat, dan sarana dalam menyampaikan suatu informasi atau pesan kepada penerima. Memanfaatkan media dalam pembelajaran yaitu mendukung untuk menyampaikan informasi dalam proses pembelajaran kepada siswa dalam meningkatkan kualitas dan kuantitas anak yang interaktif juga aktif sehingga bisa membantu melancarkan aktivitas proses pembelajaran didalam kelas. Adapun jenis-jenis media pembelajaran bisa digolongkan antara lain visual, audio, dan audio visual. Belajar dengan menggunakan berbagai media pembelajaran tujuan pembelajaran akan menjadi menarik dan optimal. (Pradana & Gerhni, 2019)

Berdasarkan wawancara dengan guru Pendidikan Agama Islam kelas VII di SMP PAB 5 Patumbak terdapat peserta didik yang masih belum mampu membaca Al-Qur'an, 40 % siswa belum mampu membedakan huruf hijaiyah beserta dengan tajwidnya dan 20% siswa mengetahui huruf hijaiyah tetapi tidak mampu menyambungkan huruf hijaiyah. Faktor penyebab peserta didik belum mampu membaca Al-Qur'an salah satunya dari lingkungan keluarga, waktu paling banyak dihabiskan oleh siswa adalah di lingkungan keluarga. Kurangnya perhatian dan pengawasan dari orang tua menjadikan salah satu faktor penghambat bagi tumbuh kembangnya anak. Media yang digunakan guru dalam membantu siswa membaca Al- Qur'an yakni dengan media iqra.

Berdasarkan wawancara dengan beberapa siswa di kelas VII, siswa masih kesulitan dalam membedakan huruf hijaiyah dan membaca Al- Qur'an yang belum sesuai dengan kaidah ilmu tajwid. Siswa tidak pernah mengulang kembali bacaan iqra yang pernah siswa pelajari di tingkat Sekolah Dasar, sehingga menyebabkan siswa lupa dan kesulitan dalam membedakan huruf hijaiyah. Hal ini menunjukkan bahwa kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an siswa kelas VII di SMP PAB 5 Patumbak masih tergolong rendah.

Permasalahan yang dihadapi oleh peserta didik diatas, solusi yang dapat diberikan untuk membantu siswa dalam kemampuan membaca Al- Qur'an agar lebih semangat dan menyenangkan dalam proses pembelajaran dengan menggunakan media *Flash Card*.

Buttner sebagaimana dikutip Angreany berpendapat bahwa *Flash Card* adalah media pembelajaran berupa gambar yang dilengkapi dengan pertanyaan-pertanyaan yang berkaitan dengan gambar untuk membantu mengingatkan atau mengarahkan siswa pada huruf hijaiyah, serta merangsang pikiran dan minat siswa dalam meningkatkan kecakapan

pengenalan simbol/huruf hijaiyah, sehingga sampai kepada kegiatan siswa memahami arti/makna yang terkandung dalam kartu.(Angreany & Saud, 2017)

Berdasarkan uraian di latar belakang tersebut, maka peneliti tertarik melakukan penelitian dengan judul **“Pengaruh Penggunaan Media *Flash Card* Hijaiyah Terhadap Kemampuan Membaca Al- Qur’an Di SMP PAB 5 Patumbak”**.

METODE PENELITIAN

Penelitian ini menggunakan pendekatan kuantitatif. Metode penelitian eksperimen memiliki berbagai desain penelitian. Pada penelitian ini, desain yang digunakan adalah *Quasi Eksperimental*(eksperimen semu). *Quasi Eksperimen* merupakan desain penelitian yang memiliki kelompok kontrol tetapi tidak dapat berfungsi sepenuhnya untuk mengontrol variabel-variabel ekstra yang memengaruhi pelaksanaan eksperimen, desain ini sering digunakan oleh peneliti karna sulit mendapatkan kelompok kontrol. (Hikmawati, 2020)

Pada penelitian ini, kelas VIII-5 menjadi kelas kontrol yang tidak menggunakan media *flash card*. Sedangkan VIII-3 menjadi kelas eksperimen dengan menggunakan media *flash card*. Agar penelitian tidak menyimpang dari tujuan yang telah ditetapkan oleh penulis, maka penulis membuat desain penelitian dengan berdasarkan analisis permasalahan kedalam unit-unit penelitian yang diorganisir secara sistematis sehingga menjadi pedoman penelitian.

Teknik pengumpulan data yang digunakan:

1. Observasi. Observasi adalah suatu teknik atau cara mengumpulkan data yang sistematis terhadap obyek penelitian baik secara langsung maupun tidak langsung.(Hardani, Nur Hikmatul Auliyah, Helmina Andriani, Roushandy Asri Fardani, Jumari Ustiawaty, Evi Fatmi Utami, 2020). Peneliti melakukan observasi di SMP PAB 5 Patumbak pada saat proses pembelajaran di SMP PAB 5 Patumbak.
2. Wawancara. Wawancara ialah tanya jawab secara lisan yang dilakukan antara dua orang atau lebih, dilakukan secara langsung dengan tujuan tertentu.(Hardani, Nur Hikmatul Auliyah, Helmina Andriani, Roushandy Asri Fardani, Jumari Ustiawaty, Evi Fatmi Utami, 2020) Peneliti melakukan wawancara kepada Guru Pendidikan Agama Islam dan Siswa kelas VIII di SMP PAB 5 Patumbak.
3. Teknik tes. Teknik tes adalah teknik pengumpulan data yang dilakukan dengan memberikan serentetan soal atau tugas serta alat lainnya kepada subjek yang diperlukan datanya
4. Dokumentasi. Dokumentasi merupakan teknik pengumpulan data penelitian mengenai hal-hal atau variabel yang berupa catatan yang sudah berlaku. Dokumen bisa berbentuk tulisan, gambar, atau karya-karya monumental dari seseorang. Hasil penelitian akan lebih dapat dipercaya jika ada bukti dokumentasinya.

HASIL DAN PEMBAHASAN

Berdasarkan hasil uji validitas kemudian dilihat dari nilai r_{xy} dikonsultasikan dengan menggunakan tabel “ r ” *product moment*, dimana berlaku ketentuan df (*degrees of freedom*) sama dengan sampel (N). Pada taraf signifikansi 5% diperoleh $r_{tabel} = 0,254$, maka berdasarkan ketentuan tersebut maka diperoleh kesimpulan sebagai berikut:

Tabel 1. Hasil Perhitungan Uji Validitas

No	Rhitung	Rtabel	keterangan
1	0,850	0,245	Valid
2	0,827	0,245	Valid
3	0,794	0,245	Valid
4	0,919	0,245	Valid

Berdasarkan tabel diatas dapat dilihat bahwa dari 4 butir tes kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an semuanya dinyatakan valid karena nilai dari setiap butir tes lebih besar daripada $R_{tabel}=0,254$. Valid berarti instrumen tersebut dapat digunakan mengukur apa yang diukur.

Uji reliabilitas dilakukan dengan tujuan untuk menunjukkan alat yang digunakan dapat dipercaya atau tidak untuk dijadikan alat hitung. Jika instrumen *reliable* (dapat dipercaya) maka hasilnya dapat untuk menghitung reliabilitas peneliti menggunakan bantuan aplikasi Statistica 2.0 dengan hasil sebagai berikut:

**Tabel 2. Hasil Pengujian Reliabilitas
Reliability Statistics**

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
,881	4

Sumber: Hasil Olahan SPSS 2.0

Berdasarkan tabel hasil pengujian reliable diatas diperoleh hasil uji reliabilitas pada penelitian ini dengan nilai *Cronbach's Alpa* sebesar $0,881 > 0,70$ sehingga dapat disimpulkan bahwa hasil penelitian ini adalah reliable.

Uji normalitas pada hasil tes kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an pada siswa di kelas kontrol dan kelas eksperimen dilakukan untuk menentukan apakah data yang diperoleh berdistribusi normal atau tidak. Uji normalitas data terhadap dua kelas tersebut dilakukan dengan menggunakan uji *Kolmogrov- Smirnov* dengan menggunakan program SPSS 20 for windows taraf signifikansi 0.05. Adapun pedoman pengambilan keputusan sebagai berikut :

1. Jika perolehan < 0.05 maka data berdistribusi tidak normal
2. Jika perolehan > 0.05 maka data berdistribusi normal

Tabel 3. Hasil Pengujian Normalitas

	Tests of Normality		
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a		
	Statistic	df	Sig.
kelas kontrol	,130	30	,200*
kelas eksperimen	,114	30	,200*

*. This is a lower bound of the true significance.

a. Lilliefors Significance Correction

Sumber: Hasil Olahan SPSS 2.0

Berdasarkan tabel diatas mengenai hasil output pengujian normalitas dengan menggunakan uji *Kolmogrov Smirnov* diperoleh hasil bahwa nilai signifikansi(sig-) pada

kolom signifikansi pada data hasil tes pada kelas kontrol dan kelas eksperimen adalah sebesar 0.200, nilai signifikansi dari hasil tes kelas kontrol dan eksperimen lebih dari 0.05 dengan demikian dapat disimpulkan bahwa data kelas kontrol dan kelas eksperimen berdistribusi normal.

Uji independen simple t test digunakan untuk mengetahui apakah terjadi perbedaan rata-rata dua sampel yang tidak berpasangan atau tidak terhubung. Uji independen simple t test dengan menggunakan SPSS 2.0 for windows. Adapun pedoman pengambilan keputusan sebagai berikut:

1. Jika nilai sig (2- tailed) < 0.05 maka terdapat perbedaan yang signifikan antara variabel a dan variabel b
2. Jika nilai sig(2-tailed) > 0.05 maka tidak terdapat perbedaan yang signifikan antara variabel a dan variabel b

Tabel 4. Hasil Pengujian Ipenden Simple t test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper	
Kemampuan Membaca Al-Qur'an	Equal variances assumed	4,630	,036	-13,299	58	,000	-17,26667	1,29833	-19,86556	-14,66777
	Equal variances not assumed			-13,299	48,300	,000	-17,26667	1,29833	-19,87672	-14,65661

Sumber: Hasil Olahan SPSS 2.0

Berdasarkan hasil pengujian independen simple t test di atas dapat dilihat bahwa nilai sig (2-tailed) 0.000 lebih kecil dari 0.05, maka dapat disimpulkan bahwa terdapat perbedaan yang signifikan antara kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an pada kelas eksperimen dan kelas kontrol.

Tabel 5. Hasil Tes Kelas Eksperimen dan Kelas Kontrol

No	Nama Siswa	Kelas Eksperimen	No	Nama Siswa	Kelas Kontrol
1	S 01	90	1	S 01	65
2	S 02	90	2	S 02	75
3	S 03	85	3	S 03	70
4	S 04	85	4	S 04	60
5	S 05	90	5	S 05	75
6	S 06	85	6	S 06	60
7	S 07	90	7	S 07	65
8	S 08	90	8	S 08	75
9	S 09	80	9	S 09	60
10	S 10	90	10	S 10	60
11	S 11	85	11	S 11	75
12	S 12	90	12	S 12	70
13	S 13	85	13	S 13	65
14	S 14	80	14	S 14	65
15	S 15	85	15	S 15	65
16	S 16	85	16	S 16	60

17	S 17	85	17	S 17	75
18	S 18	85	18	S 18	75
19	S 19	80	19	S 19	60
20	S 20	90	20	S 20	75
21	S 21	85	21	S 21	60
22	S 22	85	22	S 22	75
23	S 23	80	23	S 23	70
24	S 24	80	24	S 24	55
25	S 25	85	25	S 25	60
26	S 26	85	26	S 26	75
27	S 27	80	27	S 27	75
28	S 28	90	28	S 28	70
29	S 29	85	29	S 29	70
30	S 30	90	30	S 30	65
Jumlah		2570	Jumlah		2015
Rata-rata		85,66	Rata-rata		67,16

Sumber: Hasil Tes Siswa

Berdasarkan tabel diatas mengenai hasil tes kelas kontrol dan kelas eksperimen terkait penggunaan media flash card Hijaiyah Terhadap Kemampuan Membaca Al-Qur'an diperoleh hasil bahwa nilai terendah dikelas kontrol adalah sebesar 55 dan nilai terendah dikelas eksperimen adalah sebesar 70. Nilai tertinggi dikelas kontrol sebesar 70 dan nilai tertinggi dikelas eksperimen yaitu 90. Nilai rata-rata dari kelas kontrol 67,16 sedangkan hasil tes dari kelas eksperimen yaitu 85,66, dengan demikian dapat disimpulkan bahwa kelas kontrol belum mencapai nilai KKM sebesar 85 sedangkan kelas eksperimen telah mencapai nilai KKM Sebesar 85 yang ditentukan dalam kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an dan kelas eksperimen lebih unggul dibandingkan dengan kelas kontrol, berdasarkan hasil tes kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an pada kelas kontrol dan kelas eksperimen diperoleh kesimpulan bahwa kelas eksperimen yang menggunakan media flash card hijaiyah memperoleh dampak positif dalam kegiatan membaca Al-Qur'an.

Tabel 6. Hasil Setiap Item Indikator Kemampuan Membaca Al-Qur'an Kelas Eksperimen dan Kelas Kontrol

Kelas Eksperimen		Kelas Kontrol	
Indikator	Jumlah total	Indikator	Jumlah total
Makrajul Huruf	136	Makrajul Huruf	108
Tajwid	118	Tajwid	87
Shifatul Huruf	120	Shifatul Huruf	106
Kelancaran membaca	140	Kelancaran membaca	102

Sumber : Hasil Tes Siswa

Berdasarkan tabel hasil dari tiap item indikator kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an dapat dilihat jumlah total dari empat item instrumen tes kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an yang diberikan kepada 60 responden yang terdiri dari 30 siswa kelas eksperimen dan 30 kelas kontrol

dapat ditarik kesimpulan bahwa jumlah setiap item dari kelas eksperimen lebih besar dibandingkan dari kelas kontrol yang menandakan bahwa terdapat pengaruh positif kepada kelas eksperimen yang menggunakan media *flash card* hijaiyah dalam kegiatan membaca Al-Qur'an pada siswa.

Berdasarkan hasil uji idependen simple t test tentang pengaruh penggunaan media *flash card* hijaiyah terhadap kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an di SMP PAB 5 Patumbak. Diperoleh nilai sig (2-tailed) sebesar $0.000 < \text{dari } 0.05$, maka dari hasil tersebut dapat disimpulkan bahwa Hipotesis Alternatif(H_a) : adanya pengaruh yang signifikan antara penggunaan media *flash card* hijaiyah terhadap kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an di SMP PAB 5 Patumbak diterima dan Hipotesis Nol (H_0): tidak terdapat pengaruh penggunaan media *flashcard* hijaiyah terhadap kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an di SMP PAB 5 Patumbak ditolak. Dari analisis data diatas menunjukkan bahwa suatu media pembelajaran sangat berpengaruh terhadap kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an pada siswa.

Media *flash card* hijaiyah terhadap kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an di SMP PAB 5 Patumbak berdampak positif hal ini dapat dilihat pada bagian hasil tes pada siswa yang menunjukkan hasil tertinggi dari kelas eksperimen sebesar 90 lebih besar dari nilai KKM sebesar 85 sedangkan hasil tes kelas kontrol yang tertinggi sebesar 70 yang menandakan bahwasanya tidak memenuhi nilai KKM sebesar 85. Dengan media *flash card* hijaiyah siswa dapat mengetahui huruf hijaiyah dengan jelas dan tepat serta siswa sudah dapat menyambung huruf hijaiyah sehingga mempermudah siswa dalam membaca Al-Qur'an, hal ini dapat dilihat pada hasil tes siswa pada tiap item instrument yang dapat disimpulkan bahwa jumlah total dalam tiap item instrumen pada kelas eksperimen yang menggunakan media *flash card* hijaiyah lebih tinggi dibandingkan dengan kelas kontrol yang tidak menggunakan media *flash card* hijaiyah.

SIMPULAN DAN SARAN

Berdasarkan hasil penelitian mengambil kesimpulan bahwa, pengaruh penggunaan media *flash card* sangat berpengaruh terhadap kemampuan siswa di SMP PAB 5 Patumbak, Penelitian ini memiliki instrumen tes penilaian yang berupa 4 item dan memiliki jumlah responden sebanyak 60 orang siswa yang terdiri dari kelas kontrol sebanyak 30 siswa dan kelas eksperimen sebanyak 30 siswa. berikut ini kesimpulan dari penelitian ini :

1. Penggunaan media *flash card* dapat membantu siswa dalam mengenal huruf hijaiyah. Hal ini dapat di lihat dari hasil tes kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an dari indikator makrajul huruf pada kelas eksperimen dengan jumlah total 136 sedangkan indikator makrajul huruf dari kelas kontrol jumlah totalnya sebesar 108,dapat dilihat jumlah total kelas eksperimen lebih tinggi dibandingkan kelas kontrol.
2. Penggunaan media *flash card* dapat membantu siswa dalam mengenal huruf hijaiyah. Hal ini dapat di lihat dari hasil tes kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an dari indikator kelancaran membaca pada kelas eksperimen dengan jumlah total 140 sedangkan indikator makrajul huruf dari kelas kontrol jumlah totalnya sebesar 102,dapat dilihat jumlah total kelas eksperimen lebih tinggi dibandingkan kelas kontrol.
3. Penggunaan media *flash card* dapat membantu siswa dalam membaca Al-Qur'an.Hal ini dapat di lihat dari hasil uji idependen simple t test tentang pengaruh penggunaan

media *flash card* hijaiyah terhadap kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an di SMP PAB 5 Patumbak, diperoleh nilai sig (2-teiled) sebesar $0.000 < 0.05$. Hasil jumlah rata-rata dari kelas eksperimen berjumlah 85,66 dan hasil jumlah rata-rata dari kelas kontrol berjumlah 67,16.

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KONSEP PENDIDIKAN ISLAM DALAM PERSPEKTIF TAFSIR AL-MISBAH PROF. DR. H. MUHAMMAD QURAIISH SHIHAB, MA.

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Abstract

Research results related to educational goals M. Quraish Shihab takes educational goals from the perspective of the Koran. M. Quraish Shihab stated that the purpose of education is to foster humans so that they realize that they are God's servants and carry out their functions as God's caliphs on this earth. Education according to M. Quraish Shihab must pay attention to three aspects in human beings, namely reason, soul and body. Mind development produces knowledge, soul development produces purity and ethics, and physical development produces skills. M. Quraish Shihab argues that educational goals lead to general educational goals or what are also called perfect goals. The perfect goal or ultimate goal of education according to M. Quraish Shihab must be able to form a two-dimensional human being who is balanced between reason and faith, reason and spiritual, and finally worldly and ukhrowi.

Regarding learning methods in general, M. Quraish Shihab also takes an approach based on the Koran, which treats humans according to the elements of their creation, namely body, soul, and mind. Therefore M. Quraish Shihab did not propose a specific method of delivering the material. The most important thing in delivering material is sentences that inspire and touch the heart, accompanied by examples and habituation to solidify the material being taught. It can be concluded that the learning methods abstracted by M. Quraish Shihab from the Koran are very much in harmony with student-centered learning, this is because each method always pays attention to the condition of students, namely reason, physical and psychological.

Keywords: *Islamic Education, Muhammad Quraish Shihab's Perspective, Interpretation of Al Misbah*

PENDAHULUAN

Pendidikan adalah penyebab utama terjadinya perubahan perilaku di dalam masyarakat. Bahkan Islam sendiri menempatkan pendidikan dalam posisi vital, sehingga manusia mampu berperilaku dan berinteraksi sesuai dengan akhlak yang dianjurkan oleh agama. Gagasan utama pendidikan termasuk pendidikan Islam, terletak pada pandangan bahwa setiap manusia mempunyai nilai positif tentang kecerdasan, daya kreatif dan leluhur budi. Namun fokusnya bukan semata kemampuan spiritual dan keyakinan tauhid tetapi juga akhlak sosial dan kemanusiaan. Kualitas akhlak pun tak bisa dicapai hanya dengan doktrin halal-haram, tetapi usaha budaya di rumah, masyarakat dan ruang kelas.

Pendidikan memiliki nilai yang strategis dalam pembentukan suatu bangsa. Pendidikan itu juga berupaya menjamin kelangsungan hidup bangsa tersebut. Sebab lewat pendidikan nantinya akan diwariskan nilai-nilai luhur yang dimiliki oleh bangsa tersebut. Umumnya

masyarakat melakukan pendidikan bagi regenerasi sosial yaitu pelimpahan harta budaya dan pelestarian nilai-nilai luhur dari suatu generasi muda dalam kehidupan masyarakat.¹

Pendidikan berevolusi dari masa kemasa dengan berbagai teologi dan pemikiran serta berorientasi dalam kehidupan guna menambah pengetahuan, yang berpengaruh pada perkembangan dan pemikiran manusia yang eksklusif, mistik, dan individualistik, dengan hasil yang didapat adalah berupa pengetahuan, nilai-nilai, dan keterampilan.

Sejatinya penyelenggaraan pendidikan dimasa kini dilakukan oleh institusi, lembaga dan organisasi yang bergerak dalam pendidikan formal atau non formal seperti sekolah, masjid, mushala, TPQ, dan lain-lain. Serta adanya pembagian kerja berdasarkan profesi, dan tugas kependidikan yang diserahkan sepenuhnya kepada pendidik yang profesional atau yang disebut guru.

Hasan Langgulung dalam Jalaluddin mengatakan ada dua sudut pandang dalam pendidikan yakni, “yang pertama pendidikan merupakan usaha mengembangkan potensi individu. Yang kedua pendidikan ialah usaha mewariskan nilai-nilai budaya oleh generasi tua kepada generasi muda.”²

Pendidikan tidak pernah selesai untuk dibicarakan. Mengapa? *Pertama*, fitrah setiap orang menginginkan yang lebih baik. Ia menginginkan pendidikan yang lebih baik sekalipun belum tentu ia tahu pendidikan yang lebih baik itu. *Kedua*, karena teori pendidikan. Teori pada umumnya selalu ketinggalan oleh kebutuhan masyarakat. Umumnya, teori pendidikan dibuat berdasarkan kebutuhan masyarakat pada tempat dan waktu tertentu. Karena waktu dan tempat selalu berubah, maka kebutuhan manusia juga ikut berubah. Dan perubahan itu ikut pula merubah sifat manusia. *Ketiga*, karena pengaruh pandangan hidup. Pada suatu waktu mungkin seseorang telah puas dengan keadaan pendidikan di tempatnya karena sudah sesuai dengan hidupnya. Suatu ketika ia terpengaruh oleh pandangan hidup orang lain. Akibatnya berubah pula pendapatnya tentang pendidikan, yang tadinya sudah memuaskan menjadi merasa tidak puas. Tiga penyebab itu intinya manusia yang tidak pernah puas.³

Memang harus diakui bahwa problematika dalam dunia pendidikan Islam sangat kompleks, mulai dari permasalahan internal, seperti: kurikulum, metode dan unsur-unsur pedagogis lainnya sampai dengan permasalahan dimensi eksternal, seperti: kepentingan politik, ekonomi dan perubahan sosial budaya. Diharapkan dengan adanya pendidikan maka perubahan sosial dan kestabilan masyarakat dapat berlangsung dengan baik. Dalam hal ini, pendidikan sebagai gejala sosial masih terwujud dalam bentuk komunikasi dua arah. Maka pendidikan cenderung dinilai bersifat konservatif dan tradisional karena masih terbatas pada penyampaian bahan ajar kepada peserta didik dan bisa kehilangan ciri interaksi yang efektif.

Prof. Dr. H. Muhammad Quraish Shihab, MA. melalui karyanya yang berjudul *Membumikan Alquran* mencoba menyoroti aspek-aspek kehidupan manusia dengan tinjauan Alquran, termasuk di dalamnya tentang masalah-masalah pendidikan. Dalam bukunya tersebut, beliau menggulirkan konsep pendidikan dalam Alquran, dalam hal ini pendidikan menurut Quraish Shihab juga terbilang pendidikan Islam, karena pendidikan menurut Quraish Shihab berlandaskan dengan Alquran. Dalam karyanya tersebut, beliau membahas aspek-aspek

¹ Munzir Hitami, *Menggagas Kembali Pendidikan Islam*, (Riau: Infinite Press, 2014), h. 12.

² Jalaluddin, *Teologi Pendidikan*, (Jakarta: RajaGrafindo Persada, 2013), h. 68-69.

³ Ahmad Tafsir, *Filsafat Pendidikan Islam*, (Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya, 2014), h. 40.

pendidikan Islam, tujuan pendidikan Islam, metode pendidikan Islam, sifat pendidikan Islam, dan lain sebagainya.⁴

Dalam menguraikan tentang konsep pendidikan Islam beliau mengatakan bahwa Alquran mengintroduksikan dirinya sebagai pemberi petunjuk kepada (jalan) yang lebih lurus. Dan petunjuk-petunjuk tersebut bertujuan memberi kesejahteraan dan kebahagiaan bagi manusia, baik secara individu maupun kelompok. Oleh karena itu, Rasulullah Saw, yang dalam hal ini sebagai penerima wahyu (Alquran), bertugas menyampaikan petunjuk-petunjuk tersebut, menyucikan dan mengajarkan manusia. Menyucikan dapat diidentikkan dengan mendidik, sedang kan mengajar tidak lain kecuali mengisi benak anak didik dengan pengetahuan yang berkaitan dengan alam metafisika serta fisika. Keduanya, baik mensucikan ataupun mengajar merupakan salah satu kegiatan yang wajib ada dalam pendidikan, termasuk pendidikan Islam di dalamnya.⁵

Berdasarkan paparan di atas, Peneliti akan memilih Prof. Dr. H. Muhammad Quraish Shihab, MA. dalam mengkaji pendidikan Islam, yang mana beliau merupakan salah satu dari ulama Indonesia yang memiliki kitab tafsir Quran sendiri, Al-Misbah. Selain ketenarannya sebagai mufassir dan guru besar di Indonesia, beliau juga sering diundang menjadi narasumber di berbagai stasiun televisi terlebih pada bulan Ramadhan. Beliau juga sangat produktif, sebagai ulama Indonesia yang paling produktif dengan belasan bukunya yang kesemuanya mendapat label *best seller*. Dan tidak berlebihan jika dikatakan beliau merupakan salah satu ulama yang amat berkontribusi bagi Indonesia.

Penulis meneliti judul ini didasari dengan pentingnya bagi umat manusia khususnya umat Islam miliki pendidikan yang baik yakni Pendidikan sesuai dengan Alquran dan Sunnah. Selain penelitian ini berhubungan dengan jurusan Pendidikan Agama Islam, penelitian ini juga bisa menjadi cerminan bagi pendidik maupun peserta didik untuk membuat komponen pendidikan menjadi lebih baik lagi. Oleh karena itu, maka penulis tertarik untuk meneliti “Konsep Pendidikan Islam Dalam Perspektif Tafsir Al-Misbah Prof. Dr. H. Muhammad Quraish Shihab, MA.”

METODE PENELITIAN

Dalam hal ini, peneliti menggunakan jenis pendekatan penelitian kualitatif tentang riset yang bersifat deskriptif dengan metode *library research*. Penelitian kepustakaan (*library research*), yakni menelaah referensi atau literatur-literatur yang terkait dengan pembahasan, baik yang berbahasa asing maupun yang berbahasa Indonesia. Penelitian ini merupakan jenis penelitian kualitatif. Penelitian kualitatif adalah penelitian yang menekankan pada *quality* atau hal yang terpenting darisifat suatu barang atau jasa. Hal terpenting dari suatu barang atau jasa berupa kejadian atau fenomena atau gejala sosial adalah makna dibalik kejadian tersebut yang dapat dijadikan pelajaran berharga bagi suatu pengembangan konsep teori.⁶

Penelitian ini menyangkut konsep pendidikan Islam pandangan Prof. Dr. H. Muhammad Quraish Shihab, MA. maka sebagai kepustakaan utama dalam penelitian ini adalah pandangan

⁴ Daimah, *Pemikiran Quraish Shihab (Religius Rasional) Tentang Pendidikan Islam Dan Relevansinya Terhadap Dunia Modern*, Jurnal Madaniyah, Vol 8 Nomor 2 Edisi Agustus 2018), h. 174

⁵ M. Quraish Shihab, *Membumikan Al-Quran: Fungsi dan peran Wahyu dalam Kehidupan Masyarakat*, Cet. Ke-13 (Bandung: PT Mizan Pustaka, 1996), h. 228

⁶ Djam'an Satori, *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*, (Bandung: Alfabeta, 2017), h. 22

Prof. Dr. H. Muhammad Quraish Shihab, MA. Sedangkan kepustakaan yang bersifat sekunder adalah Alquran dan kitab tafsir, sebagai penunjang penulis menggunakan buku-buku ke-Islaman dan artikel-artikel serta buku-buku hukum yang berkaitan dengan pendidikan Islam.

Penelitian ini menggunakan dua sumber, yaitu data primer dan data sekunder. Sumber data yang diperoleh langsung dari subyek penelitian dengan menggunakan alat pengambilan data langsung pada subyek sebagai sumber informasi yang dicari.⁷ Data primer adalah data yang diambil langsung dari sumber terkait dengan karya Prof. Dr. H. Muhammad Quraish Shihab, MA. Sumber data primer dalam penelitian ini adalah M. Quraish Shihab, *Membumikan Alquran: Fungsi dan Kedudukan Wahyu Dalam Kehidupan Masyarakat*, (Bandung, Mizan 2013), Edisi ke-2, Cet. I. M. Quraish Shihab, *Tafsir Al-Misbah: Pesan, Kesan dan Keserasian Alquran Cetakan Ke-IV Vol. 6*. M. Quraish Shihab, *Menabur Pesan Ilahi: Alquran dan Dinamika Kehidupan Masyarakat* (Jakarta, Lentera Hati 2006).

Sumber data sekunder yaitu bahan-bahan tertulis yang berasal tidak langsung/asli dari sumber utama yang membahas masalah yang dikaji. Data sekunder dalam penelitian ini diperoleh dari buku-buku lain yang berkaitan dengan judul penelitian yakni tentang Konsep Pendidikan Islam Perspektif Prof. Dr. H. Muhammad Quraish Shihab, MA. Selain itu pendapat para ahli juga merupakan sumber sekunder di dalam penelitian ini.

Teknik pengumpulan data adalah langkah yang strategis dalam penelitian, karena tujuan dari sebuah penelitian adalah mendapatkan data. Untuk mendapatkan data yang akurat guna mendukung penelitian ini, maka penulis menggunakan teknik pengumpulan data dengan metode telaah, membaca.⁸ Berdasarkan jenis penelitian yang digunakan yaitu *library research* (kepustakaan), maka pengumpulan data maka penulis menggunakan metode dokumentasi. Metode dokumentasi adalah mencari dan mempelajari data dalam bentuk tulisan, gambar, atau karya seseorang. Dokumentasi bisa berupa catatan harian, sejarah kehidupan, biografi, gambar hidup, atau sejenis karya seni. Metode ini digunakan untuk mendapatkan data-data yang dibutuhkan dalam menjawab pokok permasalahan.⁹

Setelah data terkumpul, langkah selanjutnya adalah menganalisa data. Analisis data adalah salah satu langkah penting untuk mengolah data untuk menjawab rumusan masalah dalam penelitian. Teknik analisis data yang dapat digunakan dalam penulisan kepustakaan adalah analisis isi (*content analysis*). Teknik ini digunakan penulis untuk mengkaji perilaku manusia secara tidak langsung melalui analisis terhadap karya-karya seseorang seperti buku teks, essay, koran, novel, artikel, majalah, lagu, dan sebagainya. Ada dua tahap dalam teknik analisis data penulisan kepustakaan ini, yaitu reduksi data untuk mendapatkan temuan-temuan yang kemudian menjadi fokus dalam penulisan, dan display data untuk memberikan pemahaman terhadap data agar bisa ditentukan langkah selanjutnya. Selanjutnya dibuat gambaran kesimpulan dengan memaparkan penemuan baru dari penulisan yang dilakukan.¹⁰

⁷ Siswanto, *Metode Penelitian Kombinasi Kualitatif dan Kuantitatif Pada Penelitian Tindakan PTK dan PTS*, (Klaten: Boss Script, 2019), h. 297.

⁸ Sugiyono, *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*, (Bandung: Alfabeta, 2018), h. 224

⁹ *Ibid.* h. 240

¹⁰ V. Wiratna Sujarweti, *Metodologi Penelitian Lengkap, Praktis, dan Mudah dipahami*, (Yogyakarta: 2014, Pustaka Baru Press), h. 103

HASIL DAN PEMBAHASAN

Alquran memperkenalkan dirinya sebagai pemberi petunjuk kepada jalan yang lurus. Petunjuk-petunjuknya bertujuan memberi kesejahteraan dan kebahagiaan bagi manusia, baik secara pribadi maupun kelompok. Alquran telah menjadi petunjuk bagi masyarakat dimuka bumi ini untuk mencapai tujuan yang diinginkan. Tujuan pendidikan Alquran adalah membina manusia secara pribadi dan kelompok sehingga mampu menjalankan fungsinya sebagai hamba Allah SWT dan khalifah-Nya, guna membangun dunia ini sesuai dengan konsep yang ditetapkan Allah SWT. Kekhalifahan mengharuskan empat sisi yang saling berkaitan yaitu diantaranya: pertama, pemberi tugas (Allah SWT), kedua penerima tugas (manusia baik perorang maupun kelompok), ketiga tempat atau lingkungan dan keempat materi-materi penegasan yang harus mereka laksanakan.¹¹

Dalam bidang pendidikan, Alquran menuntut bersatunya kata dengan sikap. Karena keteladanan para pendidik dan tokoh masyarakat merupakan salah satu andalannya. Pada saat Alquran mewajibkan anak menghormati orang tuanya, pada saat itu pula Alquran mewajibkan orang tua untuk mendidik anak-anaknya. Pada saat masyarakat mewajibkan menaati Rasul dan para pemimpin, pada saat yang sama Rasul dan pemimpin diperintahkan menunaikan amanah, menyayangi yang dipimpin sambil bermusyawarah bersama mereka. Dengan demikian Alquran menuntut keterpaduan antara orang tua, masyarakat dan pemerintah.

Dalam hal ini telah dijelaskan pula bahwasanya peranan orang tua sangat penting dalam perkembangan anak, baik dilingkungan keluarga, masyarakat maupun negara. Sebagaimana firman Allah SWT yang telah dijelaskan dalam Alquran surat Luqman ayat 13-14,

وَإِذْ قَالَ لُقْمَانُ لِابْنِهِ وَهُوَ يَعِظُهُ يَا بُنَيَّ لَا تُشْرِكْ بِاللَّهِ إِنَّ الشِّرْكَ لَظُلْمٌ عَظِيمٌ ﴿١٣﴾

وَوَصَّيْنَا الْإِنْسَانَ بِوَالِدَيْهِ حَمَلَتْهُ أُمُّهُ وَهْتًا عَلَىٰ وَهْنٍ وَفَصَّلَهُ فِي عَامَيْنِ أَنِ اشْكُرْ لِي

وَلِوَالِدَيْكَ إِلَى الْمَصِيرِ ﴿١٤﴾

Dan (ingatlah) ketika Luqman berkata kepada anaknya, di waktu ia memberi pelajaran kepadanya: "Hai anakku, janganlah kamu mempersekutukan Allah, Sesungguhnya mempersekutukan (Allah) adalah benar-benar kezaliman yang besar". Dan Kami perintahkan kepada manusia (berbuat baik) kepada dua orang ibu-bapanya; ibunya telah mengandungnya dalam Keadaan lemah yang bertambah-tambah, dan menyapihnya dalam dua tahun. bersyukurlah kepadaku dan kepada dua orang ibu bapakmu, hanya kepada-Kulah kembalimu. (Q.S. Luqman; 13-14).¹²

Ayat diatas menjelaskan bahwasanya Allah telah menetapkan aqidah kepada anak, mengesakan Allah dan tidak mempersekutukan-Nya dengan sesuatu selain Allah SWT. Masalah tauhid dikaitkan dengan hubungan orang tua dan anak. Allah mengingatkan betapa

¹¹ M. Quraish Shihab, *Membumikan Alquran, fungsi dan Peran Wahyu dalam Kehidupan Masyarakat*, Edisi Ke-2 (Bandung: Mizan, 2013), h. 172.

¹² Departemen RI, *Alquran Tajwid dan Terjemah*, h. 644.

penting dan dominan peran orang tua dalam menanamkan nilai-nilai tauhid dalam diri anak-anak.

Pendidikan dalam ayat tersebut sejalan dengan konsep pendidikan tarbiyah yang menitikberatkan pada pelaksanaan nilai-nilai Ilahiyah yang bersumber dari Allah SWT selaku Tuhan semesta alam. Dalam hubungan antara manusia tugas penyampaian nilai-nilai ajaran tersebut dibebankan kepada orang tua, sedangkan para pendidik tak lebih hanyalah sebagai tenaga profesional yang mengemban tugas berdasarkan kepercayaan para orang tua. Pada ayat ke 14, nasehat tersebut menekankan kepada anak agar senantiasa menghormati ibu terlebih dahulu, hal ini disebabkan karena ibu telah mengandungnya dengan susah payah, kemudian mengasuhnya dengan kasih sayang yang tulus dan ikhlas, sehingga ibu berpotensi untuk tidak dihiraukan oleh anak karena kelemahan ibu yang berbeda dengan bapak.

Tujuan merupakan sesuatu yang esensial bagi kehidupan manusia. Dengan adanya tujuan, semua aktivitas dan gerak manusia menjadi lebih dinamis, terarah, dan bermakna. Tanpa tujuan, aktivitas manusia akan terombang-ambing. Dengan demikian, seluruh karya, karsa manusia hendaknya memiliki orientasi tujuan tertentu, terlebih dengan apa yang dinamakan pendidikan. M. Quraish Shihab sebagai pakar tafsir dan juga orang yang sebagian besar hidupnya dicurahkan untuk kegiatan pendidikan memiliki pandangan tersendiri akan tujuan pendidikan.

Pertama tentang tujuan pendidikan. Dengan merujuk pada ayat ke 2 surat al-Jumu'ah yang berbunyi,

هُوَ الَّذِي بَعَثَ فِي الْأُمِّيِّينَ رَسُولًا مِنْهُمْ يَتْلُو عَلَيْهِمْ آيَاتِهِ وَيُزَكِّيهِمْ وَيُعَلِّمُهُمُ الْكِتَابَ

وَالْحِكْمَةَ وَإِنْ كَانُوا مِنْ قَبْلُ لَفِي ضَلَالٍ مُّبِينٍ ﴿٢﴾

Dia-lah yang mengutus kepada kaum yang buta huruf seorang Rasul di antara mereka, yang membacakan ayat-ayat-Nya kepada mereka, mensucikan mereka dan mengajarkan mereka kitab dan Hikmah (As Sunnah). dan Sesungguhnya mereka sebelumnya benar-benar dalam kesesatan yang nyata, (Q.S. Al Jumu'ah; 2).¹³

Terkait ayat ini M. Quraish Shihab mengatakan bahwa Rasulullah SAW, yang dalam hal ini bertindak sebagai penerima Alquran, bertugas untuk menyampaikan petunjuk-petunjuk kepada orang yang bertakwa sebagaimana tersebut pada ayat di atas, menyucikan dan mengajarkan manusia. Menyucikan dapat diidentikan dengan mendidik sedangkan mengajar tidak lain kecuali mengisi benak anak didik dengan pengetahuan yang berkaitan dengan alam metafisika serta fisika.¹⁴

Tujuan yang ingin dicapai dengan pembacaan, penyucian, dan pengajaran tersebut adalah sebuah bentuk pengabdian kepada Allah. Ini sejalan dengan tujuan penciptaan manusia sebagaimana ditegaskan oleh Alquran dalam surat Adz-Dzariyat ayat 56 yang berbunyi.

¹³ Departemen RI, *Alquran Tajwid dan Terjemah*, h. 922.

¹⁴ M. Quraish Shihab, *Membumikan Alquran, fungsi dan Peran Wahyu dalam Kehidupan Masyarakat*, h. 256.

وَمَا خَلَقْتُ الْجِنَّ وَالْإِنْسَ إِلَّا لِيَعْبُدُونِ ﴿٥٦﴾

Dan aku tidak menciptakan jin dan manusia melainkan supaya mereka mengabdikan kepada-Ku. (Q.S. Adz-Dzariyat; 56).¹⁵

M. Quraish Shihab sendiri mengartikan ayat di atas dengan, “Aku tidak menciptakan jin dan manusia untuk suatu manfaat yang kembali kepada-Ku, tetapi mereka Aku ciptakan untuk beribadah kepada-Ku. Dan ibadah itu sangat bermanfaat untuk mereka sendiri.” Atas dasar tersebut M. Quraish Shihab berkesimpulan bahwa tujuan pendidikan Alquran adalah membina manusia secara pribadi dan kelompok sehingga mampu menjelaskan fungsinya sebagai hamba Allah SWT dan khalifah-Nya guna membangun dunia ini sesuai dengan konsep yang ditetapkan oleh Allah SWT.¹⁶

Wajar kiranya jika M. Quraish Shihab berpendapat demikian, latar belakang beliau sebagai pakar tafsir jelas telah memenuhi pemikiran beliau di banyak aspek salah satunya terkait pendidikan. Dengan kepakarannya sebagai mufassir itulah M. Quraish Shihab menjelaskan konsep pendidikan dalam perspektif Alquran.

Ibadah sendiri terdiri dari ibadah *mahdhah* (murni) dan *ghairu mahdhah* (tidak murni). Ibadah mahdhah adalah ibadah yang telah ditentukan oleh Allah baik waktu, tempat, serta tatacaranya, seperti zakat, puasa, shalat, haji. Ibadah ghairu mahdhah adalah segala aktivitas lahir dan batin manusia yang dimaksudkannya untuk mendekatkan diri kepada Allah. Hubungan muamalah antar manusia dapat menjadi sebuah ibadah bahkan hubungan seks pun dapat terhitung ibadah jika dikerjakakan sesuai dengan ketentuan agama. Dengan begitu ayat 56 Surat Adz-Dzariyat menjelaskan bahwa Allah menghendaki agar segala aktivitas manusia dilakukannya demi karena Allah, yakni sesuai dan sejalan dengan tuntunan petunjuk-Nya.

Selanjutnya, M. Quraish Shihab mengambil pendapat Thabathaba’I yang memahami *ista’marakum fil ardh* dalam arti mengolah bumi sehingga beralih menjadi suatu tempat dan kondisi yang memungkinkan manfaatnya dapat dipetik seperti membangun pemukiman untuk dihuni, masjid untuk tempat ibadah, tanah untuk pertanian, taman untuk dipetik buahnya dan rekreasi. Dengan demikian penggalan ayat tersebut bermakna bahwa Allah swt telah mewujudkan melalui bahan bumi ini, manusia yang Dia sempurnakan dengan mendidiknya tahap demi setahap dan menganugrahkannya fitrah berupa potensi yang menjadikan ia mampu mengolah bumi dengan mengalihkannya ke suatu kondisi di mana ia dapat memanfaatkan demi kepentingan hidupnya.¹⁷

M. Quraish Shihab menyimpulkan bahwa ayat di atas mengandung perintah kepada manusia langsung ataupun tidak langsung untuk membangun bumi dalam kedudukannya sebagai khalifah, sekaligus menjadi alasan mengapa manusia harus menyembah Allah swt semata. Berhubungan dengan tugas manusia sebagai khalifah, M. Quraish Shihab mengatakan bahwa penjabaran tugas kekhalifahan harus sejalan dan diangkat dari dalam masyarakat itu masing-masing. Itu dikarenakan adanya corak yang berbeda antara satu masyarakat dengan

¹⁵ Departemen RI, *Alquran Tajwid dan Terjemah*, h. 885.

¹⁶ M. Quraish Shihab, *Membumikan Alquran, fungsi dan Peran Wahyu dalam Kehidupan Masyarakat*, h. 269.

¹⁷ M. Quraish Shihab, *Tafsir Al-Misbah*, Vol. 6, h. 285.

masyarakat lain. Dari situ pula diambil kesimpulan bahwa sistem serta tujuan pendidikan bagi suatu masyarakat atau negara tidak dapat diimpor atau diekspor dari atau ke suatu negara atau masyarakat.¹⁸

Pandangan tentang tujuan pendidikan yang diutarakan M. Quraish Shihab sangat selaras dengan tujuan pendidikan yang dicetuskan oleh para cendekiawan Muslim. Seperti halnya Hamka, di mana menurut beliau, pendidikan memiliki dua dimensi yang pertama terkait pengembangan pemahaman tentang kehidupan konkret dalam konteks dirinya sesama manusia dan alam semesta dan dimensi kedua yang menjadikan pendidikan sebagai jembatan dalam mencapai hubungan yang abadi dengan Sang Pencipta. Dalam pandangan Hamka bisa dikatakan bahwa tujuan pendidikan adalah mengenal dan mencari keridhaan Allah swt, membangun budi pekerti untuk berakhlak mulia.¹⁹

Dalam hal tujuan pendidikan, lagi-lagi terdapat kesamaan antara pendapat M. Quraish Shihab dengan tujuan pendidikan Islam yang dikemukakan oleh Muhammad Athiyah yang dikutip oleh Zuhairini dalam bukunya, di mana tujuan pendidikan Islam adalah untuk membantu pembentukan akhlak yang mulia, persiapan untuk kehidupan dunia dan kehidupan akhirat, dan menyiapkan pelajar dari segi professional, teknis, dan perusahaan supaya ia dapat menguasai profesi tertentu.²⁰

Mengacu pemikiran M. Quraish Shihab terkait tujuan pendidikan kita bisa menyimpulkan bahwa tujuan pendidikan menurut M. Quraish Shihab hanya mengarah kepada tujuan pendidikan umum atau yang disebut juga tujuan sempurna. Tujuan sempurna berarti mengarah kepada tujuan terakhir, atau tujuan bulat suatu pendidikan, dalam bukunya, As'aril Muhajir mengatakan bahwa tujuan pendidikan ialah terciptanya insan kaffah, insan yang memiliki dimensi-dimensi religius, budaya, juga ilmiah.

Menurut M. Quraish Shihab, pendidikan tidaklah melulu soal ilmu yang bersifat kognitif, ia menyatakan bahwa secara umum ilmu tidak mampu menciptakan kebahagiaan manusia. Ilmu hanya mampu menciptakan pribadi-pribadi manusia secara satu dimensi, sehingga walaupun manusia mampu berbuat sesuatu, dia sering kali tidak bijaksana. Pendidikan haruslah meliputi aspek religius-ilmiah, akal dan spiritual sehingga apa yang dikehendaki, yaitu terciptanya manusia yang seimbang dalam duniawi-ukhrowi tercapai.²¹

Berdasarkan penjelasan tersebut dapat dikatakan bahwa aktivitas pendidikan termasuk ke dalam aktivitas beribadah kepada Allah. Membentuk manusia yang berkualitas baik jasmani maupun rohani, juga mampu mengendalikan hawa nafsu untuk taat dan berbuat baik. Pendidikan merupakan jalan agar manusia mampu mengasah baik intelektual, keterampilan, dan moral. Ketiga elemen yang terasah dan terbina oleh pendidikan merupakan jalan menuju pengenalan dan pendekatan terhadap sang Pencipta, yakni Allah SWT.

Terkait metode pembelajaran, secara umum M. Quraish Shihab menggunakan istilah metode penyampaian materi. Menurutnya Alquran memandang dalam mengarahkan

¹⁸ M. Quraish Shihab, *Membumikan Alquran, fungsi dan Peran Wahyu dalam Kehidupan Masyarakat*, h. 173.

¹⁹ Samsul Nizar, *Memperbincangkan Dinamika Intelektual dan Pemikiran Hamka tentang Pendidikan Islam* (Jakarta: Kencana Pranada Media Group, 2007), h. 117.

²⁰ Zuhairini dkk, *Filsafat Pendidikan Islam*, (Jakarta: PT. Bumi Aksara, 2019), h. 164.

²¹ M. Quraish Shihab, *Membumikan Alquran, fungsi dan Peran Wahyu dalam Kehidupan Masyarakat*, h. 65.

pendidikannya kepada manusia dengan memperlakukan makhluk tersebut dengan unsur penciptaannya yakni jasmani, jiwa, dan akal. Atau dengan kata lain mengarahkan untuk menjadikan manusia seutuhnya. Karena itu, materi-materi pendidikan yang disajikan Alquran hampir selalu mengarah pada jiwa, akal, dan raga manusia.

Menurut M. Quraish Shihab bahwa dalam penyajian materi pendidikan, Alquran membuktikan kebenaran materi tersebut melalui pembuktian-pembuktian, baik dengan argumentasi argumentasi yang dikemukakannya maupun yang dapat dibuktikan sendiri oleh manusia (peserta didik) melalui penalaran akalnya. Ini dianjurkan oleh Alquran untuk dilakukan saat mengemukakan materi tersebut, mengutip Abdul Karim Khatib yang mengemukakan “agar akal manusia merasa bahwa ia berperan dalam menemukan hakikat materi yang disajikan itu.”²²

Lebih lanjut, M. Quraish Shihab menegaskan bahwa dalam mengemukakan kisah-kisah, Alquran tidak segan-segan menceritakan kelemahan manusia. Namun hal tersebut digambarkan sebagaimana adanya, tanpa menojolkan segi-segi yang dapat mengundang tepuk tangan dan rangsangan. Ini agaknya menampilkan sebuah kekhawatiran tersendiri dari M. Quraish Shihab bahwa sering kali cerita-cerita menonjolkan aspek negatif bagi para pembacanya.

Menurut M. Quraish Shihab pengisahan di dalam Alquran biasanya diakhiri dengan menggarisbawahi akibat kelemahan, atau dengan melukiskan saat kesadaran manusia dan kemenangannya mengatasi kelemahan tadi. Bahkan metode kisah atau cerita merupakan salah satu instrument mengajar favorit dari para pendidik besar kelas dunia. Itu dikarenakan metode kisah itu membuat pendidik mengajar dengan daya Tarik dan bukan paksaan. Cerita membingkai imajinasi dan menyentuh hati. Itulah mengapa metode kisah merupakan cara alami untuk melibatkan dan membangun sisi emosional dari karakter seorang anak.²³

Di samping itu Alquran juga menggunakan metode pembiasaan dalam menanamkan ajarannya kepada umat manusia. Dalam hal ini M. Quraish Shihab mengatakan, pembiasaan yang pada akhirnya melahirkan kebiasaan yang ditempuh pula oleh Alquran dalam rangka menetapkan pelaksanaan materi-materi ajarannya. Pembiasaan tersebut menyangkut segi-segi pasif maupun aktif. Namun perlu diperhatikan bahwa pembiasaan yang digunakan Alquran terkait segi pasif hanyalah dalam hal-hal berhubungan erat dengan kondisi sosial dan ekonomi, bukan menyangkut kondisi kejiwaan yang berhubungan erat dengan akidah dan etika. Sedangkan dalam hal yang bersifat aktif atau menuntut pelaksanaan, ditemui pembiasaan tersebut secara menyeluruh.²⁴

Hal demikian menurut M. Quraish Shihab dapat dibuktikan dengan mengamati larangannya yang bersifat pasti tanpa bertahap terhadap penyembahan berhala, syirik, atau kebohongan. Sedangkan dalam hal-hal semacam pelarangan minuman keras, zina, atau riba, dan sebagainya semuanya melalui proses yang berangsur-angsur. Sebagai contoh, larangan bertahap dalam hal minuman keras adalah ayat 219 Surat Al-Baqarah yang berbunyi,

²² M. Quraish Shihab, *Tafsir Al-Misbah; Pesan, Kesan dan Keserasian Alquran*, Vol. 6 Cet. Ke-IV, h. 190.

²³ M. Quraish Shihab, *Tafsir Al-Misbah; Pesan, Kesan dan Keserasian Alquran*, Vol. 10 Cet. Ke-III, h. 409.

²⁴ M. Quraish Shihab, *Membumikan Alquran, fungsi dan Peran Wahyu dalam Kehidupan Masyarakat*, h. 275.

﴿ يَسْأَلُونَكَ عَنِ الْخَمْرِ وَالْمَيْسِرِ قُلْ فِيهِمَا إِثْمٌ كَبِيرٌ وَمَنْفَعٌ لِلنَّاسِ وَإِثْمُهُمَا أَكْبَرُ مِنْ نَفْعِهِمَا وَيَسْأَلُونَكَ مَاذَا يُنْفِقُونَ قُلِ الْعَفْوَ كَذَلِكَ يُبَيِّنُ اللَّهُ لَكُمْ آيَاتِهِ لَعَلَّكُمْ تَتَّقُونَ ﴾

Mereka bertanya kepadamu (Nabi Muhammad) tentang khamr⁶⁴) dan judi. Katakanlah, “Pada keduanya terdapat dosa besar dan beberapa manfaat bagi manusia. (Akan tetapi,) dosa keduanya lebih besar daripada manfaatnya.” Mereka (juga) bertanya kepadamu (tentang) apa yang mereka infakkan. Katakanlah, “(Yang diinfakkan adalah) kelebihan (dari apa yang diperlukan).” Demikianlah Allah menerangkan ayat-ayat-Nya kepadamu agar kamu berpikir. (Q.S. Al-Baqarah; 219).²⁵

Pelarangan selanjutnya meningkat dengan mengharamkan meminum khamr jika di dekat waktu shalat karena sifat khamr yang memabukkan dan membuat orang-orang yang shalat dalam keadaan mabuk meracau dengan tidak jelas. Dengan turunnya ayat ini, orang-orang semakin banyak yang menghindari dari khamr.²⁶ Itulah salah satu contoh metode Alquran dalam mendidik umat, seperti pelarangan minuman keras secara bertahap yang merupakan contoh dari penerapan metode dialogis yang amat memperhatikan sisi psikologis manusia.

Dari semua pembahasan yang telah di paparkan, dapat disimpulkan bahwa Alquran menggunakan berbagai macam metode untuk mendidik dan mengajar manusia. Metode diskusi, kisah, panutan, pembiasaan, nasehat-nasehat dan sebagainya diterapkan Alquran untuk menuntun nalar peserta didik menemukan kebenaran, disaat yang bersamaan amat memperhatikan kesiapan psikologis umat jika itu berkaitan dengan suatu hukum khususnya terkait dengan sebuah pelarangan sesuatu yang mulanya menjadi budaya. Jika berkaitan dengan sebuah kisah maka Alquran menuntut agar materi yang dipaparkan diyakini kebenarannya melalui argumentas-argumentasi logika dan kisah-kisah yang dipaparkannya mengantarkan mereka kepada nilai-nilai kebajikan.

Metode pembelajaran yang disarankan oleh M. Quraish Shihab Alquran amat cocok dengan pembelajaran yang terpusat pada peserta didik. Menurut M. Quraish Shihab metode dianalogikan seperti alat. Dikarenakan sebagai salah satu alat mencapai tujuan maka metode selalu memperhatikan kondisi peserta didik, khususnya pada isi psikologis, Alquran, dengan segala metode yang ditempuhnya bertujuan untuk membangun kejiwaan yang mantap dan mental yang sehat sehingga pembelajar dapat berlangsung dengan optimal. Pembelajaran disini bukan saja tentang menguatkan kognitif peserta didik, tetapi pembelajaran yang memiliki pengaruh jangka Panjang dimana peserta didik tidak hanya mengetahui sebuah teori tetapi mengamalkan apa yang mereka ketahui.

Berdasarkan uraian analisis konsep pendidikan Islam menurut M. Quraish Shihab peneliti menyimpulkan hasil penelitian tentang pemikiran M. Quraish Shihab dalam bentuk bagan sebagai berikut.

²⁵ Departemen RI, *Alquran Tajwid dan Terjemah*, h. 49.

²⁶ M. Quraish Shihab, *Tafsir Al-Misbah; Pesan, Kesan dan Keserasian Alquran* (Jakarta: Lentera Hati, 2005), Vol. 1, Cet. Ke-V, h. 462.

SIMPULAN DAN SARAN

Penelitian ini merupakan penelitian kualitatif deskriptif yang bertujuan untuk mengetahui konsep pendidikan Islam M. Quraish Shihab. Berdasarkan uraian-uraian sebagaimana yang telah dipaparkan pada bab-bab sebelumnya, maka peneliti menyimpulkan hal-hal sebagai berikut:

1. Konsep pendidikan dalam Alquran mengarahkan peserta didik agar dapat melaksanakan fungsinya sebagai manusia untuk mengabdikan kepada Allah dan menjadi khalifah-Nya. Deskripsi kependidikan yang diberikan oleh Alquran nampak lebih memosisikan dirinya sebagai pemandu dalam prinsip dan tidak memasuki Kawasan teknis.
2. Terkait dengan tujuan pendidikan M. Quraish Shihab mengambil tujuan pendidikan dari sudut pandang Alquran. M. Quraish Shihab mengemukakan bahwa tujuan Pendidikan adalah membina manusia agar menyadari bahwa dirinya sebagai hamba Allah dan menjalani fungsinya sebagai khalifah Allah di muka bumi ini. Pendidikan menurut M. Quraish Shihab harus memerhatikan ketiga aspek dalam diri manusia yaitu akal, jiwa dan jasmani. Pembinaan akal menghasilkan ilmu, pembinaan jiwa menghasilkan kesucian dan etika, serta pembinaan jasmani akan menghasilkan keterampilan. M. Quraish Shihab mengemukakan bahwa tujuan pendidikan mengarah pada tujuan Pendidikan umum atau yang disebut juga tujuan sempurna. Tujuan sempurna atau tujuan akhir pendidikan menurut M. Quraish Shihab harus mampu membentuk manusia dwidimensi yang seimbang antara akal dan iman, akal dan spiritual, dan terakhir adalah duniawi dan ukhrowi.
3. Mengenai metode pembelajaran secara umum M. Quraish Shihab juga mengambil pendekatan berdasarkan Alquran, yang memperlakukan manusia sesuai dengan unsur penciptaannya yaitu jasmani, jiwa, dan akal. Oleh karena itu M. Quraish Shihab tidak mengusulkan sebuah metode khusus dalam penyampaian materi. Hal terpenting dalam penyampaian materi adalah dengan kalimat-kalimat yang menggugah dan menyentuh hati, disertai contoh dan pembiasaan untuk memantapkan materi yang diajarkan. Dapat disimpulkan bahwa metode pembelajaran yang disarankan oleh M. Quraish Shihab dari Alquran amat selaras dengan pembelajaran yang terpusat pada peserta didik (*student center*), hal tersebut disebabkan karena setiap metodenya selalu memperhatikan kondisi peserta didik yaitu akal, fisik, maupun psikologis.
4. Menurut M. Quraish Shihab, masa berlangsungnya pendidikan adalah sepanjang hayat. Pendidikan dalam hal ini bukan hanya pendidikan formal, tetapi semua proses formal, informal, dan nonformal. Ilmu yang begitu luas dan umur manusia yang terbatas mengharuskan manusia manusia menuntut ilmu seumur hidup untuk mengoptimalkan kemampuannya.

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THE CONCEPT OF CHILDREN'S EDUCATION IN THE AL-QUR'AN LETTER LUQMAN VERSE 13 FROM PERSPECTIVE TAFSIR AL-MISBAH

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Abstract

The results of the study found that children's education in the family from the perspective of the interpretation of Al Mishbah by M. Quraish Shihab in the Qur'an Surah Luqman verses 13-15 is to provide an important role for families, especially parents, in educating children (starting at an early age) both in terms of ethics, the environment, especially in terms of monotheism (not associating partners with Allah), do good to both parents, do good to parents unless they command things that lead to polytheism, do not do lies, never lie, are not arrogant and behave politely (noble character). This also encourages the creation of human resources who instill the education of children in families in Indonesia.

The concept of children's education in Surah Luqman verses 12-15 according to the thought of M. Quraish Shihab includes three concepts, namely monotheism education or creed, moral education and worship education. Children's education according to Ahmad Mustafa al-Maraghi in Tafsir al-Maraghi, namely parents must be able to provide good education to their children, especially in praying, where prayer is a pillar of Islam that must be done and can be a sin if left behind, and do what ma'ruf and prevent evil that occurs on this earth, then must be patient in dealing with problems and difficulties. To children, parents should advise not to give up easily in the face of all kinds of difficulties, but must always pray to Allah for a good way out. In this way, parents can expand their children's hearts so that their minds are not stuck, as well as educate them to look for good alternatives in solving problems with clear minds and open hearts.

Keywords: *Tafsir Al Misbah, Children's Education*

INTRODUCTION

Education has a very important role in this day and age. Because without education the process of transformation and actualization of modern knowledge is difficult to realize. In human life, education has a very important role in shaping future generations. With education, humans are expected to be able to produce people who are qualified, responsible and able to overcome changes in the future. In essence, education is preparing and accompanying someone so that they can make progress and achieve perfection.

Education is an effort to shape the human person and must go through a long process with results that cannot be known immediately. In the process of formation, a mature and careful calculation is needed based on views and thoughts or correct theories, so that failure or mistakes in the formation steps of students can be avoided.

Education, which is one of the fundamental factors in human life, has become one of the areas covered in the content of the holy verses of the Koran, in fact it has become its main content, because the journey of human life on earth is a continuous chain of education and the

Prophet was sent God to be teachers (subjects of education) who introduce mankind to God Almighty.

In general, many verses in the Koran contain demands for humanity in its efforts to give birth to a better future generation. Things such as increasing faith and piety, developing religious insight and guidance to form a complete human being are things that can be achieved through education. The knowledge gained from the educational process is an important provision for every person to live their life. In the Koran, Surah Al-Mujaadilah verse 11, Allah says,

يَا أَيُّهَا الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا إِذَا قِيلَ لَكُمْ تَقَسَّحُوا فِي الْمَجَالِسِ فَافْسَحُوا يَفْسَحِ اللَّهُ لَكُمْ وَإِذَا قِيلَ
انشُرُوا فَانشُرُوا يَرْفَعِ اللَّهُ الَّذِينَ آمَنُوا مِنْكُمْ وَالَّذِينَ أُوتُوا الْعِلْمَ دَرَجَاتٍ وَاللَّهُ بِمَا تَعْمَلُونَ

خَيْرٌ ﴿١١﴾

O you who believe, if it is said to you "Make room in the assemblies," make room, surely Allah will give you space. When it is said, "Stand up," (you) stand up. Allah will surely elevate those who believe among you and those who have been given knowledge to several degrees. Allah is careful about what you do. (Q.S. Al-Mujadalah; 11).¹

The educational process, as it can be understood as a process where parents try to care for and guide their children to become adults and prepare them to be able to carry out their life tasks, can be seen and understood as a natural symptom and process. In the sense that the educational process takes place as it is, according to applicable regulations and habits, and is inseparable from other natural processes and phenomena. The process and symptoms of education also exist and take place in every society wherever and whenever they are.

Islamic education is at the same time faith education and charity education. And because Islamic teachings contain teachings about the personal attitudes and behavior of society, towards the welfare of individual and collective life, Islamic education is both individual education and community education.²

This opinion can be understood that the essence of religious education lies in mastering the values contained in the values of Islamic religious teachings, thus religious education is a conscious effort made by an educator to provide knowledge, experience, skills and skills to students so that they become true Muslims who are always devout, virtuous, have a complete personality, understand and appreciate and can practice the teachings of the Islamic religion in their daily lives.

The opinion above can be understood that educating children about religious values must start first with someone who truly reflects religious values in terms of attitudes, behavior,

¹ Departemen Agama RI, *Al-Qur'an dan Terjemahnya* (Jakarta: PT Intermedia, 2011), h. 900.

² Abdul Majid, *Pendidikan Agama Islam Berbasis Kompetensi*, (Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya, 2014), h. 32.

movements, the way they speak, the way they dress, and the way they deal with problems. in his entire person.

M. Quraish Shihab explained that humans who are developed through education are creatures who have material (physical) and immaterial (mind and soul) elements. Cultivating his mind produces knowledge, cultivating his soul produces purity and ethics, while cultivating his body produces skills. By combining these elements, a two-dimensional being is created in one balance, world and hereafter, knowledge and faith. That is why in Islamic education the terms *adab addin* and *adabal-dun-ya* are known.

Departing from the verses that describe how important education is for children, it encourages researchers to look more deeply at the object of research in aspects of children's education according to Prof. H. Quraish Shihab in the interpretation of Al Misbah as the focus of the study. From these reasons, the researcher chose a theme for children's education in a study entitled "The Concept of Children's Education in the Al-Qur'an Surah Luqman verse 13 from the perspective of Tafsir Al-Misbah."

RESEARCH METHODS

This type of research is library research which is also included in the second model of qualitative research. Library Research means a study by examining books related to the thesis taken from the library, meaning that data is searched and found through library research from books that are relevant to the discussion.³

In this case, library materials are used as a source of ideas for finding new ideas, as basic material for making deductions from existing knowledge, so that a new theoretical framework can be developed or as a basis for solving problems.

The approach used by researchers in this research is a qualitative approach. Because the data is qualitative, efforts to explain the data are made in the form of expressions or sentences, thus the analysis can be carried out using a historical and philosophical approach, namely an approach that examines the concept of children's education, especially the values contained in the Koran, studying the interpretation of Al -Misbah by M. Quraish Shihab.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The author draws on the essence of children's education in the Al-Qur'an which is contained in Surah Luqman verses 13-19, including the following:

1. Creed Education

Aqidah education is Luqman's first and foremost education for his children. This education aims to liberate (free) humans from dependence on other than Allah SWT. Liberation education is pursued through efforts to instill faith in Allah SWT and prohibit shirk.⁴

Luqman invited his son to free himself from all kinds of polytheism, because polytheism is a very dangerous sin.

Luqman advises and teaches matters of faith and devotion to his children because the importance of faith education (*tawhidan*) is to build belief in one God so that his

³ Djam'an Satori, *Metodologi Penelitian Kualitatif*, (Bandung: Alfabeta, 2017), h. 22

⁴ Miftahul Huda, *Idealitas Pendidikan Anak*, h. 120

children do not fall into acts of polytheism and thus fall into great injustice. Luqman uses the mau'izah hasanah method to provide the doctrine of faith education.

Liberation education here means that Luqman hopes that his child will be free from dependence on other than Allah SWT, that the best place to depend, complain and complain is only Allah SWT, and only trust in one God, namely Allah SWT, which is meant by dependence. here is excessive hope for Allah SWT's creatures for gifts, awards, and so on. Because in fact, without us expecting it from creatures, Allah SWT already knows it and has prepared an award, even though it is not directly given in this world, it will be given in the afterlife.

2. Worship Education (Shari'ah)

Worship education is an important education in every child's development. This education is one of the educational means to build a close relationship with God. This worship education emphasizes practical worship through habits so that it can help children's knowledge about worship.

Included in worship education is the command to perform prayers. According to Al-Baidhawi, Luqman's order to pray to his son is to perfect himself personally, and the order to amar ma'ruf nahi munkar to perfect his community, and the order to be patient with what happens as a consequence of his prayer and preaching.

The essence of the religious education that Luqman gives to his children through advice is that there are four basic elements of life capital that are very important. The four elements in Luqman's advice include the command to perform prayers, call to goodness (ma'ruf), prevent evil (munkar), and the command to be patient with everything that befalls him. Broadly speaking, these four elements have two objectives, namely worship to perform prayers and be patient as a worship aimed at Allah SWT, and worship calling for goodness and preventing evil as worship aimed at the social dimension.

Worship education aims to build relationships or relationships vertically with the Creator as an embodiment of continuity with aqidah (tawhid) education. So Luqman put forward the command for prayer in his advice to educate his children so that they can build a good relationship with God, because prayer is a pillar of religion. Apart from being a pillar of religion, prayer is also a way to express gratitude for the blessings given by Allah SWT.

Then it was stated that Luqman advised his son by ordering him to promote goodness and prevent evil towards fellow humans as a form of caring for others. Before carrying out amar ma'ruf nahi munkar, individuals must improve themselves first, because what they will face is society, where it is a community containing various kinds of backgrounds, characters, customs, etc. When oneself introspects and does not do things that are not in accordance with Islamic rules, then society will follow automatically.

Being patient is the peak of an attitude when you have carried out various ways to preach in society. By being patient with what has happened, a strength will emerge within you so that you become more confident in the power of Allah SWT and can become a means of increasing the intensity of your closeness to Allah SWT. Because patience in this case is a manifestation of the consequences of the prayers and da'wah

that have been carried out. In worship, one must be free from dependence on awards in the form of praise from humans or others because of the level of one's worship. The higher the level of worship performed, the greater the sense of closeness of relationship with Allah SWT.

3. Moral Education

Education in the field of morals is divided into two, namely personal morals and social morals. Luqman provides personal moral education to his children by introducing good ethics to both parents. After children are introduced to the concept of morals towards God through worship, and being filial to their parents, they are then taught morals in the context of society (social morals) which includes education in preaching/amar ma'ruf nahi evil and being patient.

Also ethical education which includes social etiquette (meeting), speaking and walking. Luqman Hakim's four basic principles of education for his children fulfill the target of forming a perfect human being consisting of perfection of aqidah, shari'ah and morals (Iman, Islam and Ihsan).⁵

The next advice given by Luqman to his children as the essence of education is moral education for parents and moral education for fellow humans. Where morals towards Allah SWT are not associating partners with Him, then morals towards parents are not disobeying them, always respecting them properly, and caring for them wholeheartedly even though they have different beliefs from them. Mothers and fathers are the reason we exist in this world.

In this verse it is stated that mothers have great services, as well as fathers have great services in life. The mother who was pregnant for nine months and ten days, then gave birth at the risk of her life and did not stop there, the mother who provided exclusive breast milk for two years and provided initial education at every moment. Apart from that, you have been instrumental in earning a halal living to sustain life. My father was willing to be stung by the hot sun to give a bite of halal rice to his family. Apart from that, the father is also a leader figure for his children in the family.

So with the various sacrifices made by these parents, it is not appropriate to disobey him and hurt his heart. Even if parents have different beliefs or do not share the same aqidah (faith). If parents order them to follow it even though the child's faith is correct, then they must be appreciated and respected and then refuse it politely and kindly.

Apart from having to have morals towards parents, you must also have morals towards fellow humans, because life takes place in the wider community and humans are social creatures, namely creatures who cannot live alone. In the verse above, morals towards others include being polite in socializing, not being arrogant or haughty, being simple in walking and being gentle in speaking. Luqman warned his children about these morals so that they should always be polite to each other, then warned his children to be wary of arrogant and arrogant attitudes because humans should not have these attitudes.

Then Luqman reminded his son to be gentle in speaking and soften his voice because Luqman gave the impression that the worst voice was the voice of a donkey.

⁵ Miftahul Huda, *Idealitas Pendidikan Anak*, h. 126-127

In having morals, freedom from dependence on creatures is also necessary, because in this case of morals there is a high risk of heart disease and temptation in the form of human praise for the behavior carried out, so that it will cause individuals to have good morals only to be seen as good by humans without paying attention to whether they are good. in the view of the creator, namely Allah SWT.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of research and discussions carried out by researchers, the conclusions in this study are:

1. Children's education in the family from the perspective of the interpretation of Al Mishbah by M. Quraish Shihab in the Koran Surah Luqman verses 13-15 is to provide an important role for the family, especially parents, in educating children (starting from an early age) both in terms of ethics and the environment, especially in terms of monotheism. (not ascribing partners to Allah), doing good to both parents, doing good to parents unless they command things that lead to polytheism, not committing lies, never telling lies, not being arrogant and behaving politely (having noble character). This also encourages the creation of human resources that enhance children's education in families in Indonesia.
2. Children's education in the Al-Qur'an surah Luqman verses 13-19 is a conscious effort made to guide, develop and direct children in developing their physical-spiritual potential (fitrah) so that they are able to achieve harmony and harmony in their lives in this world and the hereafter with efforts to internalize and transform existing educational values, culture and customs.
3. Children's education in the Al-Qur'an surah Luqman verses 13-19 according to Al-Misbah's interpretation includes three aspects of education which are the main (foundations), namely: first, Aqidah education, as basic education for introduction and education of belief in self. -The Oneness of God. Second, Worship Education, as education to build a relationship with God and as an embodiment of continuity and implementation of aqidah education. Third, Moral Education, as a provision for children to adapt themselves to their family (parents) and interact with society and their environment in their lives.

In order to further develop studies and research in the field of education, the author provides suggestions for readers, so that they can take lessons and benefits from the various stories contained in the Al-Qur'an, especially the stories in Surah Luqman verses 13-19 and can be applied in in his daily life.

For educators in educational institutions, educators are expected to carry out teaching and learning activities by providing the basics of Islamic religious education to accompany each child's development, such as aqidah education, worship education, and moral education.

For parents who are educators in the home or family environment, parents play an important role in every child's development in forming an educated child's personality when they grow up. Therefore, parents play the role of being role models and applying the

education that children receive in educational institutions so that there is harmonization between education in the school environment and in the home or family environment.

For future researchers. The researcher suggests that future researchers hope to be able to complete the deficiencies in this research and find the best concept according to current developments to create Islamic Religious Education so that it can create students with noble character based on the points found in this research.

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THE INFLUENCE OF THE COMPLETENESS OF ISLAMIC RELIGIOUS EDUCATION LEARNING FACILITIES ON STUDENT LEARNING OUTCOMES AT UPT. SD NEGERI 16 SIDO MULYO MEDANG DERAS DISTRICT COAL DISTRICT

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Abstract

This research approach is a quantitative approach, namely research where the data obtained is related to numbers which causes the use of statistical analysis techniques. The results of the research in this thesis, based on calculations, the coefficient of determination is 18.31%. Thus it can be seen that the value of the contribution of the completeness of learning facilities in the subject of Islamic Religious Education to the learning outcomes of UPT students. SD Negeri 16 Sido Mulyo, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency by 18.31% and the remaining 82% (100% -18%) is influenced by variables that were not examined in this study such as learning motivation, learning environment, methods and learning strategies and so on.

The results of the analysis show that in the product moment value table "r" df 76, then with a df of 74 the rtable value is obtained at a significant level of 5% of 0.227, while at a significant level of 10% the rtable value is 0.227. It turns out that rxy (magnitude = 0.428) is much larger than rtable (which is 0.227 and 0.296). Because rxy is greater than rtable, thus the alternative hypothesis (Ha) is accepted and the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected, because there is a significant positive relationship between the completeness of learning facilities in Islamic religious education subjects and UPT student learning outcomes. SD Negeri 16 Sido Mulyo, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency.

Keywords: *Learning Facilities, Student Learning Outcomes, Influence*

INTRODUCTION

Currently the Indonesian nation is trying to increase human resources. This is done by increasing the intelligence of human resources. This also cannot be separated from efforts to be able to compete in the era of globalization. In this era of globalization, schools are also required to be more mature in various matters, and the field of education is a mainstay for preparing human resources to face the challenges of the times, preparation is carried out from elementary school to university. To be successful, we must improve effective and efficient services and facilities.

Schools as formal education centers are community institutions that are entrusted with the obligation to provide education that is bound by formal program rules and has clear targets or targets and has an official leadership structure for implementation or management. The education system needs to be adapted to development needs in all fields that require various types of expertise and skills and can simultaneously increase productivity, mentality, quality and work efficiency.

The development of science and technology is currently experiencing quite rapid progress so that inevitably everyone has to adapt to the times. These developments also affect

the world of education. All educational institutions continue to be required to provide the best education for students in accordance with the demands of the times. For this reason, educational institutions need to be supported by complete facilities and infrastructure as well as support from the professionalism of educators and education staff.

The continuity of the learning process in schools is supported by many things such as teachers, students, the school environment, parental support, and what is no less important is the completeness of learning facilities. If all of these are in synergy with each other, then the ideals of national education will be realized.

The importance of education for every individual is emphasized by the issuance of Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System in Chapter III Article 4 which states that education is carried out in a democratic and fair manner and is not discriminatory and upholds human rights, religious values, cultural values and diversity. nation.¹

In this educational process, one very important component so that the educational process can run well is the existence of school facilities. Facilities are everything that a school has to support teaching and learning activities. For example, study rooms, tables, chairs, libraries, laboratories, prayer rooms, and other practical equipment needed at the school. Thus, the facilities needed to complete the teaching and learning process so that it can run effectively and efficiently.

But it is very unfortunate, there are still many schools that do not manage facilities and infrastructure properly, the inaccuracies include planning, procurement, responsibility/management, maintenance/maintenance, deletion. Apart from that, the limited school facilities also affect students' attitudes, because the facilities needed for learning are not met so students will become lazy in their studies. This facility greatly influences and determines the success or failure of the teaching and learning process.

Based on the results conducted by researchers, on March 16 2022 at SD Negeri 16 Sido Mulyo, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency. The facilities at this school are classified as incomplete for Islamic Religious Education learning activities. Therefore, teachers only use existing textbooks. This also affects student learning outcomes in Islamic Religious Education subjects, where student learning outcomes are still relatively low. Due to the lack of learning facilities, students are less motivated.

From the results conducted by researchers, it shows the facilities at UPT schools. SD Negeri 16 Sido Mulyo, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency is classified as slightly low. This is an interesting problem to use as a basis for research. From the explanation above, the researcher drew a research title, namely the Influence of the Completeness of Islamic Religious Education Learning Facilities on Student Learning Outcomes at UPT. SD Negeri 16 Sido Mulyo, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research was carried out by tracing backwards to find out the factors that caused the incident without providing treatment or manipulating the variables studied. This research was conducted to find out information regarding the influence of the completeness of learning facilities in Islamic religious education subjects on UPT student learning outcomes. SD Negeri

¹ Abdul Kadir, *Dasar-Dasar Pendidikan*, (Jakarta: Kencana, 2012), h. 62.

16 Sido Mulyo, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency. Thus, this research is correlation research.

This is in accordance with the opinion of Suharsismi Arikunto who states that correlation research aims to find out whether there is a relationship, if there is one, how close the relationship is and whether the relationship is meaningful or not.²

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1. Questionnaire. A questionnaire is a data collection technique that is carried out by giving a set of questions or written statements to respondents to answer. A questionnaire is an efficient data collection technique if the researcher knows exactly the variables to be measured and knows what the respondent can expect. If you look at the way of answering, the questionnaire/questionnaire used in this research is a closed questionnaire, because the answers have been provided so that the respondent just has to choose which one suits them.
2. Documentation. A document is someone's notes or work about something that has passed. This document can be in the form of written text, artefacts, images or photos. This method is used by researchers to obtain written data, archives, UPT images. SD Negeri 16 Sido Mulyo, Medang Deras District.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A student's achievement or success can be influenced by internal factors, namely coming from oneself and external factors, namely coming from outside. One of the external factors that influences the learning process is learning facilities. Learning facilities are the most important thing in the learning process. If learning facilities do not or do not support the learning process, it is likely that students will easily get bored and the process of receiving information in learning will be hampered. Educational facilities include all the facilities needed in the teaching and learning process, both mobile and immobile, so that the achievement of educational goals can run smoothly, regularly, effectively and efficiently so that students can achieve optimal learning outcomes.

In general, learning facilities are divided into two, namely learning facilities are all equipment, materials and furniture that are directly used in education such as stationery, learning media and teaching aids; while infrastructure is all basic equipment that indirectly supports the implementation of the educational process, for example classrooms, laboratory rooms, library services and toilets.

Educational facilities and infrastructure are very important educational materials. Many schools have complete educational facilities and infrastructure so that they really support the

² Suharsismi Arikunto, *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktek*, Edisi Revisi. h. 251.

education process at school. The results of the analysis that has been carried out, namely using a determination test analysis, show that learning facilities have an influence on learning achievement.

Based on this calculation, the coefficient of determination value is 18.31%. Thus, it can be seen that the contribution value of the completeness of learning facilities in Islamic Religious Education subjects to the learning outcomes of UPT students. SD Negeri 16 Sido Mulyo, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency amounted to 18.31% and the remaining 82% (100%-18%) was influenced by variables not examined in this research such as learning motivation, learning environment, methods and learning strategies and so on. In the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test output table, it is known that the Asymp.Sig (2-tailed) significance value of 0.993 is greater than 0.05. So in accordance with the basis for decision making in the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test above, it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed. Thus, the assumptions or requirements for normality in the analysis have been met

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Based on the results of the analysis, it is known that in the table the value of "r" product moment df is 76, so with a df of 74 the rtable value obtained at the 5% significant level is 0.227, while at the 10% significant level the rtable value is obtained at 0.227. It turns out that rxy (magnitude = 0.428) is much larger than r table (which is 0.227 and 0.296). Because rxy is greater than rtable, the alternative hypothesis (Ha) is accepted and the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected, because there is a significant positive relationship between the completeness of learning facilities in Islamic religious education subjects and UPT student learning outcomes. SD Negeri 16 Sido Mulyo, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion of research results, the following can be concluded:

1. Referring to the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test output table, it is known that the Asymp.Sig (2-tailed) significance value of 0.993 is greater than 0.05. So in accordance with the basis for decision making in the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test, it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed. Thus, the assumptions or requirements for normality in the analysis have been met.
2. Based on calculations, the coefficient of determination value is 18.31%. Thus, it can be seen that the contribution value of the completeness of learning facilities in Islamic Religious Education subjects to the learning outcomes of UPT students. SD Negeri 16 Sido Mulyo, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency amounted to 18.31% and the remaining 82% (100%-18%) was influenced by variables not examined in this research such as learning motivation, learning environment, methods and learning strategies and so on.
3. The results of the analysis show that in the table the "r" product moment value df is 76, so with a df of 74 the rtable value obtained at the 5% significance level is 0.227, while at the 10% significance level the rtable value is obtained at 0.227. It turns out

that r_{xy} (magnitude = 0.428) is much larger than r table (which is 0.227 and 0.296). Because r_{xy} is greater than r table, the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted and the null hypothesis (H_o) is rejected, because there is a significant positive relationship between the completeness of learning facilities in Islamic religious education subjects and UPT student learning outcomes. SD Negeri 16 Sido Mulyo, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency.

From the conclusions stated above, the researcher will provide several suggestions which are expected to be useful for improving student learning outcomes, namely as follows:

1. It is hoped that UPT school educational institutions. SD Negeri 16 Sido Mulyo, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency to pay more attention to the learning facilities needed to improve student learning outcomes for the better.
2. For UPT Islamic Religious Education Teachers. SD Negeri 16 Sido Mulyo, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency, to maintain and further increase the maximum use of the facilities provided, so that it can motivate students to study harder and improve student learning outcomes for the better.
3. It is expected of UPT students. SD Negeri 16 Sido Mulyo, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency, to always try to motivate themselves in studying, improve themselves more in participating in school activities and be diligent in repeating lessons at home in order to obtain good learning results and obtain satisfactory learning results.
4. For future researchers, it is necessary to pay attention to the factors that influence student learning outcomes. Variables that influence student learning outcomes can be expanded, for example looking at student motivation, the Madrasah environment, the teaching effectiveness of educators and learning methods.

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KUNTOWIJOYO'S THOUGHTS ON PROPHETICS AND ITS IMPLEMENTATION IN THE CURRICULUM ISLAMIC EDUCATION

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Abstract

The results of the study note that Kuntowijoyo's prophetic values consist of three pillars, namely: humanization, liberation and transcendence which are derived from the Qur'an in Ali Imran verse 110. The concept of humanization is to humanize humans, eliminate material things, dependency, violence and hatred from humans. The liberation that Kuntowijoyo means in prophetic social science is in the context of science and not in an ideological context; namely knowledge based on transcendental noble values. In such a way, these liberative values must be understood or positioned in social science which has a prophetic responsibility to liberate human beings from the cruelty of poverty, the exploitation of abundance, the domination of oppressive structures and the hegemony of false consciousness. Meanwhile, transcendence is the most important element of prophetic ethics which also forms the basis of the other two elements; humanization and liberation. Transcendence gives direction to where and for what purpose humanization and liberation are carried out.

The implications of pfofetic values for the development of the PAI curriculum are: In developing the PAI curriculum in the future, in addition to maintaining its characteristics which prioritize efforts to internalize the values of Islamic teachings, whether in the form of 'aqidah, shari'ah or morality, it can also increase the portion of aspects of social change as the demands of the times. This effort is intended to increase the portion of efforts to instill human and social values. The content of Divine values and human values must have a balanced portion. In developing the PAI curriculum in schools, apart from being able to create students who have strong faith and piety in dealing with global developments and world trends, they also have a high sense of social concern for injustice in their society and are able to participate actively in developing society towards the desired progress.

Keywords: *Prophetic, Kuntowijoyo's Thought, Islamic Education Curriculum*

INTRODUCTION

In the current millennium, science and technology are increasingly advanced, this is marked by human civilization which has experienced significant shifts in various fields (social, cultural, educational, economic, religious and science and technology). With world civilization increasing rapidly, its influence is felt in Indonesia, namely with the birth of globalization. Globalization is a worldwide system, covering all aspects of human life, including economics, politics, culture, and of course including education.

Seeing this reality, Muslims must be able to adapt to global developments. In order to align with the demands of the times, the social transformation (change) of Muslims must of course remain within the framework of Islamic teachings. So religion must be able to answer

contemporary problems that arise. The relevance of religious interpretation in responding to the tremendous changes in the world has become a demand.

As pointed out by Mun'im A. Sirry, generally, religions that have lost the ability to respond creatively to social change often show a fundamentalistic face. If religion fails to guide its people, then religion will lock its followers into a valley of confusion, frustration, and ultimately give rise to destructive reactions, conflict and violence. In other words, difficulties in coping with social change can cause religion to lose its influence and relevance.¹

According to Kuntowijoyo, understanding Islamic teachings, more specifically the theological aspect, requires new interpretations in order to understand the ever-changing reality. Efforts to reorient religious understanding, both individually and collectively, are to respond to empirical realities from a divine perspective. So, religious teachings need to be given a new interpretation or interpretation in order to understand reality.

New interpretations in order to understand this reality can be done by elaborating religious teachings in the form of a social theory. This was chosen because it will be able to engineer change through objective language and emphasizes that the field it is working on is more empirical, historical and temporal in nature. The scope of this theory is engineering for social transformation. So the concept of social science emerged which was coined by Kuntowijoyo, namely Prophetic Social Science (ISP). ISP is a social science that not only explains and changes social phenomena but also provides instructions in which direction the transformation is carried out, for what purpose, and by whom.

There are those who understand the word *kuntum* used in the verse above as a perfect verb, *kana tammah* so that it means existence, that is, you exist in the best condition of the people. There are also those who understand it in the sense of the imperfect verb *kana naqishah* and thus it contains the meaning of the existence of something in the past without knowing when it happened and it does not also contain a hint that it never existed or that one day it will cease to exist. If so, then this verse means that in the knowledge of Allah you were the best of the people.²

Any bond of equality that unites living creatures, humans or animals, such as species, nation, tribe, religion, ideology, time, place and so on, then that bond has given birth to one people, and thus all members are brothers. How beautiful, flexible and supple this word is, so that it can encompass various meanings, and thus can accommodate togetherness and various differences.

In the word *ummah* there are deep meanings. It implies dynamic movement, direction, time, a clear path, as well as a style and way of life. In a sociological context, a congregation is a human association whose members all work together in the same direction, work together and move dynamically under shared leadership. The phrase "*tu'minuna billah*" can be understood as believing in the invitation to unite to hold fast to the rope of Allah, not to be divided. Thus, this verse states three conditions that must be fulfilled in order to achieve a

¹ Mun'im A. Sirry, *Membendung Militansi Agama; Iman dan Politik dalam Masyarakat Modern*, (Jakarta: Erlangga, 2003), h. 124.

² M. Quraish Shihab, *Tafsir Al-Mishbah; Pesan, Kesan dan Keserasian Al-Qur'an*, Vol. 2. Cet. Ke- IV, (Jakarta: Lentera Hati, 2005), h. 185-186.

position as the best of the people, namely amar makruf, nahi munkar and unity in holding fast to the ropes or teachings of Allah.³

This idea was actually inspired by Muhammad Iqbal, especially when Iqbal talked about the Mi'raj event of the Prophet Muhammad SAW. If the Prophet was a mystic or Sufi, Iqbal said of course he would not want to return to earth, because he felt at peace meeting God and being by His side. . The Prophet changed the course of history. He started a socio-cultural transformation based on prophetic ideals.

Responding to Kuntowijoyo's ISP concept, Moeslim Abdurrahman in Transformational Islam stated that Kuntowijoyo's thinking is not much different from the term Transformative Theology, namely thinking that departs from the basic view that the main mission of Islam is humanity.⁴

Efforts to instill and foster the values of humanization, liberation and transcendence will be more effectively carried out through the education process. The education process will never be separated from the cultivation of values, in order to form a mature human profile in terms of thought patterns, attitudes and behavior as well as moral character. This is in line with what Ahmad Tafsir said that the most important task of education, including education in schools, is to instill values.⁵ A dignified national civilization in order to make the nation's life more intelligent, aims to develop the potential of students so that they become human beings who believe and are devoted to God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become democratic and responsible citizens. answer.

However, in reality the current trend in the world of education is still lacking in carrying out its social functions. This is characterized by many incidents that are often visible to the naked eye, such as brawls and other immoral acts, indicating that the level of success of existing educational institutions is still questionable. Apart from that, events that often occur in our society such as corruption, unfair laws, fraud, riots among citizens, murder, and other disgraceful acts also often occur.

The educational curriculum is directed only to produce people who have been mapped according to their respective skills. Education has created machine humans, pragmatic humans, who are very dry of the spiritual dimension. Education increasingly distances humans from their humanity (dehumanization), from their freedom (deliberation), even from their God (detranscendence).

The curriculum as a reference or program for achieving educational goals has a big influence in shaping quality educational output. Likewise, the values embedded in students also depend on the values contained in the curriculum that is used as a reference. Moreover, when talking about Islamic Religious Education (PAI), where the cultivation of values is dominant, which will have an effect on the affective and psychomotor aspects as a real manifestation of vertical piety and horizontal piety in students.

³ M. Quraish Shihab, *Tafsir Al-Mishbah; Pesan, Kesan dan Keserasian Al-Qur'an*, Vol. 4. Cet. Ke- III, (Jakarta: Lentera Hati, 2005), h. 185-186

⁴ Moeslim Abdurrahman, *Islam Transformatif*, (Jakarta: PT. Pustaka Firdaus, 1997), h. 40.

⁵ Ahmad Tafsir, *Filsafat Pendidikan Islam; Integrasi Jasmani, Rohani dan Kalbu Memanusiakan Manusia*, (Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosda Karya, 2018), h. 49.

Based on the explanation above, the author intends to conduct research with the title "Kuntowijoyo's Thoughts About Prophetics and Its Implementation in the Islamic Religious Education Curriculum."

RESEARCH METHODS

In this research, the author uses the Library Research Method, namely research that is identical to studying books. Library research while utilizing library resources to obtain research data. Strictly speaking, library research limits activities to library collection materials only without requiring field research.

This research concerns Kuntowijoyo's thoughts about prophetic and its implementation in the Islamic Religious Education curriculum, so the main literature in this research is Kuntowijoyo's view about prophetic. Meanwhile, secondary literature is books about prophetics and the Islamic Religious Education curriculum.

Primary data sources are information that directly has authority and responsibility for data collection or storage. This kind of data source can also be called a hand-to-hand data or information source.⁶

The primary data source that the researcher used was a book entitled:

1. Kuntowijoyo. *Dinamika Sejarah Umat Islam Indonesia*. Yogyakarta: IRCiSoD, 2017;
2. Kuntowijoyo. *Islam sebagai Ilmu: Epistemologi, Metodologi, dan Etika*. Yogyakarta: Tiara Wacana, 2006;
3. Kuntowijoyo. *Muslim Tanpa Masjid*. Bandung: Mizan, 2001;
4. Kuntowijoyo. *Paradigma Islam Interpretasi Untuk Aksi*. Bandung: Mizan, 1998;
5. Kuntowijoyo. *Maklumat Sastra Profetik dalam Horison*. Mei 2005.

In this case, the author took data from books that discuss the values of prophetic education along with various possible derivation of their definitions. In addition, data regarding the PAI curriculum is included in secondary data.

This research is library research, so the data that researchers will explore will be collected using the documentation method, namely searching and extracting data from reading materials related to the problem.

Collecting both primary and secondary data with literature studies by reading, understanding, identifying, analyzing, then comparing one data source with another contained in the data source. Once collected, they are classified according to their respective characteristics into certain chapters to facilitate analysis.

The collected data is then analyzed systematically in accordance with scientific principles both textually (appearance of the original) and contextually (understanding of the data). This research will use a rationalistic approach. This approach was taken because this research is library research and the data collected is not only textual, but also an analysis of data that has been described using descriptive analysis methods.

⁶ Muhammad Ali, *Penelitian Kependidikan Prosedur dan Strategi*, (Bandung: Angkasa, 2018), h. 34.

This method includes writing, interpreting and classifying chapters and sub-chapters. Meanwhile, to support this analysis, generalizations are drawn that have general characteristics. Then, in a deductive mindset, it is based on general knowledge or circumstances because it wants to judge a specific event.⁷

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Kuntowijoyo is a complete thinker, he holds many identities. Apart from being a professor, he is also a historian, humanist, writer, writer-columnist, Muslim intellectual, activist and also a preacher, and from his works he has made many contributions to education. Social transformation is Kuntowijoyo's idea with the creation of the concept of prophetic social science, a new paradigm for Muslims entering the scientific period. The concept of prophetic values from Kuntowijoyo's perspective consists of humanization, liberation and transcendence which is a derivation from the verse of Ali Imran's letter verse 110 verse 110,

كُنْتُمْ خَيْرَ أُمَّةٍ أُخْرِجَتْ لِلنَّاسِ تَأْمُرُونَ بِالْمَعْرُوفِ وَتَنْهَوْنَ عَنِ الْمُنْكَرِ وَتُؤْمِنُونَ بِاللَّهِ
وَلَوْ ءَامَنَ أَهْلُ الْكِتَابِ لَكَانَ خَيْرًا لَهُمْ مِّنْهُمْ الْمُؤْمِنُونَ وَأَكْثَرُهُمُ الْفَاسِقُونَ

You are the best people who were born for humans, enjoining what is right, and forbidding what is evil, and believe in Allah. If the people of the book had believed, it would have been better for them, for among them there were those who believed, and most of them were wicked people. (Q.S. Al Imran; 110).⁸

Kuntowijoyo stated that there are three elements in prophetic social science which in the context of the Koran in the letter include amar ma'ruf (humanization), nahi munkar (liberation), Tu'minuna Bilah (transcendence). Thus, prophetic education can also be interpreted as education that is based on the process of strengthening students so that they have a life character with a strong and stable dimension of transcendence to be able to realize an ideal life which is integrated with the values of humanism and liberation at the same time.⁹

This verse explains that the Prophet is an ideal human being or servant of Allah physically and spiritually who has integrated with Allah and His Angels, was given the holy book and wisdom and at the same time he was able to implement it in life and communicate it effectively to fellow humans.

Referring to the explanation above, it is known that there are four points implied in Al Imran verse 110, including (1) the concept of the best people, (2) historical activism, (3) the importance of awareness and (4) prophetic ethics. First, the concept of the best people (The Chosen People), Muslims as the best people with the condition of doing the three things as

⁷ Lexy J. Moleong, *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif* (Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya, 2015), h. 103-104.

⁸ Departemen RI, *Alquran Tajwid dan Terjemah*, h. 90.

⁹ *Ibid.* h. 104-105.

mentioned in the verse of the Koran. Muslims do not automatically become The Chosen People, because Muslims in the concept of The Chosen People have a challenge to work harder towards historical activism by competing in goodness.

Second, activism or praxis of historical movements. Working hard by competing in goodness among humanity (ukhrijat Linnas) means that the ideal for Islam is the involvement of the people in history. Not marrying, isolating oneself, and clerics are not permitted. Likewise, mystical activities are not permitted. It is not Islam's wish, because Islam is a religion of 'charity.

Third, the importance of awareness. Prophetic values must always be the basis of value rationality for every movement's practice and build the awareness of the people, especially Muslims.

Fourth, prophetic ethics, this verse contains ethics that apply both among the general public and for anyone, whether individuals (students, intellectuals, activists, etc.) or organizations (student movements, universities, mass organizations and social organizations), or collectivities (jama'ah, congregation, group/community). This last point is a logical consequence of the three awarenesses that have been built previously

Moh. Shofan in Miftahullah states that prophetic education is an educational paradigm that seeks to synthesize between an education system that concentrates on moral and religious values and a modern education system that develops human values.¹⁰

The prophetic education paradigm can also be interpreted as a collection of theories and practices that not only explain, change social phenomena and things that are only for the sake of change in modernity, but more than that direct change based on prophetic ethical ideals. In prophetic culture there are three pillars including: transcendence, liberation, and humanization. These three pillars must become the theme of Islamic education. Every Islamic education must include an element of transcendence, because without transcendence it will not be Islamic education. Islam is a human bond with Allah as well as a bond with fellow creatures so that it contrasts with the concept of humanization which must be combined with the concept

transcendence, liberation plus transcendence. Transcendence alone is often considered sufficient, even though it is not enough, especially in the reality that Islamic education is dry of humanization and poor in liberation.

The origins of Kuntowijoyo's prophetic social science thinking drew conclusions from the writings of Muhammad Iqbal and Roger Jaraudy. In his book *Rebuilding Religious Thoughts in Islam*, Iqbal reiterates the words of a Sufi that the Prophet Muhammad had reached the highest place which was the dream of mystics, but he returned to the world to fulfill his apostolic duties. This extraordinary religious experience could not tempt the Prophet to stop. However, it is a psychological force to change humanity. In other words, this religious experience actually becomes the basis for order in history, a historical activism.¹¹

Humanization emphasizes humans as conscious creatures. He is in and with the world. The implication is that he must live alone with other humans and be able to face the realities of his life. Humanization is what will bring people to a humane change in reality. Thus, the human

¹⁰ Miftahulloh, *Pendidikan Profetik Perspektif Moh. Roqib dan Implikasinya dan Rekonstruksi Pendidikan Islam Integratif*, (Purwokerto: IAIN Purwokerto, 2017), h.40.

¹¹Kuntowijoyo, *Muslim Tanpa Masjid*, (Bandung: mizan, 2001). h. 363-364

image (the basic value of being truly human) is the optimal functioning of basic human potential so that they are able to carry out life activities.

Humanism in education is an educational process that pays more attention to human potential as social and religious creatures as well as individuals who are given the opportunity by God to optimize all their potential. Humanism is interpreted as an individual's strength or potential to measure and reach the divine level and social problems so that in this case the aim of Islamic education at the humanistic level is to civilize humans or humanize humans.

Thus, humanization as a derivation of amar ma'ruf contains the meaning of humanizing in accordance with the aim of Islamic education, namely to form pious people or human beings, and the way to optimize this is none other than through educational stimulation. Thus, curriculum development must be able to direct and convey the educational process as to what the goals and aspirations of humans or citizens are being created.

Islam is a liberating religion. Along with the vision of the Prophet Muhammad SAW. is to liberate its people from ignorance towards enlightenment, so Islamic education is expected to be able to process liberating humans. According to Kuntowijoyo, liberation is an effort to free people from the materialistic knowledge system of structural dominance, for example from class.¹²

Likewise, with Islamic education, freedom is an absolute requirement for developing the potential of students. Islamic education must carry out the mission of freeing humans from the shackles of tradition which bring numbness and decline. Islamic education must create and shape the birth of a new society and new processes.¹³

Kuntowijoyo's perspective of liberation takes the spirit of liberation theology, which has four main targets, namely liberation in the knowledge system, social system, economic system and political system which shackles humans so that they cannot actualize themselves as free and noble creatures.

Thus, liberation as a derivation of nahi munkar contains the meaning of liberation from all forms of cultural and structural determinism and liberation from centralization towards decentralization. So that the liberation of Islamic education is an effort to liberate people who are creative and competent in accordance with their nature, on this basis, curriculum development should emphasize liberation. The PAI curriculum must be able to create human individuals who have the dimension of liberation from all forms of oppression, orientation towards materialism and hedonism, or confinement to global capitalism. Becoming a human being who is able to position himself as a player of change and can control it.

Transcendence in Latin is *transcendere* which means rising above. In English it is to transcend which means to penetrate, pass through, go beyond. According to the term it means a journey above or beyond. What Kuntowijoyo means is transcendence in theological terms. Namely, it means divinity.¹⁴

Which is a dimension of human faith that is used as a frame for the values of humanization and liberation. Because Islamic teachings as a universal and internal guide to life are impossible to understand in detail and in detail, considering the complexity of problems and non-linear changes over time. Faith in Allah is the frame of the teachings of amar ma'ruf

¹² Kuntowijoyo, *Islam Sebagai Ilmu: Epistemologi, Metodologi, dan Etika*, h. 103.

¹³ Mastuhu, *Memberdayakan Sistem Pendidikan Islam*, (Jakarta: Logos Wacana Ilmu, 2014), h. 49.

¹⁴ Kuntowijoyo, *Islam Sebagai Ilmu: Epistemologi, Metodologi, dan Etika*, h. 98.

nahi munkar. The words amar ma'ruf nahi munkar consist of several elements of the body such as the heart, speech, hands, while faith also contains the same elements, namely saying it verbally, justifying it with the heart and doing it with deeds.

This can be understood if the realization of amar ma'ruf nahi munkar takes the form of personal and social actions, which emphasize actions. Meanwhile, faith is a form of justification of divine reality and is manifested in actions (good deeds). Meanwhile, with regard to Islamic worldly mu'amalah, it must provide guidance in the form of transformative values that human competence requires. These transcendent values are used as the basic teachings of Islam, including: Faith in Allah, Faith in the Angels of Allah, Faith in the Books of Allah, Faith in the Prophets and Messengers of Allah, Faith in the Last Day and Faith in Qada and Qadr Allah.¹⁵

Of the three basic values, the transformation of Islamic education has very fundamental implications in order to guide humanistic survival. humanization as a derivation from amar ma'ruf contains the meaning of human humanity as a process of change, liberation which is taken from nahi munkar contains the meaning of liberation from all forms of cultural and structural determinism. Meanwhile, transcendence is a dimension of human faith that places change within the framework of humanity and divinity (humanism-theocentrism). So the transformational values of Islamic education are a form of the process of forming a pious human being or a virtuous human being. Considering the importance of transcendence.

Likewise, in developing the PAI curriculum, it must emphasize the existence of transcendence content as the aim of Islamic religious education, namely to increase students' faith, understanding, appreciation and practice of Islamic religious teachings so that Muslim human beings are formed who believe in and are devoted to Allah SWT and have noble morals. in personal, social, national and state life, as explained in the previous chapter. Islam provides freedom in interpreting opinions, ideas to be contextualized and changed according to changing times. Which remains within the framework of humanity and divinity.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the discussion of the research results, the following conclusions can be given: Kuntowijoyo's prophetic values consist of three pillars, namely: humanization, liberation and transcendence which are derived from the Koran, Ali Imran verse 110. The concept of humanization is humanizing humans, eliminating material things, dependency, violence and hatred from humans. The liberation that Kuntowijoyo means in prophetic social science is in a scientific context and not in an ideological context; namely science based on transcendental noble values. In such a way, these liberative values must be understood or placed in social science which has a prophetic responsibility to liberate humans from the cruelty of poverty, the oppression of abundance, the domination of oppressive structures and the hegemony of false consciousness. Meanwhile, transcendence is the most important element of prophetic ethics which is also the basis of the other two elements; humanization and liberation. Transcendence gives direction to where and for what purpose humanization and liberation are carried out.

The implications of pfophetic values for the development of the PAI curriculum are: In developing the PAI curriculum in the future, apart from maintaining its characteristics which prioritize efforts to internalize the values of Islamic teachings, whether in the form of 'aqidah,

¹⁵ Muhammad Daud Ali, *Pendidikan Agama Islam*, (Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo, 2018), h. 201.

shari'ah or morals, it can also increase the portion of aspects of social change as the demands of the times. This effort is intended to increase the portion of efforts to instill human and social values. The content of divine values and human values must have a balanced portion. In developing the PAI curriculum in schools, apart from being able to create students who have strong faith and piety in facing global developments and world trends, they also have a high sense of social concern for injustice in their society and are able to actively participate in the development of society towards the desired progress.

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STRATEGI DALAM MENGHAFAL AL-QUR'AN DI MADRASAH TSANAWIYAH YAPI SIPARE-PARE

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Abstract

This research is a type of qualitative research using an inductive reasoning research model which aims to find out what strategies teachers use in memorizing the Al-Qur'an students at MTs Yapi Sipare-pare. The research method used in this study is a descriptive qualitative research method to analyze data in the form of sentences or words. Data collection techniques were carried out through observation, in-depth interviews, and documentation. Data were analyzed by data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and data verification. Checking the validity of the data is done by testing the credibility, transferability testing, penguin dependability, and confirmability testing.

The results showed that: the strategy carried out by the Tahfidz Teacher at MTs Yapi Sipare-pare in improving students' ability to memorize the Koran, consisted of several actions, namely: 1), giving motivation to students, 2), giving assignments and punishments to students, and 3), guiding students to remain muraja'ah. The obstacles faced by the Tahfidz teacher at MTs Yapi Sipare-pare in an effort to improve students' ability to memorize the Koran, namely as follows: 1), there are students who have not been able to read the Koran properly, 2), the health of the teacher which can interfere with concentration in teaching, 3), there is a feeling of laziness from students when memorizing the Koran, and 4) there is a different intelligence from the students.

The solution to this obstacle can be overcome by the teacher by giving tahsin guidance which is carried out periodically. In addition to the presence of several students who have not been able to read the Koran properly, there are also students who are lazy to memorize. This situation does not occur every day, but when students feel lazy, it will be difficult for students to memorize, even for teachers to guide student memorization. The solution that teachers can do to prevent students from feeling lazy is to always provide motivation in the form of advice and continuous memorization targets so that student memorization is always measurable. In addition to these obstacles there are also obstacles that in practice are not in accordance with the theory presented by the author.

Keywords: *Teacher Strategy, Memorizing the Koran*

PENDAHULUAN

Al-Qur'an merupakan sumber utama dan pedoman hidup bagi umat islam. Al-Qur'an bukan hanya sekedar berisikan petunjuk tentang hubungan antara manusia dengan Tuhan, tetapi juga mengatur hubungan manusia dengan sesamanya (hablum minallah wa hablum minan nas), serta manusia dengan alam sekitarnya. Untuk memahami ajaran Islam secara sempurna (kaffah), diperlukan pemahaman terhadap kandungan Al-Qur'an dan mengamalkannya dalam kehidupan sehari-hari secara sungguh-sungguh dan konsisten.

Pengetahuan yang terdapat dalam Al-Qur'an dikatakan begitu luas dan mendalam. Al-Qur'an berisikan tentang ilmu dunia dan akhirat, juga tentang kisah orang-orang terdahulu dan yang akan datang. Ia juga berisi tentang berbagai hakikat ilmiah, alam semesta, ilmu kedokteran, serta perundang-undangan (Al-Khalil, 2011).

Al-Qur'an bukanlah kitab biasa seperti pada umumnya. Di dalam penggunaannya Al-Qur'an adalah sebuah kitab yang teratur dari segi tata cara membacanya, bagian mana yang harus dipendekkan, dipanjangkan, dipertebal, atau diperhalus ucapannya, dimana tempat yang dilarang atau yang boleh untuk berhenti, atau dimana harus memulai dan berhenti membacanya, bahkan diatur lagu dan iramanya, sampai pada etika membacanya itu semua terdapat di dalam Al-Qur'an (Sa'dulloh, 2008).

Al-Qur'an sebagai petunjuk dan pedoman hidup bagi umat Islam. Untuk mencapai kebahagiaan didunia dan akhirat Al-Qur'an juga berfungsi untuk membimbing manusia ke jalan yang lurus. Untuk mencapai tujuan tersebut maka dibutuhkan ilmu untuk mengkaji dan mempelajari isi dan kandungan yang ada didalam Al-Qur'an tersebut. Ilmu yang dibutuhkan untuk mengkaji isi kandungan Alquran tersebut antara lain: ilmu Nahwu, Sorof, Tajwid, Tafsir, balaghoh, dan keilmuan lainnya (Al Qattan, 2009). Al-Qur'an secara bahasa berasal dari kata *qara'a* yang berarti (membaca). Al-Qur'an merupakan kalamullah dan juga kitab suci bagi umat islam yang diturunkan kepada Rasul-Nya penutup para Nabi yakni Nabi Muhammad Saw, yang dimulai dari surat al-Fatihah dan diakhiri dengan surat an-Nas (Al-utsaimin, 2008).

Didalam Islam, istilah belajar diambil dari kata Iqra' yang mempunyai arti perintah untuk membaca. Dengan membaca, seseorang akan memperoleh banyak pengetahuan. Sehingga belajar dalam Islam sangat diprioritaskan. Kemampuan membaca merupakan hal yang terpenting bagi kehidupan manusia, terutama di era globalisasi saat sekarang ini. Setiap orang butuh untuk bisa membaca guna memperoleh informasi. Semua umat muslim diharuskan untuk bisa membaca, terutama dalam membaca Al-Qur'an bagi umat Islam. Pembelajaran Al-Qur'an merupakan suatu kewajiban yang harus dilaksanakan dan ditumbuh kembangkan bagi setiap individu muslim, karena terkait langsung dengan ibadah ritual seperti shalat, haji dan do'a. inilah yang menjadi argumentasi mendasar ditetapkannya keterampilan membaca sebagai prioritas pertama dan utama dalam pendidikan Islam. Begitu pentingnya kemampuan dasar membaca Al-Qur'an, ditegaskan bahwa umat Islam agar selalu berupaya meningkatkan kemampuan membaca Al-Qur'an dalam rangka peningkatan dan penghayatan serta pengalaman Al-Qur'an dalam kehidupan sehari-hari (Supardi, 2004).

Al-Qur'an merupakan satu-satunya kitab yang memiliki arahan untuk di hafal. Semua yang ada didalam Al-Qur'an berasal dari Allah SWT. Al-Qur'an mempunyai bahasa yang berbeda dengan kitab lainnya dan tidak akan pernah berubah. Al-Qur'an juga merupakan syair yang indah yang tidak bisa dikalahkan oleh syair- syair buatan manusia. AlQur'an benar benar dijaga oleh Allah SWT ia tidak akan berkurang ataupun berubah, tidak bercampur dengan yang batil, dan tidak mengalami perubahan sedikitpun walaupun zaman terus berubah (Harus, 2021).

Allah akan selalu menjaga kemurnian Al-Qur'an baik dalam setiap hurufnya, ayatnya maupun kalimatnya serta segala isi yang terkandung didalamnya. Maka dari itu, umat Islam diwajibkan untuk menjaga kemurnian dan keasliannya. Menghafal Al-Qur'an tidaklah mudah, hanyalah orang-orang terpilih yang dapat menghafalnya. Makhori jul huruf yang diucapkan juga harus tepat jelas dan benar, karena jika ada kesalahan sedikit saja dalam pengucapan akan berdampak fatal yaitu akan menjadi sebuah dosa. Sampai sekarang umat islam masih terus menghafal Al-Qur'an sebagai bentuk usaha umat dalam menjaga keaslian Al-Qur'an yang tidak akan pernah berubah sampai datangnya hari kiamat (Zen, 1984).

Banyak keutamaan bagi yang mempelajari Al-Qur'an, dimulai dari membaca, menghafal, memahami serta mengamalkannya. Didalam Al-Qur'an dan Hadist Allah dan Rasul-Nya telah menyampaikan keutamaan-keutamaan tersebut. Keutamaan mempelajari Al-Qur'an salah satunya telah dituliskan oleh Muhammad Ahmad Abdullah, yaitu "Sesungguhnya orang-orang yang selalu membaca kitab Allah dan mendirikan shalat dan menginfakkan sebagian rizki yang kami anugerahkan kepadanya dengan diam-diam dan terang-terangan, mereka itu mengharapkan perdagangan yang tidak akan rugi" (Qs. Al-Faṭir (35): 29-30). (Abdullah, 2009).

Orang yang memiliki minat dalam menghafal Al-Qur'an pada zaman sekarang ini sangatlah sedikit, Hal ini dikarenakan kurangnya pengetahuan dan kemauan dalam menghafal Al-Qur'an. Untuk menarik minat mereka dalam menghafal Al-Qur'an, maka sangat diperlukan adanya metode-metode khusus atau metode pembelajaran yang dapat memudahkan kita dalam menghafalnya.

Tahfidzul Qur'an ini dipandang sebagai salah satu upaya pembelajaran yang bisa dilakukan dalam pendidikan Al-Qur'an. Istilah tahfidzul Qur'an dapat diartikan sebagai proses mempelajari Al-Qur'an dengan cara menghafalnya agar selalu ingat dan dapat diucapkan diluar kepala tanpa melihat mushaf (Shihab, 1994).

Dalam menghafal Al-Qur'an, proses yang dijalani tidaklah mudah dan bahkan memakan waktu yang cukup lama bergantung pada kekuatan memori penghafal Al-Qur'an. Dalam hal ini, dikatakan tidak mudah karena yang dihafalkan dari sisi kuantitas yang tidak sedikit dan setidaknya terdiri dari 114 surat, 6.236 ayat, 77.439 kata, dan 323.015 huruf. Oleh karena itu, kekuatan memori yang ditunjang oleh personality merupakan hal yang sangat urgen dalam proses ini. Di samping itu, setelah penghafal Al-Qur'an menghafalnya, maka yang bersangkutan dihadapkan pada kewajiban dalam menjaga hafalannya (Chairani & M.A. Subandi, 2011).

Al-Qur'an bukan hanya berisi tentang hubungan manusia dengan Tuhan, melainkan mengatur hubungan manusia dengan sesamanya, serta manusia denganalam sekitarnya. Untuk memahami ajaran Islam secara sempurna, diperlukan untuk memahami isi kandungan Al-Qur'an serta mengamalkannya dalam kehidupan sehari-hari (Batubara, 2019).

Keberhasilan pendidikan tidak luput dari proses pembelajaran. Di antaranya adalah strategi pembelajaran yang di dalamnya terdapat metode dan teknik. Pemilihan strategi pembelajaran yang sesuai materi, keadaan dan kemampuan siswa akan membuat proses pembelajaran lebih optimal. Strategi pembelajaran merupakan komponen yang penting dalam setiap kegiatan pembelajaran. Oleh karena itu, dengan penggunaan strategi yang tepat dalam pembelajaran, akan tercapai tujuan secara maksimal.

Maka dari itu strategi yang digunakan guru tahfidz untuk mempermudah siswa dalam menghafal Al-Qur'an yaitu dengan cara penerapan metode-metode hafalan. Dengan adanya metode hafalan tersebut akan mempermudah dan sangat membantu bagi siswa yang mengalami kesulitan dalam menghafal Al-Qur'an. Dan penerapan metode-metode ini sebelumnya telah di terapkan oleh guru Tahfidzul Qur'an dalam proses pembelajaran guna untuk meningkatkan hafalan dan mencapai tujuan pembelajaran yang diharapkan sekaligus mempermudah siswa dalam menghafal hafalan Al-Qur'an.

Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs) Yapi Sipare-pare adalah sekolah yang menerapkan sistem pembelajaran berbasis Islami. Sekolah ini mengadakan mata pelajaran khusus Tahfidzul Qur'an pada setiap hari rabu dan sabtu. Guru Tahfidzul Qur'an di Madrasah Tsanawiyah ini juga selaku guru pembimbing ekstrakurikuler Tahfidz Qur'an di MTs tersebut. Guru Tahfidzul

Qur'an di MTs ini memberikan pelajaran Tahfidzul Qur'an dengan menggunakan metode khusus untuk memudahkan siswanya dalam menghafal Al-Qur'an.

Berdasarkan observasi penulis, guru Tahfidzul Qur'an di MTs Yapi Sipare-pare ini yang juga selaku guru pembimbing ekstrakurikuler Tahfidz al-Qur'an telah menerapkan strategi untuk mempermudah siswa dalam menghafal Al-Qur'an. Dan strategi yang telah di terapkan tersebut mengarah pada penggunaan metode hafalan Al-Qur'an dan sudah menggunakan beberapa metode dalam pembelajaran Tahfidz Al-Qur'an. Macam-macam metode yang di gunakan sudah bervariasi seperti metode Jama'i, metode Sima'i, metode Talaqqi, dan metode Juz'i.

Oleh karena itu, untuk membantu memudahkan siswa dalam menghafal Al-Qur'an, maka guru tahfidz Qur'an di MTs Yapi Sipare-pare ini telah menerapkan beberapa strategi pembelajaran, dimana strategi yang digunakan ialah berupa metode-metode hafalan dan strategi lainnya ialah bertujuan untuk membantu mempermudah siswa dalam menghafal Al-Qur'an. Berdasarkan latar belakang diatas. Maka penulis tertarik untuk melakukan penelitian dengan judul: "Strategi dalam Menghafal Al-Qur'an di Madrasah Tsanawiyah Yapi Sipare-pare".

METODE PENELITIAN

Penelitian ini termasuk dalam jenis penelitian lapangan yang berkaitan dengan penelitian kualitatif. Penelitian ini dilakukan untuk mendapatkan informasi dan data dengan terjun langsung ke lapangan agar dapat berinteraksi secara langsung dengan narasumber. Jenis penelitian ini menggunakan model penelitian penalaran induktif.

Penalaran induktif adalah metode yang digunakan dalam berpikir dengan bertumpu menjelaskan permasalahan yang bersifat khusus dalam menentukan kesimpulan yang bersifat umum. Dan sangat percaya akan banyaknya perspektif yang nantinya akan di ungkapkan. Penelitian ini berfokus pada persepsi dari partisipan dibawah studi yang didapatkan dengan cara mendengar secara langsung. Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk memberikan pemahaman terhadap metode menghafal Al-Qur'an. (Zulfa, 2019).

Dengan demikian dapat dikatakan bahwa penelitian deskriptif kualitatif dengan pendekatan induktif merupakan metode yang menggambarkan permasalahan atau kasus yang dikemukakan berdasarkan fakta yang ada dengan berpijak pada fakta yang bersifat khusus kemudian diteliti untuk dipecahkan permasalahannya dan ditarik kesimpulan secara umum. Oleh karena itu, peneliti akan menggambarkan pemahaman terhadap metode menghafal Al-Qur'an secara keseluruhan melalui pengamatan, dan wawancara.

HASIL DAN PEMBAHASAN

Meningkatkan hafalan Al-Qur'an siswa di MTs Yapi Sipare-pare, ada beberapa strategi yang digunakan oleh guru tahfidz di MTs Yapi Sipare-pare yakni memberikan motivasi kepada para siswa, memberi *punishment* dan *reward* kepada siswa, membimbing para siswa untuk tetap *muraja'ah*. Selain itu salah satu strategi yang digunakan dala meningkatkan hafalan Al-Qur'an siswa yaitu menggunakan metode yang bervariasi.

Dalam menjalankan strategi tersebut guru tahfidz di MTs Yapi Sipare-pare tentunya adanya faktor hambatan, adapun faktor hambatan tersebut yakni adanya siswa yang belum mampu membaca Alquran dengan baik, 2), kesehatan guru yang dapat mengganggu konsentrasi dalam mengajar, 3), adanya rasa malas dari diri siswa ketika menghafal Alquran, dan 4) adanya kecerdasan yang berbeda dari para siswa.

Evaluasi adalah pengukuran atau perbaikan dalam suatu kegiatan yang dilaksanakan. Pada proses ini, seorang guru tahfidz akan melakukan perbaikan strategi yang telah dilaksanakan. Dalam hal ini ada beberapa bentuk evaluasi yang dilakukan untuk oleh pihak MTs Yapi Sipare-pare yakni perlu adanya dukungan dan Kerjasama dengan semua pihak guru, memberikan motivasi kepada siswa agar bersungguh-sungguh dalam mengikuti pembelajaran tahfidz Al-Qur'an. Serta perlu adanya tes bagi siswa yang mendaftar di MTs Yapi Sipare-pare dengan tujuan untuk mengetahui kemampuan awal setiap siswa.

Secara umum strategi mempunyai pengertian suatu garis-garis besar haluan untuk bertindak dalam usaha mencapai sasaran yang telah ditentukan. Dihubungkan dengan tahfidz Al-Qur'an strategi bisa diartikan sebagai pola-pola umum kegiatan menghafal Al-Qur'an dalam perwujudan untuk mencapai tujuan yang telah digariskan (Djamarah, Bahri, & Zain, 2013).

Menghafal Al-Qur'an merupakan salah satu kegiatan belajar. Di dalam menghafal Al-Qur'an ada beberapa model atau metode yang mungkin bisa dikembangkan dalam rangka mencari alternatif terbaik untuk menghafal Al-Qur'an dan bisa memberikan bantuan kepada para penghafal dalam mengurangi kepayahan dalam menghafal Al-Qur'an.

Dalam Al-Qur'an kata *Al-Hifzhu* mempunyai arti yang bermacam-macam tergantung susunan kalimatnya, antara lain: selalu menjaga dan mengerjakan shalat pada waktunya, menjaga, memelihara, dan yang diangkat. *Al-Hifzhu* atau Tahfizh ialah menghafal materi baru yang belum pernah dihafal, hafal merupakan kata kerja yang berarti telah masuk dalam ingatan (tentang pelajaran), dapat mengingat sesuatu dengan mudah dan mengucapkannya di luar kepala. Menghafal diartikan pula sebagai aktifitas menanamkan materi verbal di dalam ingatan, sesuai dengan materi asli (Abdu Rabb Nawbuddin, 1992).

Kemampuan seorang siswa dalam menghafal dan memahami hafalannya berbeda-beda ada yang berani maju kedepan kelas dan ada juga merasa takut di karenakan teman-temannya mentertawakan saat maju di depan kelas, maka dari itu diperlukannya strategi guru dalam mempermudah siswa untuk menghafal.

Hasil pengujian ini sejalan dengan beberapa penelitian terdahulu, di antaranya adalah hasil penelitian Eka Dwi Ermawati yang menyatakan bahwa pelaksanaan pembelajaran tahfidz Al-Qur'an di Madrasah Ibtidaiyah Miftahul Ulum Plosorejo Kademangan Blitar menerapkan beberapa strategi, yaitu: Menggunakan satu jenis mushaf Al-Qur'an, tidak beralih pada ayat berikutnya sebelum ayat yang sedang dihafal benar-benar hafal, menghafal urutan-urutan ayat yang dihafalkannya dalam satu kesatuan jumlah setelah benar-benar hafal ayatnya, pengulangan ganda, dan disetorkan pada seorang pengampu.

Selain itu hasil penelitian Anggraini Widya Damayanti yang menyatakan bahwa dalam faktor hambatan menghafal masih ditemukannya siswa yang kurang memanfaatkan waktu belajar dengan semaksimal mungkin, siswa yang bermain-main saat jam hafalan berlangsung serta kurangnya waktu yang diberikan guru sehingga masih ada siswa yang tidak sempat untuk menyetorkan hafalannya dengan tepat waktu

SIMPULAN DAN SARAN

Berdasarkan hasil penelitian dan pembahasan yang telah dilaksanakan tentang Strategi dalam Menghafal Al-Qur'an di Madrasah Tsanawiyah Yapi Sipare-pare, dapat disimpulkan sebagai berikut:

1. Strategi yang dilakukan Guru Tahfidz di Madrasah Tsanawiyah Yapi Sipare-pare dalam meningkatkan kemampuan menghafal Alquran siswa, terdiri dari beberapa tindakan, yaitu:1), memberikan motivasi kepada para siswa, 2), memberi tugas dan hukuman kepada para siswa, dan 3), membimbing para siswa untuk tetap *muraja'ah*.
2. Hambatan-hambatan yang dihadapi Guru Tahfidz di Madrasah Tsanawiyah Yapi Sipare-pare dalam upaya meningkatkan kemampuan menghafal Alquran siswa, yaitu sebagai berikut:1), adanya siswa yang belum mampu membaca Alquran dengan baik, 2), kesehatan guru yang dapat mengganggu konsentrasi dalam mengajar, 3), adanya rasa malas dari diri siswa ketika menghafal Alquran, dan 4) adanya kecerdasan yang berbeda dari para siswa
3. Dalam hal ini ada beberapa bentuk evaluasi yang dilakukan untuk oleh pihak MTs Yapi Sipare-pare yakni perlu adanya dukungan dan Kerjasama dengan semua pihak guru, memberikan motivasi kepada siswa agar bersungguh-sungguh dalam mengikuti pembelajaran tahfidz Al-Qur'an. Serta perlu adanya tes bagi siswa yang mendaftar di MTs Yapi Sipare-pare dengan tujuan untuk mengetahui kemampuan awal setiap siswa.

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EFFECT OF USING THE TIK TOK APPLICATION TO WARDS SOCIAL INTERACTION OF CLASS STUDENTS XI AT MAS AL-WASHLIYAH PAKAM VILLAGE MEDANG DERAS DISTRICT COAL DISTRICT

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Abstract

This study uses a quantitative approach. Where the symptoms will be measured using numbers. This type of research is ex post facto. The data collection technique used is a questionnaire (questionnaire), observation and documentation. The subjects in this study were students of class XI.

The results of the research in this thesis, there is the influence of the use of the tik tok application on the social interaction of class XI students. This is evidenced from the table of output coefficients obtained tcount value of 3.690. With= 5%, dk= 59-2=57, the ttable value is 2,000. From these numbers, it can be seen that tcount (3,690) > ttable (2,000), as well as with a significance value of 0.00 < 0.05, it can be concluded that if the hypothesis is accepted, it means that there is an effect of using the tik tok application on the social interactions of class XI MAS students. AL-WASHLIYAH Pakam Village, Medang Deras Subdistrict, Batu Bara Regency for the 2022/2023 Academic Year.

Keywords: *Influence, Use of Tik Tok Applications, Student Social Interaction*

INTRODUCTION

Digital technology currently seems to be one of the main things that is very important for human life. In this era, there are many things that can be done with technology, one example is to create and communicate. With technology, there is no need to go to your destination because it can be accessed via the internet. One of them is that cellphones have become part of everyday human life and breathing.

Social media applications, especially the Tik Tok application, allow us to connect with millions of people around the world. Interpersonal communication is now gradually changing, becoming interaction between people and mobile phones. Because now interacting is very easy using a cellphone. Compared to interactions in the social environment around us, many people are more comfortable with cell phones. People prefer to make friends through Internet social networks and forget about others. Even if we are in the same room with other people, we do not participate in the conversation because they are busy with their respective Cell Phones.

They feel very cool about their own world. When the cell phone becomes a closer friend than the social environment, friends on social networks seem closer and more real than the neighbors around us.

Thus, the author took the title of this research, namely "The Effect of Using the Tik Tok Application on the Social Interaction of Class XI Students at MAS AL-WASHLIYAH Pakam Village, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency". The reason the author chose the title of this research is because the author is interested and wants to know more about the influence of

the Tik Tok application on students' social interactions because many students gather in one place but do not interact socially because they are engrossed in using their respective Tik Tok applications, considering the problems that arise. discussed in this thesis, which means interaction is very important for us

RESEARCH METHODS

In this research, the author uses quantitative data. Quantitative data is an analysis used on data in the form of numbers and is discussed using statistical tests. Quantitative analysis emphasizes testing theories through measuring research variables with numbers and analyzing data using statistical procedures. The research in this thesis uses quantitative research, while the approach used is a simple regression analysis approach. This type of approach aims to see whether three or more variables have an influence.

The research location is the place where the research will be carried out. The research location is expected to be able to provide the information needed by a researcher in the research being conducted. The place or location of this research is at MAS AL-WASHLIYAH Pakam Village, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency, North Sumatra Province.

To collect and compile the data required in this quantitative research are questionnaires, observation and documentation.

Based on the source, the data used in this research is Primary Data which is data obtained directly from data sources obtained from the results of questionnaires given to class XI MAS AL-WASHLIYAH students in Pakam Village and Secondary Data is data obtained through other sources. written sources in the form of documents and written reports. Secondary data sources in this research are documents that support this research.

Before carrying out further statistical tests, it is necessary to test research measuring instruments. In this research using the SPSS 25 program, the first test was to test the validity and reliability of the questionnaire which included the influence of using the Tik Tok application on the social interaction of class XI students at MAS AL-WASHLIYAH Pakam Village, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the output coefficients table above, the tcount value is 3,690. With $\alpha = 5\%$, $dk = 59-2 = 57$, the ttable value is 2,000. From these figures it can be seen that $tcount (3,690) > ttable (2,000)$, likewise with a significance value of $0.00 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that if the hypothesis is accepted, it means that there is an influence of student etiquette on the influence of using the Tik Tok application on students' social interactions. class XI Mas Al-Washliyah Pakam Village, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency, Academic Year 2022/2023.

Based on this, it can be seen that the majority of MAS Al-Washliyah students in Pakam Village, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency have cellphones and the Tik Tok application. They also often use the Tik Tok application when they want. Some of them even play the Tik Tok application all the time.

Based on the results of the regression test above, it can also be seen that the variable use of the Tik Tok application greatly influences students' social interactions by 35%. This can be seen from the Pearson correlation value which is a form of hypothesis testing based on statistics which can be described as follows:

- a. Uji Hipotesis Pengaruh Penggunaan Aplikasi Tik Tok terhadap Interaksi Sosial Siswa
 - 1) Hipotesis Terdapat pengaruh penggunaan aplikasi tik tok terhadap interaksi sosial Siswa kelas XIMAS AL-WASHLIYAH Desa Pakam Kecamatan Medang Deras Kabupaten Batu Bara Tahun Pelajaran 2022/2023.
 - 2) Kriteria Pengambilan Keputusan
- b. Terima H_a Jika $t_{hitung} < t_{tabel}$ atau $-t_{hitung} > -t_{tabel}$ atau nilai Sig. $> 0,05$
- c. Tolak H_a Jika $t_{hitung} \geq t_{tabel}$ atau $-t_{hitung} \leq -t_{tabel}$ atau Sig. $< 0,05$
 - 1) Prestasi Pengujian
 - 2) Dari tabel *output coefficients* diatas diperoleh nilai t_{hitung} sebesar 3.690. Dengan $\alpha = 5\%$, $dk = 59-2 = 57$ diperoleh nilai t_{tabel} sebesar 2,000. Dari angka tersebut dapat diketahui bahwa $t_{hitung} (3.690) > t_{tabel} (2,000)$, demikian pula dengan nilai signifikansinya sebesar $0,00 < 0,05$ maka dapat disimpulkan jika hipotesis diterima, artinya Terdapat pengaruh penggunaan aplikasi tik tok terhadap interaksi sosial siswa kelas XIMAS AL-WASHLIYAH Desa Pakam Kec. Medang Deras Kab. Batu Bara Tahun Pelajaran 2022/2023.

From the explanation above, it can be seen that the use of the Tik Tok application has an influence on students' social interactions. This is because every student has the Tik Tok application and always uses it, so many of them rarely interact socially with fellow students.

Based on the out put model summary table above, it can be seen that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.350 or 35%. This shows that the variable use of the Tik Tok application can explain the student social interaction variable by 35%. The remaining 65% (100% - 35%) is explained by other variables not included in this research such as interpersonal communication, school environment, social interaction. , peers and so on who were not careful in this research.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the research and analysis that the author has described in the previous chapters regarding the Influence of Using the Tik Tok Application on Student Social Interaction at MAS Al-Washliyah, Pakam Village, Medang Deras District, Batu Bara Regency. So the author will explain a little about the findings of this research. It can be concluded that the majority of class XI students have the Tik Tok application. And they are also users of the Tik Tok application. They always use the Tik Tok application.

From the output coefficients table above, the tcount value is 3,690. With $\alpha = 5\%$, $dk = 59-2 = 57$, the ttable value is 2,000. From these figures it can be seen that tcount (3,690) $>$ ttable (2,000), likewise with a significance value of $0.00 < 0.05$, it can be concluded that if the hypothesis is accepted, this means that there is an influence of the use of the Tik Tok application on the social interaction of class XIMAS AL students. -WASHLIYAH Pakam Village, District. Medang Deras District. Coal for Academic Year 2022/2023.

The interaction patterns of students change because they rarely communicate or interact socially with fellow students, as a result they are more engrossed in using the Tik Tok application. One of them even became anti-social. And that is bad for them. Even though they say that playing Tik Tok makes them happy, it's not always good for them.

The negative impact of the Tik Tok application, if misused, will result in sexual harassment, loss of shame, lack of interaction with people around you and wasting time. The positive impact of the Tik Tok application is to train its users' abilities in creating creative, interesting and entertaining content.

Based on studies in the field, the author intends to provide suggestions that will hopefully be useful for institutions and future researchers, namely as follows.

It is hoped that suggestions for students using the Tik Tok application will reduce the use or frequency of playing Tik Tok. Because their frequent use of Tik Tok can have a bad impact on them and make them anti-social towards their environment.

Teachers can monitor their students so that they can use their cellphones as well as possible and they can use the Tik Tok application appropriately.

For researchers who are interested in conducting research with the same title as this research, this thesis can be a reference for conducting further research more thoroughly and better than this research.

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THE ROLE OF ISLAMIC COMMUNITY FIGURES IN FOSTERING YOUTH RELIGIOUS ACTIVITIES AT THE AL-AMIN MOSQUE IN KUALA TANJUNG VILLAGE, SEI SUKA DISTRICT, BATU BARA REGENCY

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Abstract

Community leaders are people who have been trusted by the community because of their good abilities and background. In this case the role of community leaders is closely related to the problem of fostering the religious activities of mosque youth. Because it is used as a coach for religious activities in the community, so here the researcher wants to know what roles are played by community leaders, especially Islamic religious leaders in fostering the religious activities of mosque youth.

Adolescence is part of the phase in the process experienced by every human being. Adolescence is also a decisive period because at this time children experience many changes in their psychology and physique. The occurrence of psychological changes causes confusion among adolescents. The reason is because they experience emotional turmoil and mental pressure so that they easily deviate from the rules and social norms that apply in society.

Thus, Islamic religious leaders as leaders in society must be able to provide good examples and interactions to direct and provide guidance to adolescents. Social interaction is regulated based on goodness, justice and the common good, not just for a particular person or group. Especially youth in mosques, because the presence of Islamic youth groups in this mosque will greatly assist activities held by religious leaders, to unite youth with the environment.

Keywords: *Role, Islamic Religious Leaders, Fostering Youth Mosque Activities*

INTRODUCTION

A community figure is someone who has been trusted by the community because of his good abilities and background. In this case, the role of the community figure is very related to the issue of fostering the religious activities of mosque youth. Because it is used as a supervisor of religious activities in the community, here the researcher wants to know what roles are played by community figures, especially Islamic religious figures, in fostering the religious activities of mosque youth.

Islamic religious figures have a very important role in fostering activities in society in religious activities. The success of Islamic religious figures in developing mosque youth in religious activities is largely determined by the ability or style of religious figures in providing examples as role models, their interactions with appeals and suggestions in influencing community members or is also largely determined by the way religious figures use their authority as leaders. religion. Thus, the role of Islamic religious figures in the religious activities of Islamic youth at mosques has a very close relationship and cannot be separated.

Da'wah is a noble activity, it is an obligation for every community, with the aim of providing information about Islam and inviting other people to be willing to take actions that

reflect Islamic values. Da'wah must be able to condition it with targets that can be seen from various aspects, including social, economic, cultural and ideological conditions that one believes in, in fact the success of changing the da'wah is the visible change in targets (mad'u), especially in increasing religious experience.

In this era of globalization, it not only provides positive input, but also has many negative aspects, which have influenced our nation's lifestyle. The Indonesian nation, which still strongly adheres to eastern norms and culture, feels poisoned by the influx of culture from outside. Especially with the condition of teenagers who act as future successors of the nation who still need provisions for their future. Many of them have deviated from the norms of Islam as a universal religion that can always answer all future and future challenges.

Thus, Islamic religious figures as leaders in society must be able to provide good examples and interactions to direct and provide guidance to teenagers. Social interactions are regulated based on goodness, justice and mutual benefit, not just for a particular person or group.¹ Especially mosque teenagers, because the existence of this mosque Islamic youth group will really help activities held by religious leaders, to unite teenagers with the environment.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research was carried out in Kuala Tanjung Village, Sei Suka District, Batu Bara Regency. This is based on consideration of time and distance traveled as well as the completeness of the facilities and infrastructure in the village. Qualitative research is research that is intended to reveal symptoms in a holistic conceptual way through collecting data from natural settings using the author as the key instrument.²

The subject of this research is a community figure in Kuala Tanjung Village, Sei Suka District, Batu Bara Regency and Al-Amin Mosque Youth, while the object of this research is an effort to foster mosque youth activities.

The data sources in this research are community leaders, mosque youth, Kuala Tanjung village, Sei Suka District, Batu Bara Regency. Apart from that, the data sources can also be taken from interested parties in this research.

To collect and compile the data needed in this qualitative research, the author used several direct instruments, namely observation, interviews and documentation studies.

Reducing data means summarizing, selecting the main things, focusing on the important things, and looking for themes and patterns. In this way, the reduced data will provide a clearer picture, and make it easier for researchers to collect further data and search for it if necessary. Data reduction can be assisted with equipment, such as computers, notebooks, and so on.

Conclusions in qualitative research are new findings that have never existed before. Findings can be in the form of a description or picture of an object that was previously still dim or even dark, so that after research it becomes clear. This conclusion can be in the form of a causal or interactive relationship, as well as a hypothesis or theory .

Visits and direct involvement at locations in collecting required data and information. Member check and triangulation (assessing the validity of the data) which includes data

¹ Muhamad Qodir Ahmad, "Metodologi Pengajaran Agama Islam" Jakarta bineka cipta th 2008. H.12

² Kode Etik dan panduan penulisan Skripsi (Stai Tebing Tinggi Deli, 2022)

sources, data collection methods from one another. Discuss with friends, supervisors, or other people who are not involved in this research to get constructive input.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Religious figures are role models for the people around them in their daily lives, as mentors and role models for the people, providing guidance to the Muslim community so that they become human beings who believe and are devoted to Allah SWT, and have noble morals so that prosperity, prosperity and justice are realized in their lives. real life in society.

From the results of interviews with the two religious figures, researchers were able to analyze the role of religious figures in fostering the activities of Muslim youth at the mosque, namely: Inviting Islamic youth at the mosque to become active again in the religious activities that have been programmed. Providing an example and directing Islamic teenagers at the mosque to realize the importance of this organization being formed, namely to develop the minds of teenagers to improve themselves in religious knowledge, so that they become a generation that loves Islam and has good morals.³

The role of religious figures is very important in fostering religious activities, as for the efforts made by religious figures to promote the religious activities of Islamic youth at mosques through several methods such as their daily activities. Currently, not all Islamic youth at mosques around the Al-Amin prayer room are aware of the importance of Islamic youth mosque organizations, so this is one of the factors in the non-functioning of Islamic youth mosque organizations that have been formed.

Religious figures in Idalam hamlet provide guidance to Muslim youth at the mosque, namely by inviting Islamic youth from the mosque to become active again in the religious activities that have been programmed. Furthermore, one of the ways that religious leaders can develop Islamic youth in mosques is through daily activities, for example praying together in the mosque, sometimes once a week cleaning the mosque. This aims to make teenagers aware of how important it is to clean the mosque, as for the programmed religious activities. which used to run once a week but now doesn't run.

Based on the results of interviews with religious figures, he said that these two factors are: Factors that influence the role of religious figures in fostering the religious activities of Islamic youth at the Al Amin Mosque are as follows: Parents are the main and first educators. Mainly because their influence is very fundamental in the development of their child's personality. As a direct illustration of a family whose family members always get used to carrying out religious activities which will color habits both within the family and religious activities outside the environment. In relation to the role of religious figures in fostering the religious activities of Islamic youth in mosques, one of the factors is parents and religious figures.

One factor that greatly influences changes in a person's behavior is communication in interactions. To advance a common interest, such as religious activities, a figure or figure who has been given the mandate to carry it out must continuously remind and build good communication.

Based on the research results, it can be analyzed the role of religious figures in fostering the religious activities of mosque youth as mentors of religious activities for mosque Islamic

³ Irwansyah , Ketua Risma, *Wawancara*, 29 Juli 2022

youth through direct interviews with religious leaders and mosque Islamic youth. Following are the results of research findings related to the role of religious figures as follows:

The role of religious figures as supervisors of religious activities for mosque youth has not yet been realized optimally. There are things that have been done by the role of religious figures in Dusun I Kuala Tanjung Village, namely social service (baksos) and learning recitation but now these activities are no longer running. Now the role played by religious figures is only limited to daily actions, carrying out activities, for example praying in congregation at the mosque, doing good deeds and good deeds. Religious leaders need to approach Islamic teenagers in mosques, what activities do teenagers really like, because of the fun? This could later become an activity idea that could reactivate the religious activities of Islamic youth mosques (RISMA).

Religious figures are used as mentors and givers of direction in various religious activities in particular. To realize this, truly programmed and well-coordinated interaction, management, attention and guidance from religious figures is needed. So that the role of teenagers, especially mosque teenagers, can be held and can achieve what all members of the community aspire to, of course the main role played by mosque youth is related to Islamic teachings. The role of religious figures is very important, namely to provide encouragement, motivation and social interaction which must be well established, to make it happen.

Mosque youth religious activities (RISMA) cannot be said to be maximally active, due to inhibiting factors originating from the supervisors and Islamic youth of the mosque itself. There is a lack of good communication and interaction, so they cannot be united, for example gathering for discussions or deliberations to activate activities. RISMA's religion is back.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The role of religious figures in fostering the religious activities of Islamic youth in mosques is currently still not good, because their role in fostering the religious activities of Islamic youth in mosques has not been well realized. Because the role carried out is still only teaching positive things which are carried out directly in daily activities so far, the activity that has been carried out is teaching reading the Al-Qur'an with good and correct recitation.

The factors that influence the role of religious figures in fostering Islamic youth activities at mosques consist of supporting factors, namely: Family environment; The large number of mosque youth and adequate infrastructure, namely Al-Qur'an, tables, sound systems, etc., are in the prayer room to support the ongoing activities carried out in the implementation of Risma activities.

There are several inhibiting factors in implementing the role of religious figures in fostering religious activities, namely: Disharmony among Islamic youth members of the mosque; The lack of good interaction and communication between religious leaders and mosque Islamic youth, thus making mosque Islamic youth lazy in carrying out activities, not united and lacking commitment in the organization and also caused by social interactions.

In this regard, some of the suggestions recommended by the author are: For all the efforts that have been made by religious figures in fostering the religious activities of Islamic youth in mosques, it is hoped that they will continue and become more optimal. Reviving activities that have been programmed but have not yet been carried out, and increasingly minimizing all forms of obstacles encountered, both obstacles in terms of teenagers and religious leaders. An

activity program was developed based on the millennial Islamic young generation which aims to ensure that activities are not monotonous, and it is hoped that the Islamic youth of the mosque will be enthusiastic. In the form of entrepreneurship and education sections in the mosque's Islamic youth structure which aims to be able to develop businesses so they can be more advanced.

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THE ROLE OF PARENTAL COMMUNICATION IN MONITORING SMARTPHONE USERS AT AGE TEENAGERS IN PENGGALAN VILLAGE, TEBING SYAHBANDAR DISTRICT

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Abstract

The role of communication between parents and adolescents can be seen as the efforts made by parents in monitoring and directing the development of adolescents. By creating communication that can affect the relationship between the two, both physically and psychologically. One technology, namely a smartphone, is a sophisticated tool that can penetrate information anywhere and anytime, to find out information from any angle without considering the influence that will be received by its users. Therefore, this research aims to find out how effective and efficient the role of parental communication is in monitoring smartphone users in their teens. In this study, the type of research that the authors use is qualitative research. While the approach used is descriptive analysis, which is a research method that looks at objects or conditions, systematically, factually and accurately describes the facts that have been investigated and the results can be used for the future.

The dominant factor that causes the role of communication between parents and adolescents is not good, resulting in many teenagers losing direction and their growth and development being hampered due to the influence of communication technology in the form of smartphones that are continuously used without any restrictions and good directions

Keywords: *The Role of Communication, Parents, Smartphones, Adolescents*

INTRODUCTION

The role of communication is a process that forms an internal relationship creating a single communication goal so that it runs more effectively and efficiently between communicators with the communications involved. The role of communication enables an action communication carried out for communication targets that are designed so that produce the desired changes. The importance of this communication role can make other people are aware of someone's negligence and can help resolve the problem through communication (Michael Jibrael Rorong: 2016)

The way parents communicate can influence positive or negative perceptions from the child, therefore the communication role used by parents must be appropriate situations and conditions in children. Considering that nowadays children are more sensitive to technology communication which is usually called a smartphone (smart phone or mobile phone). As Parents, giving special attention to teenage children is the main thing to do done. Remembering that teenagers are the nation's next generation or can be said to be agents of change which will provide good changes for religion, nation and state (Adji Annisa: 2015). A teenager is someone who is facing a transition period childhood to adulthood, which includes all the development

experienced as preparation for entering adulthood. These developmental changes include aspects physical, psychological and psychosocial.

Adolescence is a period of very rapid change in physical changes as well as changes in attitudes and behavior. At this teenage age, they tend to have a great curiosity attitude, but besides that they are teenagers usually indicated that he does not yet have commitment (Angelina Hosada Zefay & Indra Prapto: 2019).

So in this case, the dominant factor causing the importance of the role of communication between parents and teenagers is not good, resulting in many teenagers lost direction and his growth and development was hampered due to the influence of communication technology in the form of smartphones which are continuously used without any restrictions and good direction from the teenager himself.

By referring to the background above, the purpose of this writing is to knowing the role of parental communication in monitoring smartphone users at age teenagers, especially problems with teenagers in Hamlet VIII, Penggalangan Village. This matter raises various complex problems and must receive attention from all parties, so that the role of parents is in monitoring their children as they socialize in the new world (digital) is really needed.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research method used in this research is a qualitative method. Study qualitative method, namely research that is not carried out using formulas and statistical symbols. This research also aims to explain the phenomenon in as much depth as possible. in it through data collection. So in this research the problem is emphasized more into (quality) data, not amount (quantity) of data. The approach used in this research is an analytical descriptive approach. According to Issac and Michel, as introduced by Jalaluddin Rahmat, that approach Descriptive aims to systematically describe facts or characteristics of a population certain areas or specific areas factually and carefully. (Ismail Nurdin & Sri Hartati: 2019)

In other words, the descriptive approach is a research method that looks at things objects/conditions, descriptions, systematically, factually and accurately regarding the facts investigated and the results can be used to make future decisions. Approach Descriptive also aims to obtain an in-depth description of speech and behavior that can be observed from an individual, group, community or organization in a setting certain things that are studied from a comprehensive point of view.

In qualitative research, data analysis is generally divided into three levels: (1) data analysis at the initial level, (2) data analysis during field data collection and, (3) data analysis after completing data collection. The essence of data analysis in qualitative research is to reduce data, because in qualitative research the data collected must be in-depth and sufficient according to the focus and objectives of the research. The data analysis process in when data collection consists of: (1) activities starting from the data tracking process with observation techniques, interviews and documentation studies, (2) data or information obtained the unit of analysis is identified, (3) the validity of the unit of analysis is tested through triangulation. All of these activities are carried out in a structured and documented manner (Helaluddin Hengki Wijaya: 2019)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The role of parents towards teenagers is very important given from an early age, because they have been taught Know that the family, especially parents, have a major role in providing influence on children, especially teenagers. Adolescence is a period of quality undergoes the most changes, so that the baggage is transferred from childhood towards adulthood, where childhood experiences growth in all areas, his ability to work decreases and he often ignores his authority.

In this case, the role of parents in the development process is especially the role of people parents to teenagers is very important because teenagers are easily influenced by social interactions not good. Relating to the problem of parental communication towards smartphone users in adolescence. Therefore, every parent has their own way of educating and directing his child on the path he considers right. All that effort of course requires a way of communicating that can make children obey and follow what is said parents want. Communication has very high power in building a relationship within the family, especially the relationship between parents and teenagers requires communication.

Communication needs to be carried out by parents in controlling or supervising teenagers in doing various things. Because adolescence needs attention especially from their parents, especially from the progress of the times which demands of everyone having a smartphone to help with life activities. Like smartphones used by teenagers in Hamlet VIII Penggalangan Village has now been made as a multifunctional tool in its use. From this statement, it is clear that the role Support from parents is very important in guiding children's success in the future come. Moreover, teenagers are still in a transition period and are still looking for their identity himself. In this research, the author found that there are several ways that parents do this in Hamlet VIII Penggalangan Village in monitoring smartphone use on teenagers, namely:

1. Spending Time Together

In implementing effective communication with teenagers, the roles that people play parents can spend time with them. Give them access to express directly with family members. This can make children teenagers Become a more open person and be able to socialize well with people around you. In At the age of teenagers, they are capable and have their own thoughts regarding context and topics that is being talked about. So in this case, as a parent you have to be the one to talk to able to balance children's thinking and not immediately blame them with the opinions they have. Parents are not only active listeners but try to understand and appreciate whatever the teenager says.

Provide sufficient time and focus to communicate with teenagers so that communication can be established effectively. As a parent you shouldn't always either imposes his will on teenagers to become active and open people, but Encourage them by providing a sense of security and comfort in being able to tell what what they are feeling (Melinda Restu Pertiwi et al: 2022).

2. Application of Parental Habits and Motivation

Habituation of positive behavior at home and providing motivation to do so by parents can give encouragement to teenagers to always do something in a good and responsible manner. Good behavior habits applied at home so that teenagers can get used to these activities. Good habits and encouragement have a great influence on the souls of teenagers, if they are parents always give it, then teenagers will imitate it. These habits aside forming

discipline as well as responsibility for carrying out obligations both as children or as students.

Parental example is the main factor in the success of character formation within family. This is in line with the proverb, namely "the fruit does not fall far from the tree". So, Any behavior from parents will decrease or be followed by their children. Apart from that, most of them Psychological researchers reveal that most of what children learn is not original from what parents say when teaching their children, but most children learn from the example of their parents.

Habituation is an educational method by which children get used to doing something since he was little. The essence of this habit is repetition. Behavior Humans are largely determined by their habits. If someone is used to doing good then he does it easily, and vice versa. Because it's a child From an early age, he was taught to be given good habits so that these habits became personal to him himself (Agus Wibowo: 2012)

3. Provide Advice and Direction

Parents are two individuals who become one who live in a relationship which is called family. In a family, having children is a form of trust given by God to be looked after and educated as best as possible. For that, parents of course has a role in providing the best for his children, by always guiding them and direct them to get the best life in the future. Attitude authoritarian, always feels that the right and best way of educating should be eliminated. On the other hand, as parents you must always support, give advice and direct them, because adolescence is a time when their emotions are being tested. Be a person parents who can act as friends in front of them (Abdul Cholik: 2016)

Giving good advice is the responsibility of parents, as well as directing them Always behaving positively is also a parent's duty. In Q.S Surah Lukman: 18, Allah SWT says:

وَلَا تُصَعِّرْ خَدَّكَ لِلنَّاسِ وَلَا تَمْشِ فِي الْأَرْضِ مَرَحًا إِنَّ اللَّهَ لَا يُحِبُّ كُلَّ مُخْتَالٍ فَخُورٍ ﴿١٨﴾

Do not turn your face away from humans (out of pride) and do not walk on this earth arrogantly. Indeed, Allah does not like anyone who is arrogant or very proud of themselves.

From this verse it can be seen that parents have the obligation to advise and directing children to become someone who has a good and virtuous personality sublime. Always act and behave in a noble manner and do not be arrogant in front of other people

4. Sanctions/Punishments

Smartphone communication media is a communication technology that is very popular by many groups such as adults, teenagers and also children. That media is not it is only used as a communication tool but is also used for entertainment, games and others which is in the smartphone. However, not all teenagers use it smartphones can be good and wise, there are still many to find some deviations committed by teenagers.

Punishment is an educational tool that parents use to discipline child. The purpose of punishment in Islamic education is to provide direction and improvement, not revenge. For this reason, parents must understand their children and their character beforehand punish him. Motivate children to try to correct their mistakes and errors it is forgiven after

it is repaired. Parents must also use forms of punishment to direct behavior teenagers to conform to expected behavior and stop that behavior not expected.

Punishment is a tool that is deliberately used to provide an effect deterrent so that teenagers think about their behavior. The punishment used for neutralize smartphone users among teenagers. To obtain an education being required does not mean parents have to force them to fulfill all the facilities What is there, at least parents have provided what their children need (Aprilia Dewi Anjarwati: 2019).

One of the efforts made by parents is to monitor smartphone users teenagers in Hamlet VIII Penggalangan Village is to provide sanctions or punishment if a teenager has violated the rules in the house or committed an act which should not be related to smartphone use. Parents have rights full of their children, therefore this needs to be applied in people's communication roles old.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of research data analysis on the Role of Parental Communication Monitoring Smartphone Users in Teenage Hamlet VIII, Penggalangan Village Tebing Syahbandar District, Serdang Bedagai Regency, it can be concluded that:

Taking time, namely giving some of your parents' time to teenagers can be done making relationships within the family more harmonious and communication between parents with teenagers are also more effective. You can also spend time with teenagers making them become more open individuals.

Implementation of habituation, namely positive behavior that is applied at home so that it is good Teenagers are able to get used to these activities. Habits matter a lot in the soul of teenagers, if parents always provide good habits, then teenagers imitate him.

Application of advice, namely the method used by parents to provide guidance and direction and warnings to teenagers about using smartphones.

Parents use sanctions/punishments to direct behavior conform to expected behavior and stop behavior that is not expected. This is a tool that is deliberately used to provide a deterrent effect for teenagers think about the behavior carried out.

There are various ways for parents to monitor teenagers' development related to smartphone use. The concerns felt by parents about teenagers above is a natural thing. That's because parents know that apart from having an impact While positive, smartphones also have a negative impact. But besides that, the parents in Hamlet VIII Penggalangan Village also realizes that in this day and age, use Teenagers can't just let go of smartphones. Considering the need for

Smartphones are also needed, such as for studying and other things. Because in the era of globalization and the development of increasingly sophisticated science and technology, the spread information and faster and easier telecommunications access demands it always following him, one of which is a smartphone. Likewise, there are teenagers in Hamlet VIII, Penggalangan Village They make many deviations, such as not using smartphones used as a learning medium, but more widely used as a means of entertainment them as well as the high intensity of smartphone use, thus making some of them They feel addicted and ultimately have a negative impact on themselves teenager.

In this regard, that is why researchers state how important it is the role of parental communication in monitoring teenage children when using smartphone, this is so that they don't fall into things they don't want. Because teenagers are valuable national assets and of course have good qualities.

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THE INFLUENCE OF THE SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT ON STUDENTS' LEARNING MOTIVATION IN PRIVATE MADRASAH ALIYAH HIDAYAH OF THE KHALIPAH BOOKIE

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ABSTRACT

This research approach is a quantitative approach, namely research where the data obtained is related to numbers which causes the use of statistical analysis techniques. The results of the research in this thesis, the school environment at Madrasah Aliyah Hidayah Private Bandar Khalipah is in the "enough" category. This can be seen from the average school environment at Madrasah Aliyah Hidayah Private Bandar Khalipah, which is 62.36 which is in the interval 56.80 - 68.01. The learning motivation of students at Madrasah Aliyah Private Hidayah Bandar Khalipah is in the "enough" category. This can be seen from the average student learning motivation at Madrasah Aliyah Hidayah Private Bandar Khalipah, which is 54.57 which is at intervals of 48.62 - 60.49.

Based on the results of the t test, it can be seen that the first alternative hypothesis (H_a) test is accepted. Hypothesis testing is done by comparing the results of tcount with ttable. From the table of t test results, the tcount value is -2.349. Meanwhile, for ttable with a significance level of 0.05, a ttable value of 1.6759 was obtained. The comparison between the two results: tcount > ttable (-2.349 > 1.6759). The significance value of t for the school environment variable is 0.03 and this value is smaller than the probability of 0.05 (0.03 < 0.05). So that in this test it shows that H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected. This means that there is an influence between the school environment on student learning motivation at Madrasah Aliyah Private Hidayah Bandar Khalipah.

Keywords: *Learning Motivation, School Environment*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a universal activity in human life and in the life of any society there is always a need for education. Education is a process to improve human dignity.

Every nation views that education is an effort that plays an important role in the survival of the nation. Education can develop personality, knowledge, skills and broad thinking insights.¹

The success of the educational process is greatly influenced by the learning that takes place because it is the core of the educational process. In learning, students' motivation to

¹ Akhmad Muhaimin Azzet, *Urgensi Pendidikan Karakter di Indonesia*, (Yogyakarta: Ar- Ruzz Media, 2011), h. 9.

participate in learning is a very important aspect. Student learning motivation is really needed to achieve learning goals, because it is a factor that has a big influence on success in learning.

By motivation is meant efforts to provide conditions so that the child wants to do it. If he doesn't like it, he will try to avoid it. Children who have high intelligence may fail in lessons because they lack motivation. Good results are achieved with strong motivation. Children who fail cannot simply be blamed. Maybe it's because teachers fail to provide motivation that arouses activity in children.

In this case it is very clear that the role of the teacher is very important. How teachers make efforts to grow and provide motivation so that their students carry out learning activities well. To be able to learn well requires a good process and motivation.

Providing motivation to a student, moving students to do something or want to do something. Providing motivation is not an easy job. Motivation for one child or one group may not work for another child or group.²

Students who have high motivation for learning show great attention to learning activities and have satisfactory results and vice versa. In addition, the awards given to students are very effective in motivating them to carry out learning activities. Another factor that greatly influences students' learning motivation is the existence of a classroom atmosphere that is a learning environment.

According to Skinner, student motivation is largely determined by their environment. Therefore, students will be motivated to learn if the learning environment can provide stimulation so that students are interested in learning. It is hoped that students' understanding and good use of the classroom atmosphere will be able to support their success in learning.³

Some ways to foster motivation are through varying teaching methods, repeating information, providing new stimuli for example through questions to students, giving students opportunities to channel their desire to learn, using media and tools that attract students' attention, such as pictures, photos, diagrams, and so on. In general, students will be stimulated to learn (actively involved in teaching) if they see that the teaching situation tends to satisfy them according to their needs.

For a teacher, the purpose of motivation is to move or stimulate students so that they have the desire and willingness to improve their learning achievements so that educational goals are achieved in accordance with what is expected and stipulated in the school curriculum.

So, it is clear that every motivational action has a goal. The clearer the goal that is expected or will be achieved, the clearer it is how the motivating action will be carried out. Therefore, every person who will provide motivation must know and truly understand the life background, needs and personality of the person who will be motivated.

Students' learning motivation at school is not only influenced by how actively students study and can understand the lessons at school, but also the supportive conditions of the school environment. A comfortable and clean school environment can support optimal student growth and development, students become healthier and can think clearly, so they can become intelligent students and in the future become quality human resources.

² S. Nasution, *Didaktik Asas-asas Mengajar* (Jakarta: Bumi Aksara, 2010), h. 73.

³ Elida Prayitno, *Motivasi Dalam Belajar*, (Jakarta: Proyek Pengembangan Lembaga Pendidikan Tenaga Kependidikan, 2015), h. 5

Motivation can also be said to be a series of efforts to provide certain conditions, so that someone wants and wants to do something, and if he doesn't like it, he will try to eliminate or avoid that feeling of dislike. So motivation can be stimulated by external factors but motivation also grows within a person.

People often interpret the environment narrowly, as if the environment is just the natural surroundings outside of humans or individuals. The environment actually includes all material and stimuli inside and outside the individual, both physiological, psychological and socio-cultural. Thus, the environment can be interpreted physiologically, psychologically and socio-culturally.

Physiologically, the environment includes all physical conditions and materials in the body such as nutrition, vitamins, water, acids, temperature, nervous system, blood circulation, breathing, food digestion, endocrine glands, growth cells, and physical health.

Psychologically, the environment includes all the stimulation received by an individual from birth to death. For example, this stimulation takes the form of: the characteristics of "genes", the interaction of "genes", tastes, desires, feelings, goals, interests, needs, desires, emotions and intellectual capacity.

Socio-culturally, the environment includes all stimulation, interactions and external conditions in relation to the treatment or work of other people. Family lifestyle, group interactions, community lifestyle, training, learning, education, teaching, guidance and counseling, are included in this environment.⁴

The school environment is one of the places or vehicles most commonly used as a learning medium in the teaching and learning process in Indonesia. The school environment is considered to be able to foster interest and stimulate students to act and prove the learning outcomes received, especially in the field of natural sciences.

In every aspect and behavior of students, this can be seen from their daily habits. This is the case with the classroom environment and even the school environment. If the school environment and classroom environment, including classrooms, are clean and well-organized, then the motivation to learn that arises will encourage friends to be enthusiastic about participating in learning.

The condition of the student's learning environment is thought to strongly determine the high/low level of student motivation to learn. The conditions in question are the conditions in which children learn, grow and develop towards maturity, as well as the atmosphere that accompanies growth and development. Learning environmental conditions include natural conditions, living environment, peer interactions, and social life.

In accordance with the ideas put forward by Ki Hajar Dewantoro in Abu Ahmadi & Nur Uhbiyati, he differentiates the educational environment into three, which are often known as the Three Education Centers, namely: the family, school and community environments.⁵

Based on observations at the Hidayah Private Madrasah Bandar Khalipah, information was obtained from student learning outcomes stating that students' learning motivation varies, this is due to several factors, including facilities and infrastructure that support learning, the condition of the school building, and discipline. This proves that the school environment has quite an important influence on students in achieving their learning achievements. The better

⁴ Wasty Soemanto, *Psikologi Pendidikan* (Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta, 2016), h. 84-85

⁵ Abu Ahmadi & Nur Uhbiyati, *Ilmu Pendidikan*, (Jakarta: PT Rineka Cipta, 2015), h.66

the school environment, the more motivated students will be to study harder in achieving achievements.

Based on the description above, the author is interested in conducting further research on "The influence of the Madrasah environment on student learning motivation at the Private Hidayah Aliyah Bandar Khalipah Madrasah."

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a quantitative approach, where the symptoms will be measured using numbers. As Sugiyono said, quantitative data is data in the form of numbers.⁶

Thus, this research allows statistical analysis techniques to be used to process data. This research also includes ex post facto research. Ex post facto research is research where the independent variables have occurred when the researcher starts by observing the dependent variable in a study.

The research was carried out by tracing backwards to find out the factors that caused the incident without providing treatment or manipulating the variables studied. This research was conducted to find out information regarding the influence of the school environment on student learning motivation at the Hidayah Private Madrasah Aliyah Bandar Khalipah.

Data analysis techniques in quantitative research use statistics. The statistics used in this research are descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics can be used when researchers only want to describe sample data, and do not want to make conclusions that apply to the population from which the sample was taken. The hypothesis testing technique in this research uses regression analysis techniques.

HASIL DAN PEMBAHASAN

The results of the t test show that the first alternative hypothesis (H_a) test is accepted. Hypothesis testing is carried out by comparing the results of t_{count} with t_{table} . From the t test results table, the calculated t value is -2.349 . Meanwhile, for t table with a significance level of 0.05, the t table value is 1.6759.

A comparison between the two produces: $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($-2.349 > 1.6759$). The t significance value for the school environment variable is 0.03 and this value is smaller than the probability of 0.05 ($0.03 < 0.05$). So this test shows that H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected. This means that there is an influence between the school environment on students' learning motivation at the Hidayah Private Madrasah Aliyah Bandar Khalipah.

This is in accordance with the opinion of Dimiyati and Mudijono, who state that students' environment can be in the form of natural conditions, living environment, peer interactions and social life. As members of society, students can be influenced by the surrounding environment. Natural disasters, dirty housing, threats from naughty colleagues, fights between students, will interfere with seriousness in studying.

On the other hand, a beautiful campus, school, harmonious student relationships, will strengthen motivation to learn. Therefore, the quality of a healthy school environment and social harmony and social order need to be improved. With a safe, peaceful, orderly and beautiful environment, enthusiasm and motivation for learning can easily be strengthened.

⁶ Sugiyono, *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*, (Bandung: Alfabeta, 2016), h. 23

Based on simple linear regression analysis, the results of the regression equation can be obtained, namely $Y = 33.921 + 0.331X$. From the regression equation above, it can be interpreted that the constant value = 33.921, this shows that if the learning environment value (X) in the research object is equal to zero, then the amount of student learning motivation (Y) is 33.921. Coefficient value = 0.331, this shows that if the learning environment value (X) increases by one point, then student learning motivation will increase by 0.331.

A conducive school environment, both physical, social and psychological, can foster and develop motives to work well and productively. For this reason, the best possible physical environment can be created, for example room cleanliness, layout, facilities and so on.

Humans and the environment have a very close relationship. The concept of ecology has been developed as a scientific discipline that studies living things and the interactions of various components within them. In essence, nature and all its contents have functions and benefits in the life of this world as confirmed by Allah in the Al-Qur'an Surah Ar Rahman verse 10.

وَالْأَرْضَ وَضَعَهَا لِلْأَنَامِ ﴿١٠﴾

And Allah has leveled the earth for (His) creatures.

Based on the results of the simple correlation analysis, it can be seen in the Model Summary output from the results of the simple linear regression analysis that the R square is 0.98. The R square can be called the termination coefficient, which in this case means that there is a 98% contribution or influence between school learning environment variables on learning motivation. while the remaining 2% can be explained by other causes outside the research variables.

Referring to the results of research analysis, it can be seen that the school environment is the second most influential environment after the family environment, and the success of the learning process is not only determined by a process or school environment, but the family environment and community environment are also factors that support this success.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

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THE INFLUENCE OF LEARNING MORAL CREEDS ON STUDENT BEHAVIOR AT THE BUSTANUL ULUM GUPPI PRIVATE MADRASAH TSANAWIYAH, TEBING TINGGI CITY

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Abstract

This research approach is a quantitative approach, namely research where the data obtained is related to numbers which causes the use of statistical analysis techniques. The results of the research in this thesis, based on the results of the analysis it is known that the rcount or rxy value is 0.868 much greater than rtable (which is 0.235 and 0.306). Because rxy is greater than rtable, thus the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted and the null hypothesis (H_o) is rejected, because there is a significant positive relationship between the effect of learning aqidah morals on student behavior at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Private Bustanul Ulum Guppi Tebing Tinggi City.

Aqidah Akhlak Learning on student behavior at the Private Madrasah Tsanawiyah Bustanul Ulum Guppi Tebing Tinggi City. The analysis of this study has a high positive correlation, namely 0.868. This is in accordance with the results of observations in the field that teaching aqeedah akhlaq is taught by educators very well because in addition to containing all the material it also provides understanding to students, so they can understand and practice about aqeedah akhlaq learning. From these calculations it is obtained that the Coefficient of Determination is 75.3%. Thus it can be seen that the contribution of the influence of learning aqidah morals on student behavior in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Private Bustanul Ulum Guppi City of Tebing Tinggi is 75.3%.

Keywords: *Epistemic Beliefs, Elementary School Teachers, Reading Comprehension*

INTRODUCTION

Education is something that is very important and cannot be neglected in every human being's life. This is because with education humans are able to raise their dignity towards a cultural civilization and a more advanced, dynamic and scientific way of thinking.

In relation to education based on divinity, Islamic religious education is an effort to instill the teachings of the Islamic religion in humans, one of which is studying and instilling good creeds and morals so that they reflect a good Muslim personality, apart from studying these morals, they must be practiced in everyday life.

Moral education is a conscious effort to prepare students to understand Islamic teachings (knowing), especially in the aspects of Aqidah (tauhid) and morals, to be skilled in carrying out Islamic teachings (doing), and to carry out Islamic teachings in everyday life (being) so that they reflect the teachings of the Islamic religion. the Rahmatan lil alamin.¹

Islamic teachings guide humanity starting with improving morals. If human morals are good, then the family, society and nation will be good too. Islam always teaches that every community should always try to improve their personal and societal morals. The damaged

¹ Khalimi, *Pembelajaran Akidah dan Akhlak*, (Jakarta: KEMENAG, 2009) h. 51.

social environment must immediately change its morals, so that its actions and behavior become good.

Islam, both its beliefs and education, are much better than other schools of thought. His faith is stronger than any belief. Therefore, young Islamic men and women should not fall into a dead end when facing various difficulties or questions.

This verse explains the noble promise from Allah to believers who strive in His path by sacrificing their lives and property and enduring torture and obstacles. Therefore, Allah will give them guidance, help them make up their minds, and provide assistance, so that they obtain victory in this world and happiness and glory in the hereafter.

Attention to the importance of morals is getting stronger, namely when humans in the modern era are faced with serious moral and ethical problems, if left unchecked, it will destroy the future of the nation concerned. Deviant life practices and misuse of opportunities by taking the form of sadistic acts and harming others thrive in areas of immorality. Corruption, collusion, muggings, robberies, murders, rapes, brawls between students and residents, and deprivation of human rights in general are too much to see and witness.

The way to overcome this is not only with money, science and technology, but must be accompanied by calming in the spiritual mental field (instilling strong beliefs) and noble morals. As science and technology develop, humans are dragged along and immersed in a transparent world without secrets. Humans are faced with rapid changes in various dimensions of life.²

There are many reasons behind changes or deterioration in mental behavior, beliefs and morals that are not in accordance with Islamic teachings. What is ironic is that it strikes students where the values of *akhlakul karimah* or commendable morals have often been abandoned, such as manners towards Allah, parents, teachers, friends, other creatures, impoliteness, rude/dirty speaking, lying, excessive fear of other than Allah. and others. Nowadays, from the perspective of noble morals, we observe an alarming phenomenon. Before our eyes is a reality that often makes no sense. Noble morals and noble character, both at the individual and social levels, seem to be sinking. The decline in morals among society is getting worse.

Moral education is a very fundamental aspect in public life. Because no matter how smart a student is without being based on good morals, he cannot reflect a good personality either. Moral issues are an important issue for Islamic teachings and for the lives of its people.

Morals are a person's personal values and self-esteem, so people who do not have morals will lose their self-esteem before Allah SWT and society. It cannot be denied that both developments are the result of education and teaching. Humans really need education and teaching because without education and teaching humans can fall into the abyss of destruction and will always prioritize only their desires. As a creature created by Allah SWT. Humans should be able to control themselves from bad things. Morals are traits that are pervasive in the soul and reflect spontaneous behavior without being artificial. A person who has good morals will find peace, happiness and benefit both for himself and others.

Thus it is clear that learning the *Aqidah Akhlak* is a basic stage of implementing beliefs and is also an integral part of the National education system. Indeed, moral education in schools is not the only factor that influences student behavior. However, apart from that, moral education also greatly influences the development of student behavior. Education in faith and

² Aminuddin dkk, *Pendidikan Agama Islam*, (Jakarta : Ghalia Indonesia, 2012), h. 157

morals is the basis of every education, it is also the foundation and stronghold of developments in the times that cannot be separated from misleading external culture.

Because we see that it is important to instill the learning of Aqidah Morals from an early age, school is a place to nurture and prepare students and a place for children to socialize with peers and a place for teachers to gather. Therefore, it is very necessary for this behavior development to be carried out through learning the Aqidah Akhlak at school, as well as in family life, because learning the Aqidah Akhlak contains a lot of material that directs students to always behave well and avoid bad behavior.

In general, the moral aqidah learning given to tsanawiyah students still includes basic and simple Islamic aqidah and moral values, for example the values of being helpful, humble, speaking politely and so on. This is because basically formal education regarding Islamic aqidah and moral values is being received by students for the first time. Apart from that, of course the material provided is adapted to the stage of mental development of students at the madrasah tsanawiyah level. Education regarding aqidah and morals in more depth can be studied at a linear advanced level, namely at the aliyah level up to Higher Education.

Madrasah Tsanawiyah Bustanul Ulum Guppi is one of the formal educational institutions that has gained enough trust from the community in the Padang Hilir District of Tebing Tinggi City, especially the community located in the Jalan Deblod Sundoro area and its surroundings. In this madrasa, students take part in one of the lessons aimed at shaping student behavior, namely Aqidah Akhlak learning, where the learning aims to shape students' Islamic beliefs, morals and manners.

Aqidah Akhlak learning contains materials that can direct students to always behave in a commendable manner and avoid disgraceful actions. Apart from that, learning Aqidah Akhlak basically aims to form a good personality in accordance with the teachings of the Islamic religion, namely becoming a human being who has faith and is devoted to Allah SWT, so that he can carry himself to the highest level of glory in accordance with Islamic law.

Based on these problems and thoughts, the researcher was interested in researching and presenting it in a research report with the title "The Influence of Learning Moral Creeds on Student Behavior at the Bustanul Ulum Guppi Private Madrasah Tsanawiyah, Tebing Tinggi City."

RESEARCH METHODS

The research method that will be used in this research is an associative method with a quantitative approach. The associative method is a method that intends to explain the causal relationship and influence between variables through hypothesis testing. According to Sugiyono "associative research is research that aims to determine the relationship between two or more variables. In this research, a theory can be built that can function to explain, predict and control a phenomenon."³

In this research, the associative method is used to explain the influence of teacher teaching skills and student interest on student learning achievement. This research explains the relationship that influences and is influenced by the variables to be studied. Using a quantitative

³ Sugiyono, Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D, h. 43.

approach because the data that will be used to analyze the relationship between variables is expressed with numbers or a numerical scale.⁴

Pendekatan penelitian ini adalah pendekatan kuantitatif, yaitu penelitian dimana data yang obtained relates to numbers that lead to the use of statistical analysis techniques. According to Saifuddin Azwar "a quantitative approach is research whose analysis focuses more on numerical data (numbers) which are processed using statistical methods." In this research, the independent variable is learning Aqidah Morals. Meanwhile, the dependent variable is student behavior which is also known as variable Y.

Samples To simplify the process of data collection and data processing, the researcher took a sampling technique. Sampling (sampling) according to Nana Syaodih Sukmadinata "is a process of selecting and determining the type of sample in calculating the size of the sample that will be the subject or object of research."⁵ So, here the sample is a part or representative of the population studied.

The sampling technique used is a probability random sampling technique or random selection using the Slovin formula, as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

To use this formula, first determine what the error tolerance limit is. This error tolerance limit is expressed as a percentage. The smaller the error tolerance, the more accurately the sample represents the population. In this research, the author states that the error tolerance limit used is 10%. So in taking samples from a total population of 268, namely:

$$n = \frac{268}{1 + 268 (0,1)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{268}{1 + 2,68}$$

$$n = 72,8$$

Thus, the sample obtained from a population of 268 is 72.8 rounded to 73. Thus it can be seen that the research sample numbered 73 people.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Learning aqidah morals is providing direction or guidance to students by referring to the values and teachings of the Islamic religion so that students have good behavior and continue to adhere to it. Learning aqidah morals discusses divine issues in detail, including the pillars of faith and other basic teachings of Islam. Learning moral aqidah plays a very important role in shaping students' behavior because learning moral aqidah discusses various materials which aim to provide understanding so that students have good personality and behavior.

⁴ Riduwan, *Belajar Mudah Penelitian Untuk Guru, Karyawan dan Peneliti Pemula*, (Bandung: Alfabeta, 2019), h. 50

⁵ Nana Syaodih Sukmadinata, *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan* (Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarta, 2014). hlm. 252.

The role of learning moral aqidah is very important and is really needed by students in developing their behavior in accordance with Islamic law, especially during secondary level education, where at this level of education students' behavior begins to be formed. Therefore, learning moral aqidah is really needed by students.

This research was carried out at one of the Tsanawiyah Madrasahs in Tebing Tinggi City, specifically at the Bustanul Ulum Guppi Private Tsanawiyah Madrasah, Tebing Tinggi City. This research involved all 268 students. The sampling technique used in this research was the probability random sampling technique or random selection using the Slovin formula. From using the Slovin formula, we get 72.8 or rounded up to 73. Thus, the sample used in this research consisted of 73 respondents.

The techniques and instruments in this research use observation techniques to observe the process of learning aqidah akhlak and observe the behavior of students, tests carried out by researchers to measure the extent of student behavior after learning aqidah akhlak, documentation techniques are used to see the conditions of the location in this research including, school identity, vision and mission as well as existing facilities at the school, especially at the Bustanul Ulum Guppi Private Madrasah Tsanawiyah, Tebing Tinggi City. The instrument used was a questionnaire consisting of 12 statement items and 4 alternative answers for each variable X and variable Y. So the question items distributed totaled 24 question items.

The questionnaire instrument for measuring moral aqidah learning on student behavior has carried out several test requirements. Testing the validity of variable data collection.

Next, to find out whether the two variables are normally distributed, a normality test is carried out with a significance level set at 0.05, provided that if the significance is more than 0.05, it means the data is normal, whereas if the significance is less than 0.05, it means the data is not normal. The normality test in this study used the IBM SPSS Statistics version 22 for Windows computer program.

The results from IBM SPSS Statistics version 22 for Windows show that the significance value (Monte Carlo Sig. Lower Bound) for all variables is 0.813. Based on the provisions, if the significance is more than 0.05, it means the data is normal, whereas if the significance is less than 0.05, it means the data is not normal. Thus, it can be seen that the significance value (Monte Carlo Sig. Lower Bound) for all variables is $0.813 > 0.05$, so the data in this study is normally distributed.

Next, to determine whether there is an influence of learning moral beliefs on student behavior at the Private Madrasah Tsanawiyah Bustanul Ulum Guppi, Tebing Tinggi City, researchers used a correlation test using Karl Pearson's Product Moment formula. Based on the results of calculations using the Product Moment formula from Karl Pearson, the r_{xy} value is 0.86860204, rounded to 0.868. From these results it is known that there is a positive correlation between the influence of learning moral beliefs on student behavior at the Bustanul Ulum Guppi Private Madrasah Tsanawiyah, Tebing Tinggi City.

As for finding out how big the contribution (contribution) is from the influence of learning moral beliefs on student behavior at the Bustanul Ulum Guppi Private Madrasah Tsanawiyah, Tebing Tinggi City, researchers used the formula $KD = r^2 \times 100\%$. From the calculation results, the Determination Coefficient value was 75.3%. Thus it can be seen that the contribution of the influence of learning moral beliefs on student behavior at the Bustanul Ulum Guppi Private Madrasah Tsanawiyah Tebing Tinggi City is 75.3% and the remainder ($100\% - 75.3\% = 24.7\%$)

is influenced by other variables that are not examined in this research such as the madrasa environment, family environment and so on.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion of research results, it can be concluded that Aqidah Akhlak learning affects student behavior at the Bustanul Ulum Guppi Private Madrasah Tsanawiyah, Tebing Tinggi City. In the analysis of this research, there is a high positive correlation, namely 0.868. This is in accordance with the results of observations in the field that the learning of moral aqidah taught by educators is very good because apart from containing all the material it also provides understanding to students, so that they can understand and practice the learning of moral aqidah.

From these calculations, the Determination Coefficient was obtained at 75.3%. Thus, it can be seen that the contribution of the influence of learning moral beliefs on student behavior at the Private Madrasah Tsanawiyah Bustanul Ulum Guppi, Tebing Tinggi City is 75.3%.

Based on the analysis results, it is known that the rcount or rxy value of 0.868 is much greater than rtable (which are 0.235 and 0.306). Because rxy is greater than rtable, the alternative hypothesis (Ha) is accepted and the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected, because there is a significant positive relationship between the influence of learning moral beliefs on student behavior at the Bustanul Ulum Guppi Private Madrasah Tsanawiyah, Tebing Tinggi City.

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MASTER OF CEREMONY MANTEN COMMUNICATION STRATEGY JAVA AT TRADITIONAL JAVANESE WEDDING CEREMONIES IN TANJUNG MARULAK HILIR DISTRICT RAMBUTAN DISTRICT HIGH CLIFFS CITY

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Abstract

This research uses descriptive qualitative method. Qualitative descriptive is focused on answering research questions related to the questions of who, what, where and how an event or experience occurs until finally it is examined in depth to find patterns that emerge in these events. The result of this study is the lack of communication between the Master of Ceremony Manten Javanese and the Javanese community in Tanjung Marulak Hilir Village, which can be seen from the low level of public understanding of Javanese traditional marriages which is characterized by the lack of human resources who can carry out the task of guiding wedding processions, especially as Pranata Adicara.

Keywords: *Communication Strategy, Javanese Traditional Wedding Ceremony, Master of Ceremony Manten Jawa*

INTRODUCTION

Marriage is an agreement or aqad (ijab and qabul) between a man and a woman to justify physical relations as a legal husband and wife which contains the conditions and pillars determined by Islamic religious law and statutory regulations. Marriage is carrying out an aqad or agreement to bind oneself between a man and a woman to justify sexual relations between the two parties, on a voluntary basis and with the consent of both parties to create a happy family life filled with a sense of affection and peace in a way -a way that is approved by Allah (Ahmad Azhar: 1977).

The Javanese people are one of the ethnicities that are very proud of their language and culture, even though sometimes they are no longer able to use the Javanese language actively, and do not really understand their culture (Ni Wayan Sartini: 2009). Regarding Javanese culture, we can also touch on the organizers of traditional wedding ceremonies and ceremonial activities which are considered very meaningful for the people who support them, apart from being respect for ancestors and gratitude towards Almighty God, as well as a means of socializing and strengthening existing cultural values and applies in everyday people's lives.

One way to enliven a wedding is by holding a wedding ceremony. Javanese people often hold traditional Javanese wedding ceremonies as a stage that a person must go through before entering real domestic life, which is a sacred ceremony that contains expressions of customs, mental attitudes, thoughts and spiritual views that originate from Javanese culture.

During the traditional Javanese wedding ceremony procession, the language used is Javanese. In Javanese tradition, the wedding ceremony or manten is performed in Javanese wayang. The language used is different from refined Javanese. The language is more difficult to understand because the wayang language was used by ancient Javanese people. In supporting the smoothness and success

of such a sacred series of wedding processions, one of the supports is the role of the event organizer (Master of Ceremony) who uses the Javanese language *Pranata adicara*.

The lack of communication between the Master of Ceremony *Manten Jawa* and the Javanese community in Tanjung Marulak Hilir Subdistrict can be seen from the low level of community understanding about traditional Javanese weddings which is characterized by the lack of human resources who can carry out their duties as guides for wedding processions, especially as *Pranata adicara*.

By referring to the background above, the purpose of this writing is to find out the communication strategies that need to be carried out by the Master of Ceremony *Manten Jawa* in Tanjung Marulak Hilir Village, Rambutan District, Tebing Tinggi City in Traditional Javanese Wedding Ceremonies.

RESEARCH METHODS

Polit D. F (2004) explains that this research uses descriptive qualitative methods. Descriptive qualitative research is qualitative research for a descriptive study. This type of research is generally used in social phenomenology. Qualitative descriptive (QD) is focused on answering research questions related to the question of who, what, where and how an event or experience occurred until finally it is studied in depth to find patterns that emerge in the event. , H, Sefcik : 2016.

The rationale for using this method is because this research wants to know about phenomena that exist in natural conditions, not in controlled, laboratory or experimental conditions. In addition, because researchers need to directly visit the field with the research object, descriptive qualitative research is more appropriate to use. This research was carried out using the following steps: 1) Determine the problem in the research; 2) Determine the limitations of the research problem; 3) Determine the research focus and subfocus; 4) Data collection; 5) Processing and interpreting data; 6) The emergence of theory; 7) Reporting research results.

Qualitative data collection techniques according to. In this research, the data collection techniques used by researchers are as follows: 1) Observation; 2) Interview (Interview); 3) Documentation.

Qualitative data analysis is carried out if the empirical data obtained is qualitative data in the form of a collection of words and not a series of numbers and cannot be arranged into categories/classification structures. Data can be collected in various ways (observation, interviews, document digests, tape recordings) and is usually processed first before it is ready to be used (through note-taking, typing, editing, or writing), but descriptive qualitative analysis still uses the same words. usually arranged into expanded text and does not use mathematical calculations or statistics as analysis tools. Data analysis techniques used in descriptive qualitative research include interview transcripts, data reduction, triangulation, data display and verification.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sugito (2023) explains that Javanese traditional wedding procedures basically have several stages that are usually passed through, namely the initial stage, the preparation stage, the peak stage of the event, and the final stage. However, not everyone who organizes a wedding always implements this. Some of these series have now undergone changes in line with developing

values. Until now, there are Javanese people who are interested in carrying out the stages of a wedding ritual ceremony in a complete and complete classical style.

The traditional Javanese wedding ceremony in Tanjung Marulak Hilir Village, Rambutan District is oriented towards the Surakarta School or Yogyakarta School. Sugito explained that, among the series of Javanese traditional wedding ceremonies are as follows (Sugito: 2023).

First, the wedding ceremony, where the bride's guardian hands over her daughter to the groom, and the groom accepts it. After the marriage vows, prayers continued, the marriage sermon and the presentation of the dowry. After completion, the two of them were legally husband and wife both in religion and state.

Second, exchange rings. This process can be carried out in a series of wedding ceremonies. The exchange of rings symbolizes the love of the bride and groom.

Third, call. After the wedding ceremony was completed, the bride and groom were reunited wearing typical Yogyakarta clothing and accompanied by a musical piece. According to Yogyakarta custom, the presence of the bride is preceded by a dance by four pairs of dancers called beksan edan-edanan. Meanwhile, the groom's presence was preceded by two pairs of crazy beksan accompanied by the piece bindri. This dance has the meaning of being a means of expelling the haunting spirits that would disturb the progress of the panggih ceremony.

Fourth, Balangan ordered. When the bride and groom met, they both approached about three meters and then both began throwing bundles of soruh leaves and orange leaves tied with white thread. The two did it with enthusiasm and happiness, and everyone smiled happily. The leaves used are believed to have the power to ward off various bad disorders. By throwing leaves at each other, they show that the bride and groom are truly real people, not demons or other people who think of themselves as the groom or bride.

Fifth, wiji dadi is the process of breaking eggs. The groom's right foot steps on the egg until it breaks, then his feet are washed by the bride using water filled with setaman flowers. This means that the groom is ready to become a responsible father and husband, while the bride will serve her husband loyally.

Sixth, dahar klimah symbolizes family harmony, enjoying God's gifts, and having enough food and clothing. Lauk pandang or ati symbolizes steadfastness in his choice to live together to build a family, it also symbolizes the hope of a husband who has a steadfast heart and a wife who can keep family secrets.

Seventh, sungkeman where the bride and groom kneel to their parents to ask for their blessing which begins with sungkeman to the bride's parents and ends with a wedding party where the guests and invitees congratulate the bride and groom.

If culture or customs do not contradict religious rules and do not give rise to polytheism and are in accordance with Islamic law, then Islamic religion does not limit that culture or customs from developing in society. Sugito (2023) explains that

"In the wedding culture carried out by Javanese people, several things are not permitted by the Islamic religion, namely: First, the ceremony of placing offerings. Second, holding an excessive wedding party. Third, improve your intention to always be on the path of Allah SWT. Fourth, when holding a wedding party, it should be simple. Fifth, when inviting invited guests, priority is given to relatives, neighbors and people of the same religion regardless of social status, namely rich or poor. Sixth, it is best not to overdo the wedding party. Seventh, at

weddings it is recommended to avoid mixing members of the opposite sex. Eighth, do not fill the reception with evil things (immorality).

The results of the explanation above explain that the obstacles faced by the Master of Ceremony Manten Java in providing an understanding of the Javanese community, the inability to carry out a series of traditional event processions, especially Javanese traditional wedding ceremonies, is very unfortunate for the Javanese community, so there is a need for innovations in inviting Javanese ethnic community to socialize Javanese culture in Tanjung Marulak Hilir Village.

In carrying out an activity, the word obstacle cannot be separated from it, so how can an obstacle be overcome? The only way is to look for a solution, by looking for a solution, how to make sure that an obstacle can have a meeting point or be called a way out, then Therefore, in this activity of developing the Javanese ethnic community, we really think about how to deal with various Javanese ethnic communities who have different characters. To get a solution to the problem you are going through, there are several first steps, we need to recognize what the problem actually is, then we look for facts or evidence of the following problem, after that we study and look for the background, then we can consider a solution.

Overcoming communication barriers can be done by increasing feedback so that in this way it can be made easier to find out whether the message or information has been received, understood and implemented or not. The delivery of the message must be adapted to the recipient's condition and repetition to ensure that the message can be understood using simple language, so that everyone can understand the content of the message conveyed. Determining effective timing and managing the flow of information needs to be considered so that the message conveyed by the recipient is ready to hear it and listens effectively so that interpersonal communication between subordinates and superiors can take place well.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of data analysis and research findings in Tanjung Marulak Hilir Village, Rambutan District, Tebing Tinggi City, conclusions can be drawn regarding the interpersonal communication strategy of the Javanese Master of Ceremony Manten at traditional Javanese wedding ceremonies in Tanjung Marulak Hilir Village, Rambutan District, Tebing Tinggi City, namely:

The communication strategy carried out by the Master of Ceremony Manten Java Tanjung Marulak Hilir at Javanese traditional ceremonies uses communication strategies with methods, namely (1) Redundancy, (2) Canalizing, (3) Educative.

The traditional Javanese wedding ceremony which was held in Tanjung Marulak Hilir Village was a Javanese wedding ceremony which was oriented towards the Yogyakarta School.

The series of traditional Javanese wedding ceremony processions, namely (1) Consent, (2) Ring exchange, (3) Panggih, (4) Balangan suruh, (5) Wiji dadi, (6) Dahar klimah, (7) Sungkeman.

The communication strategy that needs to be carried out by the Master of Ceremony Manten Java Tanjung Marulak Hilir at traditional Javanese wedding ceremonies, uses communication strategies with methods, (1) Redundancy, (2) Canalizing, (3) Informative, (4) Persuasive, (5) Educative, (6) Cursive.

Based on the findings and conclusions of this research, the researcher provides the following suggestions:

To the Master of Ceremony *Manten Jawa*, Tanjung Marulak Hilir, Rambutan District, please establish more communication with the Javanese community and have deliberations to design and create training modules and direct practice to become a Master of Ceremony *Manten Jawa* on an ongoing basis to improve the public speaking of the Javanese community in Tanjung Marulak District, Downstream, Rambutan District, Tebing Tinggi City.

To the Javanese traditional leaders of Tanjung Marulak Hilir Subdistrict, please take part in assisting the Master of Ceremony *Manten Jawa* in creating public speaking training for cultural institutions in improving the implementation of Javanese cultural activities or Javanese traditional processions other than wedding ceremonies so that Javanese culture is better known to the people of the area. Tanjung Marulak Hilir Village, Rambutan District, Tebing Tinggi City.

To the Javanese community in Tanjung Marulak Hilir Village, Rambutan District, please take part in deliberations in designing and creating public speaking training modules for *Pranata Adicara* and direct practice to become a Master of Ceremony *Manten Jawa* to promote and preserve Javanese culture in Tanjung Marulak Hilir Village, Rambutan Kota District High cliff.

To the people of other ethnic groups in Tanjung Marulak Hilir Village, Rambutan District, please participate in celebrating every traditional Javanese wedding ceremony and respect each other's cultures in Tanjung Marulak Hilir Village, Rambutan District, Tebing Tinggi City.

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